

**A phenomenological study of culture and cultural beliefs on ethnic minority
micro-business leaders in London.**

By

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Abstract

Micro-businesses are critically important for the economy with London seeing the greatest number of new start-ups in the UK in recent years. Approximately 20% of micro-business in London are owned by ethnic minorities and despite research exploring success factors for micro-businesses in general, there is little understanding of specific factors that impact on success of ethnic minority owned microbusinesses. Organisational culture guides how organisational decisions are made and how employees interact with each other and in micro-businesses the leader plays an influential role in shaping the organisational culture. National culture and religion may influence the organisational culture of ethnic minority-led micro-businesses through it leader, with calls seen in the literature to develop a greater understanding of those influences. Taking a phenomenological approach, the lived experiences of 15 ethnic minority leaders in London from a range of sectors were examined using Interpretive Phenomenological Analysis. Using paternalistic leadership theory as a theoretical lens, findings highlighted the role that religion played in guiding decisions around both their lives and their businesses and were centred around morality benevolence and authority. These findings contribute to practice by highlighting the need for business support, especially policies around financial support, consider the impact of religion on decision making. From a theoretical perspective the study also develops paternalistic leadership theory to emphasise the role of religion as a cross cutting influence in the dimensions of morality, benevolence, and authority when applied to ethnic minority leaders.

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1. Chapter One: Introduction

1.1 Background of study

The importance of micro-businesses, small and medium enterprises (SMEs) in a country's economy and social development is widely acknowledged (Haq *et al.*, 2023; Özer & Tinaztepe, 2014). Due to its importance and fragility, it commands huge interest from the government, policymakers, organisations, and researchers. Globalisation and technological advancement have increased small businesses' struggles with stiff competition, thus creating a saturated and hostile market environment (Haq, 2015).

London is the commercial centre of the UK and host of the largest population of ethnic minorities led businesses (20%) in the UK (Hutton, 2022; Ram *et al.*, 2022). It is a conducive and volatile market environment. According to Enterprise Research Centre (ERC, 2018) London has the highest number of new business creations and business failures in the UK. This view is supported by the Office of National Statistics (ONS, 2019). In London, ethnic minorities engage in micro-businesses despite the recorded high rate of business failure (Hutton, 2022; Whitehead *et al.*, 2006) with these ethnic businesses most likely to fail within five years (ERC, 2018). Argument as to why this is the case include individuals having easier access to starting micro-businesses, finance, or due to discrimination in the labour market making starting a business a financial necessity (ERC, 2018; Haq *et al.*, 2023). Among the of studies on small businesses, finance is highlighted as a significant failure factor, yet the leadership role of the owners and managers of micro-businesses is often ignored (Carter *et al.*, 2015; Mendy & Hack-Polay, 2018). The

leadership approach is vital for the survival of any business as it plays an essential role, together with management in the day-to-day operation of a business (Franco & Matos, 2015; Northouse, 2021). This is even more important in a small business, due to the hands-on approach of the owners and managers (Franco & Matos, 2015; Garavan *et al.*, 2016), and the lived experience of ethnic minority owners has the potential to shape their leadership approach through the influence of their national or familial culture.

The aims for the present study are to examine the leadership approach of ethnic minority-led micro-businesses in London through Hofstede cultural dimensions building on works by previous scholars (Beugelsdijk & Welzel, 2018; Jackson, 2020; Sent & Kroese, 2022) through the application of paternalistic leadership theory (Farh & Cheng, 2000). Paternalistic leadership theory develops a criticism of traditional leadership theories which took a historical Western lens by providing a non-Western leadership approach (Aycan *et al.*, 2000; Dickson *et al.*, 2003; Jackson, 2016), therefore provides a useful theoretical framework to explore the cultural influence in ethnic minority leadership behaviours.

A qualitative phenomenological approach has been adopted to explore the cultural influences on ethnic minority micro-business leaders in order to understand the participants' lived experiences and gain a rich understanding of the influences guiding their approach. The phenomenological research approach focuses on the experiential meaning and essence of an experience (Finlay, 2013; Moustakas, 1994) to enable the interpretation and analytical description of people's experiences from their perspective (Creswell & Poth, 2016). The chosen sample is the owners and managers of ethnic

minority micro-businesses with less than ten employees in London to fit with the aims of the study and the description of micro-business in the literature. This sample allows for the exploration of leadership behaviour and cultural influence of owner/managers of ethnic minority-led micro-businesses in London and their perceived effect on the success and failure on their businesses. Throughout this study, owners, or managers of businesses will be referred to as leaders. Those who are being led or work under a leader will be named followers, employees, or subordinates. The rest of this chapter provides an overview of the present study by introducing the rationale, research background and purpose of this study. Then the problem statement, aim and objectives will be presented, followed by a brief description of the significance of this study. Next, the research methodology and mode of data collection will be detailed. Finally, the outline and the structure of this study will be presented.

1.2 Rationale of the study

The primary aim for carrying out this research is the paucity of literature on ethnic minorities-led micro-businesses (Collins & Fakoussa, 2015; Haq *et al.*, 2023; Ram *et al.*, 2022) despite an abundance of literature on small businesses in general (Carter *et al.*, 2015). Focus of this literature continues to follow the narrow theme of their financial struggles (Carter *et al.*, 2015) with little understanding of the lived experiences of leaders of ethnic minority-led micro-businesses.

This purpose of the present study is to fill a void in the leadership, organisational, and management literature concerning ethnic minorities through contributing new insights on the influence of culture on leadership behaviour of ethnic minority-led micro-business

leaders in London, thereby enhancing our understanding in these domains. Paternalistic leadership theory is used as theoretical lens because of the non-Western foundation of the theory, rooted in Confucianism (Farh & Cheng, 2000). Confucianism is a belief system that extend beyond the socio-political aspects of society and encompasses spiritual elements or dimensions (Aycan, 2006; Chen *et al.*, 2014; Farh & Cheng, 2000). It forms the cultural and spiritual orientation of society in China (Farh & Cheng, 2000). Paternalistic leadership theory in this study has been applied with one of the prominent cultural frameworks for studying national culture and leadership in Hofstede's cultural framework (Beugelsdijk & Welzel, 2018; Jackson, 2020; Sent & Kroese, 2022) and thus answer the call to explore the cultural and religious influence on ethnic minority micro-business (Collins & Fakoussa, 2015).

London is the business hub of the UK and has the highest population of minority businesses (20%) in the UK (Hutton, 2022). However, ethnic minority businesses will likely not survive beyond five years according to Enterprise Research Centre (ERC, 2018). According to the Office of National Statistics ONS (2019), London leads the whole of the UK with new small business start-ups and has the highest rate of failed businesses in the UK (see Table 1). As seen below, London has the greatest proportion of new businesses, roughly 86,000 highlighting the economic importance of the city. Unfortunately, London also has the greatest number of business death, approximately 70,000 (Hutton, 2022). With a high proportion of these business death being ethnic minority micro-business (ERC, 2018), gaining a richer understanding on the factors that influence business decision making it important for the sustainability of these businesses.

Table 1. Business births and Deaths by region in the UK, 2021

	Birth	Death
North East	10,080	8,535
North West	39,135	33,895
Yorkshire and the Humber	24,985	22,060
East Midlands	23,370	21,530
West Midlands	34,155	31,255
East	33,150	31,195
London	85,305	69,860
South East	48,375	48,705
South West	25,930	23,300
Wales	13,945	12,145
Scotland	18,910	19,705
Northern Ireland	6,655	5,200
United Kingdom	363,995	327,385

Source: Hutton, 2022

1.3 Originality

Defining originality in doctoral research is a complex subjective matter with varying interpretations, creating challenges in its definition (Phillips & Pugh, 2007). The discussion on originality is prolonged and influenced by individual requirements across disciplines and countries (Edwards, 2014; Guetzkow *et al.*, 2004).

From the sociological standpoint, originality involves constructing new theories and findings (Guetzkow *et al.*, 2004). It requires doctoral students to contribute to existing knowledge while demonstrating independence, creativity, responsibility, and professionalism in their field of study (Edwards, 2014). According to Phillips & Pugh (2007), originality in a doctoral thesis entails advancing previous ideas and demonstrating relevance. From the point of view of the current study, theoretical originality comes from the application of paternalistic leadership theory with Hofstede's cultural dimensions to expand understanding of leadership behaviours in a novel way.

Phillips & Pugh (2007) produced nine definitions of originality based on interview with stakeholders, suggesting that achieving originality is feasible with any of the nine definitions of originality.

- Conduct an empirical study that has not been done anywhere in the world.
- Carrying out an original synthesis that has not been done before
- Applying existing knowledge in a new way
- Investigating something in Britain that has only been explored abroad
- Using a particular approach in a different way
- Finding new evidence for old topics or matter
- Being interdisciplinary and adopting new methodologies
- Looking at unexplored areas in a discipline
- Producing original ideas or new knowledge

This present study aligns with Phillips & Pugh (2007) definitions, by contributing new knowledge and advancing existing knowledge in leadership, cross-cultural leadership, and ethnic minority studies, with more details in Chapter 6.

1.4 Purpose of study

This purpose of the research is to understand better the cultural influence of the leadership approach of leaders of ethnic minority-led micro-businesses in London through the lived-experience of the business leaders with the aim of providing practical guidance for the sustainability of these businesses.

1.5 Problem Statement

Micro-businesses are critically important for the survival of any economy (Basu, 2004; Carter *et al.*, 2015; Choongo *et al.*, 2016; Fergie *et al.*, 2020; Gherhes *et al.*, 2016; Haq *et al.*, 2023; Olszak & Ziemba, 2012; Özer & Tinaztepe, 2014; Suriyankietkaew & Avery, 2016; Tan *et al.*, 2010). Many studies have been conducted to explore their success factors, strategies for sustainability and barriers in order to provide the necessary support or assistance for growth (Carter *et al.*, 2015; Choongo *et al.*, 2016; Fergie *et al.*, 2020; Gherhes *et al.*, 2016; Haq *et al.*, 2023; Mendy & Hack-Polay 2018; Ram & Jones, 2008). However, there is little on ethnic minority micro-businesses (Fergie *et al.*, 2020; Haq *et al.*, 2023). In the UK, London has the highest number of new start-ups (ONS, 2019). According to Hutton (2022), 20% of ethnic minority businesses call London home in 2021 and it has highest population of ethnic minorities in any one region in the UK (Hutton, 2022). Ethnic minorities are well represented in self-employment and small businesses in London and are drivers of regeneration (Carter *et al.*, 2015). London also

accounts for almost 50% of the population of ethnic minorities in England (Whitehead *et al.*, 2006) highlighting the economic importance of these businesses not just in the city itself but in England as a whole.

According to Hutton (2022) London has the most failed businesses in the UK and studies have focused mostly on the financial struggles of small businesses with little on the role of the leadership behaviour and decisions (ONS, 2019). The high failure rate of small businesses in London has led to the government providing various schemes to curb the failure rate and alleviate the challenges of small businesses in London (Barrett *et al.*, 2001). These broad solutions mostly surround financial assistance ignoring the unique issue of leadership and cultural influences on micro and small businesses (Al Mamun *et al.*, 2018; Arslan *et al.*, 2022; Aziz *et al.*, 2013; Birbirs & Lakew, 2020). Despite government interventions, the number of failed businesses in London remain high, with 69,860 business death in 2021, compared to the second highest region, the Southeast region of the UK, with 48,705 business death, as indicated in Table 1 (Hutton, 2022).

1.6 Aim and Objectives

The aim is to examine the leadership approach and cultural influence of the leadership experiences of leaders of ethnic minority-led micro-businesses in London. To achieve this aim, the following objectives were established:

- i. To explore the leadership style of the leaders of ethnic minority-led micro-businesses in London.
- ii. To examine the cultural influence of the leadership approach of the leaders of ethnic minority-led micro-business in London.

iii. To explore the leadership behaviour of the leaders of ethnic minority-led micro-businesses in London in relation to their business success.

1.7 Research Question

How does culture and cultural belief influence ethnic minority micro-business leaders' experience of leading their business?

1.8 Significance of the study

Theoretically, this study is of significance through the use of a non-Western leadership theory in combination with cultural theory. From an applied research perspective, it will contribute to and extend the existing body of knowledge on leadership and ethnic minority-led micro-businesses. As seen in Table 2, micro-businesses are the majority, mostly a one-man business with a hands-on approach, which makes leadership integral to its success (Arslan *et al.*, 2022; BEIS, 2022; Ram *et al.*, 2022). Leadership is a barrier to the growth of SMEs (Morrison, 2003; Nanjundeswaraswamy & Swamy, 2014) but the majority of attention is given to their financial performances and struggles (Carter *et al.*, 2015), disregarding the role of the leader in managing resources such as finance (Mendy & Hack-Polay, 2018).

Ethnic minorities have a significant presence in London and engage heavily in micro-businesses (Hutton, 2022; Whitehead *et al.*, 2006). However, their businesses are most likely to fail in London due to financial issues (ERC, 2018) highlighting the role in leaders' decision making to manage limited resources. Also, London has the highest number of failed small businesses in the UK (ONS, 2019). Their challenges are well

documented, but there is a scarcity of literature on ethnic minority leadership (Chin, 2013; Okozi *et al.*, 2009). Thus, it is important to understand the leadership style and behaviour of the leaders of ethnic minorities-led micro-businesses to gain a richer knowledge base related to business success and failure beyond just finance.

Table 2. Estimated number of businesses in the UK private sector and their associated employment and turnover, by size of the business, start of 2022.

	Businesses	Employment Thousands	Turnovers £ millions
All business	5,508,935	27,054	4,156,773
SMEs (0-249 employees)	5,501,260	16,432	2,124,439
Small business (0-49 employees)	5,465,320	12,935	1,416,907
With no employees	4,061,035	4,399	277,599
All employers Of which:	1,477,900	22,655	3,879,174
1-9 employees	1,187,054	4,308	530,456
10-49	217,240	4,228	608,852
50-249	35,940	3,497	707,532
250 or more employees	7,675	10,622	2,032,334

Source: BEIS, 2022, Business population estimate for the UK and regions, Statistical release.

Practically, this study is adding to the knowledge on leadership and ethnic minority-led micro-businesses to be able to provide sources of guidance for policymakers and business leaders. Moreover, this study will help understand how leadership behaviour and culture influences their business growth to give the government and policymakers an alternate perspective on the challenges of ethnic minority micro-businesses rather than on the finance or financial challenges of SMEs (Carter *et al.*, 2015).

1.9 Research Methodology

The methodology for this research is qualitative to achieve the aim of capturing the essence of the participants' experiences from their perspectives (Mohajan, 2018). The qualitative research provides a detailed, nuanced understanding of social phenomena such as the role of leadership behaviour in micro-business (Mohajan, 2018; Queirós *et al.*, 2017) and allows for the capture of the context and complexity of human behaviour and beliefs from the perspective of the individual or population being studied, in this case the ethnic minority leaders (Mohajan, 2018; Queirós *et al.*, 2017). Qualitative research helps in understanding phenomena within their specific cultural, social, and historical contexts, providing a holistic view of the subject under study (Mohajan, 2018; Queirós *et al.*, 2017). Often, it contributes to the development or refinement of theories by providing rich qualitative data that can be analysed and interpreted in theoretical frameworks (Mohajan, 2018). In this case, paternalistic leadership theory and Hofstede's cultural dimensions. A qualitative approach emphasises the perspectives of participants, giving a voice to individuals and communities whose experiences might be marginalised or

underrepresented, for example, ethnic minorities (Mohajan, 2018; Queirós *et al.*, 2017). Qualitative research findings can inform policy-making and practical interventions by providing insights into the needs, challenges, and experiences of specific groups or communities like ethnic minority leaders in London (Mohajan, 2018).

The research approach for this study is phenomenology which concentrate on sense-making and the meaning attached to people's experiences (Mohajan, 2018; Neubauer *et al.*, 2019). The purpose of phenomenological research is to explore and understand individuals' lived experiences, perceptions, and meanings attributed to a specific phenomenon or phenomena (Mohajan, 2018; Neubauer *et al.*, 2019). Phenomenology aims to uncover the essence of human experiences and gain insight into the subjective perspectives of individuals involved in a particular situation or phenomenon (Creswell & Poth, 2016; Mohajan, 2018; Van Manen, 2016). Researchers conducting phenomenological studies seek to comprehend the underlying structures of these experiences, allowing for a deeper understanding of the phenomenon from the participant's point of view (Finlay, 2013; Neubauer *et al.*, 2019) making it a suitable approach to explore the inner world and cultural beliefs of ethnic minority micro-business leaders. This qualitative research approach focuses on describing and interpreting the intricate aspects of being a leader of a micro-business in London from an ethnic minority background, shedding light on the complexities of human consciousness and perception (Mohajan, 2018).

Qualitative studies are common in behavioural science (Farh & Cheng, 2000). However, a large amount of literature on leadership has focused and adopted either a

quantitative or mixed method while attempting to measure leadership values, features and characteristics or compare the effectiveness of various leadership styles (Ardichvili, 2001; Chin, 2013; Frank & Matos, 2015; House *et al.*, 2004; Ngoc Khuong *et al.*, 2022). This approach is reductive and may miss the nuance of experience between and within leaders. As such, the present study aims to understand and explore the meaning of the participants' experiences to provide a rich picture of what it means to be a leader of a micro-business from an ethnic minority background in London rather than reach any reductive conclusion through statistical calculations (Creswell & Poth, 2016).

The mode of data collection adopted in this study is a semi-structured interview. This mode is flexible, suitable for qualitative data and a reliable source of data collection in a phenomenological study (Creswell & Poth, 2016; Mohajan, 2018; Moustakas, 1994; Scotland, 2012). A qualitative phenomenological analysis was conducted following six steps as present in Chapter 3. In addition, the sample is purposive and snowballing sampling in order to recruit the specific group of people with shared experiences and specific features that are relevant to this study to achieve informative and rich data (Creswell & Poth, 2016). Chapter 3 provides detailed clarification of the methodology for this present study, complemented by a virtual representation in Figure 1 within the same chapter.

1.10 Outline of the study

Chapter 1 introduces the research background, the rationale for the study, the research question, and the aim and objectives. A brief description of the research methodology, structure, contribution to existing research and a summary is presented.

Chapter 2 presents a literature review of ethnic minority micro-businesses. It provides a comprehensive review of relevant literature and identifies gaps in ethnic minority micro-businesses and leadership literature. Also, it introduces the leadership theory of paternalistic leadership and a relevant cultural leadership framework for understanding leadership behaviour in Hofstede cultural framework. Further, Chapter 3 discusses the methodology adopted in this study and provides the rationale behind using a qualitative phenomenological approach that informs the research method. While Chapter 4 focuses on the identification and interpretation of emerging themes through a multilevel analysis of the data collected. Chapter 5 discusses the findings of this study in relation to the research objectives, aim and question. Finally, Chapter 6 conclude the present study, it provides a summary of key findings and an overview of the research process. It also acknowledges this study's contributions and limitations and suggests areas for further research.

2. Chapter Two: Literature Review

2.1 Introduction

The following chapter presents a review of academic and professional literature on the cultural influence of the leaders of ethnic minority micro-businesses in London, ethnic minority entrepreneurship and their leadership approach. The justification for the theoretical framework of paternalistic leadership theory, due being a recognised non-Western leadership style, is presented. Also, Hofstede's cultural theory is explored to better understand the influence of culture on the leadership behaviour of ethnic minority-led micro-businesses. Religious influence on ethnic minorities is also explored within the context of culture to provide an additional lens of the cultural influence on ethnic minority micro-business leaders.

2.2 Ethnic Minority Group

According to ONS (2021a), the combined population of England and Wales was 59.6 million. Among this, 18% (10.9 million) belonged to Asia, black, mixed, and other ethnic minority groups, showing an increase from 13.8% in 2011. The breakdown of ethnic minority groups in the UK includes people from Asian backgrounds who constitute the second largest ethnic group with (9.3%), followed by black (4.0%), mixed (2.9%), and other (2.1%) ethnic groups (ONS, 2021a). Ethnic minority group-led businesses, like any other SMEs, are instrumental in fostering a sustainable economy (Haq *et al.*, 2023; Mendy & Hack-Polay, 2018). They can be referred to as unconscious government agencies as they actively work to reduce the burden on the government by providing revenue, employment, expansion in different industries, the revival of

declining sectors, and the development of new technology and communities (Carter *et al.*, 2015).

Ethnic minority-led businesses are small businesses where the sole proprietor is from an ethnic minority group or where fifty per cent (50%) or more of the partners or directors in the daily control of the business are people from ethnic minority groups (BIS, 2012; Haq *et al.*, 2023). The majority of ethnic minority-owned businesses are micro firms employing less than ten employees and mostly in London (Haq *et al.*, 2023; Whitehead *et al.*, 2006) with more than 50% operating in London (see Table 3). Ethnic minority micro-business leaders have a hands-on approach to their business, and leaders are critical to the survival of businesses (Al Mamun *et al.*, 2018; Arslan *et al.*, 2022; Garavan *et al.*, 2016; Ram *et al.*, 2022; Wang & Altinay, 2012). The study of ethnic minority businesses has witnessed an accelerated interest over time (Mendy & Hack-Polay, 2018; Ram & Jones, 2008). Although in isolation from leadership style (Carter *et al.*, 2015) and under-researched in the context of micro-businesses (Haq *et al.*, 2021).

The paucity of information regarding ethnic minority businesses can be attributed to the unavailability of high quality and accurate data (Hyde, 2020). Existing data often lacks the necessary details or elements, thereby obscuring the full understanding of the experiences of the diverse ethnic minority groups (Hyde, 2022). Scholars in ethnic minority and business field have identified the inadequacies in the data available and accessible to researchers and policymakers (Kašperová *et al.*, 2022). Therefore, there is need to contribute to existing knowledge on ethnic minority micro-businesses in a practical way that benefits the sustainability of these businesses.

The terms or acronyms EMG and EMB represent ethnic minority groups and ethnic minority businesses, and they are easy ways to describe businesses owned and managed by ethnic minorities as used in this study. Ethnicity is an idea only relevant when making comparisons between groups (Berthoud, 1998). There is an ongoing debate about the use of the label or term EMG or EMB as they are seen as ambiguous and controversial, and care should be taken in their usage (Carter *et al.*, 2015). Ethnicity is used as an umbrella name to represent people from different racial or ethnic groups here in the UK and by doing so, denies these unique groups of people their identity (Berthoud, 1998). Also, these terms are often rejected by those meeting the definition of ethnic minorities because it suggests a White majority (Carter *et al.*, 2015) and fails to reflect the balance of ethnic diversity globally. Most ethnic minority business owners and managers avoid using these terms and avoid referring to themselves as an ethnic minority business (Carter *et al.*, 2015). The 1991 census in Britain shows an increase in the use of the word ethnicity in attempts to describe minority groups in a multicultural society (Berthoud, 1998) with the indication that:

“Ethnicity is a multi-faceted phenomenon based on some or all of several possible ingredients: physical appearance, subjective identification, cultural and religious affiliation, stereotyping and social exclusion” (Berthoud, 1998, pg.54). As such ethnicity and ethnic minority research is complex, with meaning and language dependent upon a researcher’s philosophy, life-world, and perspective.

Ethnicity is a collective term used as an identifier to group people based on their race, language, religion, nationality and so on (Venkatesh, 1995). It is an idea created to describe a group that is culturally and physically different to the dominant culture or group. This suggests ethnicity can only be experienced when a person is different, or a minority based on their race, language, religion, and nationality. However, ethnicity

should not be used as a characteristic to define ethnic minority businesses (Carter *et al.*, 2015) and as such the acronyms EMG or EMB will not be adopted in this study to reflect the sensitivity towards these terms. Instead, the whole term ethnic minority groups and businesses are adopted, however, caution is applied in their usage. The terms owner/managers of ethnic minority-led micro-businesses, ethnic minority-led micro-businesses, ethnic minority groups, ethnic minority small businesses and ethnic minority entrepreneurs are used interchangeably in this study to describe non-White and immigrant micro-business leaders regardless of their nationality or considered ethnic minority.

The focus for this present study is ethnic minority micro-businesses in London. It has the largest population of ethnic minorities (see Table 3), and their businesses are mostly micro-businesses (Gherhes *et al.*, 2016; Haq *et al.*, 2023; Hutton, 2022). Given the large proportion of these businesses within London, they are of economic importance not only to London but the wider UK economy.

Table 3. Ethnicity by Areas of England and Wales

Area	Asian %	Black %	Mixed %	White British %	White other %	Other %
East Midlands	8.0	2.7	2.4	79.6	6.1	1.3
East of England	6.4	2.9	2.8	78.5	8.0	1.4
London	20.7	13.5	5.7	36.8	17.0	6.3
North East	3.7	1.0	1.3	90.6	2.5	1.0
North West	8.4	2.3	2.2	81.2	4.4	1.5

South East	7.0	2.4	2.8	78.8	7.5	1.5
South West	2.8	1.2	2.0	87.8	5.3	0.9
Wales	2.9	0.9	1.6	90.6	3.3	0.9
West Midlands	13.3	4.5	3.0	71.8	5.2	2.1
Yorkshire and The Humber	8.9	2.1	2.1	80.9	4.5	1.4

Source: ONS, 2022

Ethnic minority-led businesses operate within their communities (Altinay, 2010; Gbadamosi, 2015; Jones *et al.*, 2019), and capture the ready market, cheap labour, and community support available to them (Hyde, 2022; Jones *et al.*, 2019). These communities serve as a safe space or a haven for new and existing ethnic minority micro and small businesses (Ram & Jones, 2008). Ethnic minorities rely on and incorporate their culture and belief system which sometimes includes religion into their business and leadership approach, and this behaviour can determine the kind of business they engage in or the leadership behaviour they display or exhibit (Nwankwo *et al.*, 2012; Ospina & Foldy, 2009).

Ram & Jones (2008) highlights how the second generations of migrants were well equipped for business opportunities and easily capture available opportunities through the changing demographics of educational levels and skill. In addition, ethnic minority groups have been shown to be engaging more in the knowledge economy through the internet to expand their ideas and businesses to a broader market appeal, away from their traditional sectors or labour-intensive businesses like micro- business (Dabić *et al.*, 2020; Jones *et al.*, 2019). Also, Ram & Jones (2008) explained how the

Chinese and Indians became highly educated and followed the business route as an opportunistic venture, not the stereotypical business borne out of necessity.

However, the differences between micro-businesses and SMEs in terms of size, structure, and impact on the economy can be used to create targeted support programs for ethnic minority micro-businesses and SMEs, promote entrepreneurship, and foster economic development and growth (Gherhes *et al.*, 2016; Lussier & Sonfield, 2015).

2.3 Ethnic Minority Micro-business

According to Haq *et al.* (2023), businesses owned by ethnic minorities primarily fall under the category of micro-businesses, characterised by either no employee or less than ten employees (Haq *et al.*, 2023). According to BVA BDRC (2023) it is suggested that 98% of ethnic minority businesses are micro-businesses. They are visibly represented in London, and in the wholesale and retail sectors (Hutton, 2022; Hyde, 2022). These businesses exhibit a higher level of innovation in their approaches and experience rapid growth compared to non-ethnic minority micro-businesses (Dabić *et al.*, 2020; Haq *et al.*, 2021; Haq *et al.*, 2023; Hyde, 2022). Consequently, ethnic minority micro-businesses are widely recognised as driving forces for local, regional, and national economic development in many countries (Haq *et al.*, 2023; Ram *et al.*, 2022).

However, they are under-researched (Collins & Fakoussa, 2015; Haq *et al.*, 2023; Ram *et al.*, 2022), and mainstream business and management literature seldom address or discuss ethnic minority micro-businesses (Haq *et al.*, 2023; Ram *et al.*, 2022). They are also ignored in government policymaking (Haq *et al.*, 2023). A frequently cited reason for not addressing ethnic minority micro-businesses by popular

or conventional entrepreneurship researcher is the inaccessibility of these type of businesses or the knowledge they yield are considered as inconsequential (Haq *et al.*, 2023). Similarly, the difficulty in gaining access to ethnic minority micro-businesses maybe because of cultural and language barrier and lack of trust (Collins & Fakoussa, 2015). Furthermore, discrimination and being perceived as underdogs may explain why ethnic minority micro-businesses receive less attention from government and policymakers (Haq *et al.*, 2023). Ram *et al.*, (2022) referred to the oversight on ethnic minority micro-businesses as “surprising” (Ram *et al.*,2022, pg. 541). The paucity of information regarding ethnic minority businesses can be attributed to the unavailability of high quality and accurate data which often lacks the necessary elements for detailed insight, thereby obscuring the full understanding of the experiences of the diverse ethnic minority groups (Hyde, 2022). Scholars in the ethnic minority and business field have identified the inadequacies in the data available and accessible to researchers and policymakers (Haq *et al.*, 2023; Kašperová *et al.*, 2022). Therefore, high quality and insightful data is needed to fully understand the factors at play in the success of ethnic minority business.

Research on ethnic minorities micro-businesses are either on ethnic entrepreneurship (Dabić *et al.*, 2020; Daniel *et al.*, 2019; Ramadani *et al.*,2014; Volery, 2007), and human and capital resources (Haq *et al.*, 2023; Ram *et al.*, 2022), ethnic minority family businesses (Collins & Fakoussa, 2015) and survival, barriers or challenges to ethnic minority business (Arslan *et al.*, 2022; Carter *et al.*, 2015; Ishaq, 2010; Rahman *et al.*, 2018). A recent systematic literature review highlights the key themes within the ethnic minority business research area focus on migration, diversity, networks, and culture (Moro *et al.*, 2023). While Haq *et al.*, (2023) investigated how ethnic minority create human capital resources and the impact of these resources on

their performance in the Yorkshire area of the UK. Also, Ram *et al.* (2022) research interest was in human resource development program in ethnic minority micro-businesses. They felt there is a missed opportunity by the human resource profession and local business practitioners to collaborate.

It is noteworthy to say there are limited studies who focused on ethnic minority micro-businesses (Haq *et al.*, 2023; Ram *et al.*, 2022), but they did not address the cultural influence on the leadership behaviour of ethnic minority micro-business leaders. Existing literature often overlooks or insufficiently address ethnic minority micro-business, as evidence by the absence of any mention of ethnic minority micro-business in Moro *et al.* (2023) review of literature on ethnic minority businesses. Hence the focus of this current study on the leadership of ethnic minority micro-businesses to understand their experiences and add to existing knowledge on ethnic minority micro-businesses because of the economic importance they play within London and the UK.

Ethnic minority micro-businesses, typically those with fewer than ten employees, face considerable resource constraints, compared to large, medium, and small firms. They often present greater challenges for researchers and external stakeholders seeking to gain access to them (Haq *et al.*, 2023; Ram *et al.*, 2022). Also, there are indications that ethnic minority businesses have a high failure rate (Mendy & Hack-Polay, 2018; Whitehead *et al.*, 2006). Entrepreneurship literature acknowledges the difficulties faced by small and non-local businesses (Haq *et al.*, 2023). Ethnic minority businesses fall into this category as they are small and mostly immigrants (non-local), meaning they encounter both challenges (Haq *et al.*, 2023; Ram *et al.*, 2022). Despite these constraints, ethnic minority micro-businesses

continue to make significant contributions to economic turnover and employment levels (Haq *et al.*, 2023).

Micro-business

Micro-businesses are a subset of (SMEs) and have distinct experiences and challenges due to their size (Al Mamun *et al.*, 2018; Gherhes *et al.*, 2016; Granata *et al.*, 2018). They account for most private businesses in most countries (Haq *et al.*, 2023; Masiak *et al.*, 2019). They are integral to the development of any economy (Al Mamun *et al.*, 2018; Granata *et al.*, 2018; Haq *et al.*, 2023; Masiak *et al.*, 2019). Despite their crucial role in national economies, there is a dearth of literature on micro-businesses (Fergie *et al.*, 2020). Moreover, most ethnic minority businesses are micro-businesses, accounting for 98% of micro-businesses in the UK (BVA BDRC, 2023; Gherhes *et al.*, 2016; Haq *et al.*, 2023; Lussier & Sonfield, 2015), facing unique challenges (Masiak *et al.*, 2019; Ram *et al.*, 2022). The leaders within these businesses are required to manage scarce resources effectively to help the business develop and survive (Arslan *et al.*, 2022; Birbirsa & Lakew, 2020; Nabella *et al.*, 2022; Ram *et al.*, 2022). The ability to make decisions and manage resources is significantly vested in the leader of a business (Arslan *et al.*, 2022; Birbirsa & Lakew, 2020; Fergie *et al.*, 2020; Gherhes *et al.*, 2016; Lussier & Sonfield, 2015; Wang & Altinay, 2012). This underscores the critical importance of effective leadership for the survival and growth of small businesses (Al Mamun *et al.*, 2018; Arslan *et al.*, 2022; Aziz *et al.*, 2013; Birbirsa & Lakew, 2020; Madanchian & Taherdoost 2017; Özer & Tinaztepe, 2014).

While the importance of leadership is universally acknowledged across businesses it holds particular significance for the growth and success of small

businesses (Fergie *et al.*, 2020; Nabella *et al.*, 2022). A few studies on SMEs have identified leadership as a driver and a key factor for a successful SME (Bakås *et al.*, 2011; Bolden & Terry, 2000; Fergie *et al.*, 2020; Franco & Matos, 2015; Ghosh *et al.*, 2001; Hung *et al.*, 2011; Ram *et al.*, 2022; Wong, 2005). Leaders help to formulate organisational culture and take critical decisions to help small businesses survive, grow, and become highly competitive (Hyde, 2022; Ram *et al.*, 2022). However, within the domain of small businesses, especially in the micro-business sector, there exists a notable absence of literature focusing on leadership development (Fergie *et al.*, 2020). Some studies have indicated that the behaviour of ethnic minority micro-business leaders is influenced by their cultural and religious values, impacting both their personal lives and business strategies (Altinay, 2010; Dabić *et al.*, 2020; Hofstede, 2011; Mendy & Polay 2018). However, there is still a significant gap in understanding how these cultural influences affect the leaders of ethnic minority micro-businesses.

2.3.1 Definition of Micro-business

The definition of micro-business varies globally and lacks consistency (Haq, 2015). According to the Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) 2023, micro-businesses are businesses with zero to nine employees or is described as a firm with less than ten employees (Gherhes *et al.*, 2016; Haq *et al.*, 2023; Masiak *et al.*, 2019). This study adopts the definition of micro-business by OECD (2023), which referred to one with no employees and up to a maximum of nine employees. Micro-businesses are small, owner-operated, flexible, and have limited resources with 0-9 employees, compared to SMEs, which are slightly larger, have a more established structure, and can have up to 250 employees (Gherhes *et al.*, 2016;

Masiak *et al.*, 2019).

Some studies tend to treat SMEs as uniform entities, lacking specific distinctions, by grouping micro-businesses together with small businesses or SMEs (Birbirsa & Lakew, 2020; Ishak *et al.*, 2021; Masiak *et al.*, 2019; Mendy & Hack-Polay, 2018). This practice may partly explain and contribute to the limited literature available on micro-businesses (Masiak *et al.*, 2019). Gherhes *et al.* (2016) explored the differences between micro-businesses and SMEs and concluded that micro-businesses and SMEs have distinct characteristics and contribute to the economy. For example, micro-businesses provide employment opportunities, they have zero to less than ten employees, contribute to local communities and are innovative (Haq *et al.*, 2023). In contrast, SMEs have between ten to forty-nine employees, drive economic growth and innovation Gherhes *et al.*, 2016; Haq *et al.*, 2023). Gherhes *et al.* (2016) posited that their findings can be used to create targeted support programs, promote entrepreneurship, and foster economic growth. Their study creates an understanding of the distinct characteristics and contributions of micro-businesses and SMEs, which can inform policy decisions and support the development of these businesses (Gherhes *et al.*, 2016). Despite their differences, both types of businesses contribute to the economy in their own ways (Gherhes *et al.*, 2016; Haq *et al.*, 2023; Lussier & Sonfield, 2015; Masiak *et al.*, 2019).

Micro-firms account for roughly 96% of all businesses in the UK (Fergie *et al.*, 2020; Gherhes *et al.*, 2016). They are one of the largest employers of labour, with 32% and 19% turnover in the UK (Hutton, 2022). They account for 5.2 million businesses, 95% of all firms in the UK in 2022, which is a massive increase in numbers from 2018 (Hutton, 2022). Micro-businesses provide employment opportunities, contribute to

local communities and are the engine room for societies (Gherhes *et al.*, 2016; Haq *et al.*, 2023; Masiak *et al.*, 2019).

However, there is no clear understanding of the unique challenges of micro-businesses (Fergie *et al.*, 2020; Gherhes *et al.*, 2016). Micro-businesses face many challenges and disadvantages: limited resources, lack of scalability, vulnerability to market changes, limited access to funding, lack of specialisation, limited capacity for innovation, reliance on the owner, marketing, branding challenges, difficulty in attracting and retaining talent, lack of bargaining power, limited economies of scale, difficulty in accessing support and resources and lack of leadership or managerial skill (Gherhes *et al.*, 2016; Haq *et al.*, 2023; Lussier & Sonfield, 2015; Masiak *et al.*, 2019). These disadvantages can impact the competitiveness and growth potential of micro-businesses (Ram *et al.*, 2022). Additionally, recognising the distinctions in size, structure, and economic impact between micro-businesses and SMEs can inform tailored support initiatives for ethnic minority businesses (Gherhes *et al.*, 2016). This approach aims to stimulate entrepreneurship, contributing to economic development and growth (Gherhes *et al.*, 2016; Lussier & Sonfield, 2015).

2.3.2 Micro-businesses in London

Micro-businesses play a vital role in London's economy, contributing to economic growth, job creation, and the fabric of local communities (London Assembly, 2018). There are 1 million micro-businesses across London, constituting 96% of all businesses in London (London Assembly, 2018). Notably, not all micro-businesses aspire to expand rapidly, as many are focused on a more fundamental and significant concern: survival (London Assembly, 2018). London has the highest population of ethnic minority groups and businesses in the UK (Hutton, 2022; ONS, 2022). The

percentage of each ethnic minority group that is most likely to live in London is as follows: Black (58.4 %), Asians (35.9 %), Mixed ethnicities (33.1%), and Other ethnic groups (49.9%), according to Ethnicity, Facts and Figures (ONS, 2022). Hutton (2022) reported that in 2022, London had 1.0 million private sector businesses, which is the most of all businesses in the UK. London also has the highest number of new businesses in 2021, with 85,305 new start-ups, as well as the highest number of failed businesses at 69,860 in 2021 in the UK (Hutton, 2022). Despite being perceived as a region with abundant supply of opportunities, London, as indicated earlier by its significant number of failed businesses, can also be a hostile environment for businesses (London Assembly, 2018).

The London Assembly survey “What works for micro-businesses in London” highlighted the provision of the right support for micro-businesses in London. According to the report, in London alone, micro-businesses have made significant contributions to the economy, generating 277.3 billion in turnover in 2018, accounting for 27% of the city's total turnover, creating 282,000 jobs over the past five years, and being the fastest-growing business category in London (London Assembly, 2018). In addition, the report sheds light on the challenges faced by micro-businesses in London, including difficulties in attracting new customers and expanding into new markets, concerns about the high cost of doing business in London, struggles with income volatility primarily due to late payments, and worries about finding suitable workspaces or retail spaces (London Assembly, 2018). Rising living and rental costs in London have made it increasingly challenging for micro-businesses to secure affordable spaces, as the city's costly new-builds often do not consider micro-businesses and their needs. Interestingly, the report revealed that micro-businesses are eager to learn from peers of a similar size through direct interactions, co-working

events, or participation in trade associations (London Assembly, 2018).

Nevertheless, accessing business support in the UK remains challenges for them (London Assembly, 2018). Securing finance and coping with high operating costs in London are key concerns for ethnic minority micro-businesses, emphasising the necessity of understanding their dynamics to tackle these issues (Arslan *et al.*, 2022; Haq, 2015). However, it is noteworthy to say that ethnic minority micro-businesses have received less attention from the mainstream literature in the field of business and management (Fergie *et al.*, 2020; Haq *et al.*, 2023).

2.3.3 Micro-business Challenges

Businesses are faced with complex challenges due to globalisation, technological development, and the consistent and rapid changes in the business environment (Suriyankietkaew & Avery, 2016). It makes it more challenging for small business owners and managers with traditional practices, business as usual approach, and ill-equipped to keep up and cope with the new pace of conducting business (Alves *et al.*, 2020; Olszak & Ziemba, 2012; Özer & Tinaztepe, 2014; Suriyankietkaew & Avery, 2016). Crises are natural events in business, sometimes firm size plays a crucial role in determining how businesses withstand crises or shocks (Alves *et al.*, 2020; Miklian & Hoelscher, 2022). Micro and small businesses typically operate with limited resources and have less influence over their external environment (Alves *et al.*, 2020; Miklian & Hoelscher, 2022). Consequently, they are more susceptible to the impact of shock, face greater challenges in recovering and are at a higher risk of failing during a crisis compared to large firms (Miklian & Hoelscher, 2022). Small businesses encounter additional hurdles during crises, such as tighter lending restrictions, restricted access to capital, limited financial and managerial capabilities, over-reliance

on a small market and limited ability to adapt and react to disruptive shocks (Miklian & Hoelscher, 2022). However, micro-businesses may have an advantage and survive crisis due to their size which gives them the ability to innovate and make decisions quickly (Haq *et al.*, 2023). But they remain very vulnerable and show weaker performance compared to large firms (Miklian & Hoelscher, 2022).

Ethnic minority-led businesses are more susceptible to experiencing a business crisis or are more likely to fail (ERC, 2018; Franco & Matos, 2015; Mendy & Hack-Polay, 2018). One potential reason for this failure was suggested to be through a tendency to lack future planning and crisis management strategies (Razzak *et al.*, 2023). Being resilient is critical to the survival of small businesses, and ethnic minority micro-businesses are less resilient (Arslan *et al.*, 2022; Battisti & Deakins, 2017; Cowling *et al.*, 2020). COVID-19 exposed their fragility, with many unable to survive due to government restrictions on essential and non-essential businesses (Arslan *et al.*, 2022; Battisti & Deakins, 2017; Cowling *et al.*, 2020). Contemporary research has highlighted small businesses often do not possess formal business plans or contingency plans (Razzark *et al.*, 2023). Notwithstanding, small businesses, for example micro-businesses, have a good chance to survive during crisis as the size of small firms is also their advantage (Alves *et al.*, 2020; Miklian & Hoelscher, 2022). It makes them able to react to crises easily and quickly and sometimes, out of necessity, small businesses can take advantage of opportunities that become available as a result of a crisis (Miklian & Hoelscher, 2022).

One of the primary challenges faced by ethnic minority micro-businesses is limited access to finance (Arslan *et al.*, 2022; Haq *et al.*, 2021; Howell, 2019; London Assembly, 2018; Rahman *et al.*, 2018; Ram *et al.*, 2017; Sithas & Surangi, 2021). Studies have shown that ethnic minority business leaders often encounter difficulties

in securing loans and funding for their businesses (Gbadamosi, 2015; Howell, 2019). They are either denied loans or discouraged from having one compared to non-ethnic minorities (Gbadamosi, 2015). Also, it was reported that access to finance is the most cited barrier faced by ethnic minority micro-businesses, evidently, Black and African Caribbean firms (Mendy & Hack-Polay, 2018; Smallbone *et al.*, 2003). The fear of rejection was claimed to be the reason behind the high level of discouragement of ethnic minority groups from applying for loans (Carter *et al.*, 2015). It was reported that 44% of Black Africans, 39% of Black Caribbeans, 31% of Bangladeshi, 21% of Pakistanis and 9% of Indians businesses said fear of rejection had discouraged them from taking loans that their businesses required compared to 6% of non-ethnic minority firms (Carter *et al.*, 2015). This lack of access to financial resources hampers their ability to expand operations, invest in technology, and compete effectively in the market (Arslan *et al.*, 2022).

It has been well documented that ethnic minority businesses face significant hurdles in securing financing (Gbadamosi, 2015). Consequently, the UK government established an Ethnic Minority Business taskforce to examine various issues, including the causes behind unfavourable credit outcomes, higher rates of loan denials, and increased interest payments among ethnic minority business owners (Gbadamosi, 2015). Also, Mendy & Hack-Polay (2018) Identified a lack of access to capital and slack management as part of the reason ethnic minority micro-businesses fail. Also, they asserted that the failure rate of ethnic minority businesses in the UK is high compared to non-minority businesses. Further, research conducted in China underscores the financial challenges faced by ethnic minority micro-businesses (Howell, 2019). The study illustrates the crucial role finance plays in any business, particularly in the context of ethnic minority micro-businesses (Howell, 2019). The

study's conclusion revealed that when businesses from the ethnic majority were given similar access to external finances or were placed in similar situations as ethnic minority micro-businesses, they encountered comparable difficulties, and as a result, the performance disparity between the two ethnic groups was non-existence (Howell, 2019).

Ethnic discrimination has been identified as a significant obstacle hindering access to finance for ethnic minority micro-businesses (Sithas & Surangi, 2021). In addition, certain critical factors, including limited business comprehension, language barrier, distrust, limited knowledge of the laws, and unfamiliarity with the larger society's culture, elucidate why ethnic minority businesses struggle to secure financial support (Sithas & Surangi, 2021). The difficulties of the leader or manager of small firms accessing finance can also be associated with discrimination of some of their personal characteristics such as race, ethnicity, gender, age, and education (Campanella & Serino, 2019; Nguyen & Canh, 2021). Financial decisions by financial institutions or lending officers on loan applications have been shown to be influenced by characteristics of the leader or managers of small businesses (Campanella & Serino, 2019; Nguyen & Canh, 2021). However, understanding the processes underpinning these decisions is complex with sensitivities and ethical consideration is needed to conduct detailed research in this area.

Research on ethnic minorities indicates that they are more inclined to establish their own businesses in comparison to the indigenous population, primarily due to the prevalent negative discrimination directed at them (Haq, 2015). Extant literature has emphasised the systematic discrimination faced by ethnic minority micro-business leaders in the UK job market and by financial institutions (Haq, 2015; Haq *et al.*, 2023).

Scholars have substantiated the challenges faced by minorities, highlighting their differences from larger communities across various dimensions (Sithas & Surangi, 2021). These differences include racial, religious, colour, nationality, and cultural differences, which subject minorities to discriminatory behaviour and racial violations by the mainstream population, impeding their integration into the labour market (Sithas & Surangi, 2021). Additionally, distrust and discrimination, including difficulties establishing connections with larger communities, have been identified as significant factors contributing to ethnic business failures in recent empirical studies (Sithas & Surangi, 2021).

Haq (2015) provides a compelling argument about ethnic minority micro-businesses that discrimination jointly led them to pursue self-employment (Haq, 2015). This argument posits two negative factors driving ethnic minority micro-business leaders toward self-employment in the UK, which are that they encounter discrimination in the job market due to language barriers, making traditional employment less accessible or attractive to them. Secondly, illegal immigrants find it easier to evade detection by working for themselves rather than being employed (Haq, 2015). Also, the assumption prevails that ethnic minority micro-business leaders are compelled to venture into self-employment because their foreign-acquired human capital, which includes qualifications, skills, and experiences, is undervalued compared to locally acquired human capital (Haq *et al.*, 2021). Consequently, they face discrimination in the labour market (Haq, 2015).

In London, 37% of businesses have reported experiencing a survival threatening crisis in the past five years (ERC, 2018). Not only does London has the highest number of new businesses, but it also has the highest number of failed

businesses in the UK (see Table 1). Some of these failures can also be attributed to discrimination, finance, leadership styles and cultural issues (Birbisa & Lakew, 2020; ERC, 2018; Fergie *et al.*, 2020; Haq *et al.*, 2023; Mendy & Hack-Polay, 2018; Özer & Tinaztepe, 2014). A survey of 600 London firms by the Enterprise Research Centre (ERC, 2018), revealed that 48% of ethnic minority-led businesses experienced an existential crisis in the past five years. The challenges significantly impacted lower-income boroughs, where the figure surpassed 50%. In contrast, only 33% of non-ethnic minority-led firms faced a similar crisis. These findings highlight the distinct challenges encountered by ethnic minority micro-business leaders, a growing yet poorly understood portion and group of UK companies (ERC, 2018).

However, the drive behind ethnic minority groups' collective entrepreneurial mindset in the UK is not clear, it might be for survival, self-sustenance, or necessity (Basu, 2004; Haq 2015; Mendy & Hack-Polay, 2018; Ram & Jones, 2008; Sithas & Surangi, 2021) and may be significantly influenced by culture (Gbadamosi, 2015).

2.4 Ethnic Minority Entrepreneurship Theories

Ethnic minority challenges are well documented (Haq *et al.*, 2021; Jones *et al.*, 2019; Ram & Jones, 2008; Ramadani *et al.*, 2014). So, to understand the struggles of ethnic minority businesses, owners, or entrepreneurs, we need to understand their reasons for venturing into business (Haq, 2015; Raimi *et al.*, 2023). There is an ongoing debate about the reasons or the factors why ethnic minorities venture into business (Dabić *et al.*, 2020; Raimi *et al.*, 2023), whether the decision by ethnic minorities to venture into business is influenced by cultural or structural factors (Dabić *et al.*, 2020; Daniel *et al.*, 2019; Volery, 2007). Before exploring why ethnic minorities venture into business, it is appropriate to understand the meaning of ethnic

entrepreneurship.

According to Ramadani *et al.* (2014), ethnic entrepreneurship is a process that involves identifying market opportunities and engaging in innovative and challenging ventures by individuals who are a minority group in society, and in pursuit of economic prosperity for themselves, their families, and the broader society (Ramadani *et al.*, 2014). Similarly, ethnic entrepreneurship is viewed as all entrepreneurs of ethnic minority backgrounds, irrespective of where they were born or when they arrived in their host country (Daniel *et al.*, 2019). It means a person is regarded as an ethnic minority entrepreneur, whether that person is born in the host country or not or how long the person has been in the host country. Entrepreneurs are leaders who are charged with the responsibility to lead their businesses by managing and controlling limited resources effectively to achieve their goals (Udovita, 2020). Ethnic minority business leaders have to be informed and take advantage of the resources and support available to them (Udovita, 2020). However, it was suggested that the behaviour of ethnic minorities is embedded in their culture (Gaitho, 2019; Kargas & Varoutas, 2015).

Several studies have explored ethnic minority entrepreneurship, for instance, in a study carried out in London about the link between ethnic minority entrepreneurship and religion, it was found that ethnic minority entrepreneurs in London use their religious faith as a business strategy for survival and claimed that it was responsible for their business success (Gbadamosi, 2015). Daniel *et al.* (2019) employed the mixed embeddedness theory to investigate whether more new ethnic minority entrepreneurs have succeeded in moving away from low-growth sectors and if the breakout is different among ethnic minority groups. The study looked at the

differences in the quality of entrepreneurship in terms of weekly hours and earnings worked weekly, and job satisfaction. However, the research revealed that achieving a breakout in entrepreneurship is not linked to being a new ethnic minority entrepreneur. Also, breakout is different across different ethnic minority groups (Daniel *et al.*, 2019).

Jones *et al.* (2019) explored the topic of diversity, economic development, and new migrant entrepreneurs in the West Midlands UK to understand the different contributions of migrant entrepreneurs. They argued that the discussion surrounding the benefits of diversity should extend beyond considerations of economic growth alone to include its impact on social processes. Also, they commended ethnic minority entrepreneurs that, despite facing significant resource constraints, migrant entrepreneurs operating at the grassroots level play a crucial role in their local communities. For example, they generate employment opportunities, address community-specific needs, and contribute to the social integration of new migrant communities within the UK (Carter *et al.*, 2015; Jones *et al.*, 2019). However, these studies did not specifically examine ethnic minority micro-businesses in London.

Moreover, different theories have been proposed to explain ethnic minority entrepreneurship and it was suggested that the factors for their entrepreneurship behaviour are multi-facet which include, cultural factors, social-economic factors, personal factors and institutional factors (Dabić *et al.*, 2020; Haq *et al.*, 2021; Kloosterman *et al.*, 1999; Mohan *et al.*, 2018; Raimi *et al.*, 2023; Ramadani *et al.*, 2014; Solano, 2021; Volery, 2007). These theories provide a rationale or explanation for the influence of culture on ethnic minorities and why they venture into business while acknowledging the challenges and motivation they face in the host country (Dabić *et al.*, 2020; Raimi *et al.*, 2023).

Opportunity vs Necessity Entrepreneurship Theory

Mohan *et al.* (2018) adopted the pull and push theory also known as the opportunity and necessity factors to explain why ethnic minorities venture into business. This dual concept is used to show the difference between internal individual personal motivation to achieve self-realisation and external motivation borne out of economic need to survive (Mohan *et al.*, 2018). Opportunity entrepreneurs are pulled into taking advantage of a business opportunity or unexploited market compared to necessity entrepreneurs, who are pushed or forced to venture into business due to their personal situation or the need to survive (Jones *et al.*, 2019; Mohan *et al.*, 2018). They claimed that entrepreneurs in developing countries tend to engage in business activities due to necessity after exhausting other options available to them, for example, poverty, discrimination in the labour market and economic survival (Mohan *et al.*, 2018). Also, these kinds of businesses (necessity entrepreneurs) are common in traditional or informal sectors because they are motivated to provide for themselves and their families by increasing their income and standard of living (Dabić *et al.*, 2020; Daniel *et al.*, 2019; Mohan *et al.*, 2018). Migrant entrepreneurs have a strong presence in low-value sectors and even with the intention to expand or diversify, these attempts were halted by a lack of capital resources which remain significant for migrant businesses to grow or succeed (Jones *et al.*, 2019).

On the contrary, Ram & Jones (2008) posited that there is a positive shift by ethnic minority entrepreneurs from traditional sectors to higher value sectors and businesses for example IT consultancy, computer manufacturing, financial services and software design (Dabić *et al.*, 2020). This shift was embraced by Africans, Caribbeans and Asians (Indians) who seem to be well-represented in this innovative

sector (Haq *et al.*, 2021; Haq *et al.*, 2023; Ram & Jones, 2008). However, in an empirical study, Mohan *et al.* (2018) concluded that Caribbeans are necessity entrepreneurs, which means they are pushed into doing business because of their unfavourable personal situations. The differences seen in these findings suggest that an explanation of a culture influence on the push or pull towards business opportunities may be too simplistic.

Mixed-Embeddedness

Another perspective or concept that shows the complex interplay between economic activities, social networks and cultural activities or context that shapes the experiences of ethnic minority or immigrant entrepreneurs is referred to as mixed embeddedness (Kloosterman *et al.*, 1999). Ram *et al.*, (2017) define mixed embeddedness as an intricate interplay between multiple factors that influence the experiences and outcome of ethnic minority or immigrant entrepreneurs. It is described as the interaction between institutional and social embeddedness with the human capital of ethnic minorities which influences entrepreneurial decisions and performance (Solano, 2021). Mixed embeddedness is one of the leading theories and approaches to ethnic minority or immigrant entrepreneurship research and a significant tool in understanding the economic activities of immigrants or ethnic minorities (Solano, 2021).

This theory suggests that ethnic minorities or immigrants who engage in business activities are influenced at the same time by their home country's culture and the conditions, rules, and regulations in their host country (Kloosterman *et al.*, 1999). Also, Ram *et al.* (2017) acknowledge that ethnic minority entrepreneurs operate their businesses with the help of networks for example, family, ethnic communities, and

professional relationships, which act as a bridge between their home country and host country. This allows them to take advantage of available resources in the form of information and support from both countries to develop and sustain their businesses (Dabić *et al.*, 2020; Kloosterman *et al.*, 1999; Ram *et al.*, 2017).

Kloosterman *et al.* (1999) emphasised that the motivation behind the pursuit of economic stability by ethnic minorities or immigrants is not mainly driven by the need to make money or gain economic stability, but by a complex combination of cultural and social factors (Ram *et al.*, 2017; Verver *et al.*, 2019). This concept improves the understanding of how ethnic minorities or immigrant entrepreneurs balance and combine the influences from their national culture and that of their host country, and how it affects their business decisions, networking, and business success (Kloosterman *et al.*, 1999). Even though ethnic minority business success is claimed to be influenced by the combination of transnational connections, cultural values, and economic constraints (Ram *et al.*, 2017), notwithstanding, financial capital is still considered significant to ethnic minority business success (Arslan *et al.*, 2022; Ram *et al.*, 2017).

Interactive Theory

Further, the opportunity necessity entrepreneurship theory is similar to the interactive theory of ethnic minority entrepreneurship propagated by (Ramadani *et al.*, 2014). This theory suggests the interaction between opportunities and resources which are significant to the sustainable success of ethnic minority businesses in foreign society (Ramadani *et al.*, 2014). Opportunity structure consists of market conditions, legal frameworks, access to property, labour market conditions and institutional frameworks, while the elements under resources include culture and

ethnic social networks (Ramadani *et al.*, 2014). However, they argued that the opportunity necessity theory is more complex than just starting a business. This is true because other factors can be influential and significant in the decision to venture into business, like personal, cultural, religious, and institutional factors (Kloosterman *et al.*, 1999; Ramadani *et al.*, 2014; Ram & Jones, 2008; Solano, 2021).

The mixed-embeddedness and interactive theories suggest the interaction between sociocultural and economic factors is influential in explaining the decisions, behaviour and experiences of ethnic minority entrepreneurs (Kloosterman *et al.*, 1999; Ramadani *et al.*, 2014). However, the opportunity necessity concept does not necessarily have to be separate because they can be combined as one factor and result in a strategic decision (Ramadani *et al.*, 2014). A good example of interactive theory is the suggestion that ethnic minorities in the UK are commonly found in deprived areas, they suffer discrimination from the labour market and at the same time take advantage of the opportunities available to them in their ethnic communities (Ram & Jones, 2008). However, according to Jones *et al.* (2019), ethnic minorities are already disadvantaged, coming sometimes from distressed societies (Raimi *et al.*, 2013), into an unfamiliar environment with new challenges like language, racial discrimination, legal structure, and culture to contend with (Ishaq *et al.*, 2010; Jones *et al.*, 2019; Ram *et al.*, 2017). This can make it more difficult for them to make strategic decisions or take advantage of available opportunities.

Acculturation

Throughout history, people have travelled around the world for various reasons, such as tourists, asylum seekers or economic migrants (Kunst *et al.*, 2021). These travels have enabled people from different cultures and countries to meet or converge

in a place. This convergence of people from diverse backgrounds in a new environment has led to the modification of the pattern of lives and culture of the people and resulted in the creation of new societies. This coming together of people and the mixture of cultures can be referred to as acculturation. According to Kunst *et al.* (2021), acculturation is the interaction of different cultures of people when they cohabit and the transformation or changes that ensue. It was described as an intercultural change between groups (Kunst *et al.*, 2021). Acculturation highlights the challenges experienced by immigrants in the host country because of the lack of required knowledge for social adaptation in the new or host country. For example, social behaviour, language, rules, and regulations (Ward *et al.*, 2010). The result of acculturation is cultural adaptation, which can be positive or negative (Ward *et al.*, 2010). Ethnic minorities used adaptation as a strategy to integrate into a new environment (Ward *et al.*, 2010). Acculturation is a two-way process that involves the contact and adaptation of ethnic minority culture and that of the host community (Ward *et al.*, 2010). This process relies heavily on the attitude of the host country (Ward *et al.*, 2010). Attitudes such as prejudice and exclusion can have a negative impact on ethnic minorities, as it could surface as discrimination in the labour market or racism (Ishaq *et al.*, 2010; Jones *et al.*, 2019; Ram *et al.*, 2017). Ethnic minority communities from a community acculturation perspective, serve as a haven and provide a sense of belonging and support for coping and adaptation for new immigrants or ethnic minority members (Ward *et al.*, 2010).

Despite acculturation being a concept that has existed since recorded history and was mostly adopted by anthropologists in researching indigenous people, it was only in the last twenty-something years that it gained significant attention from

psychology researchers (Kunst *et al.*, 2021). However, Kunst and colleagues claimed that psychologists expressed their concerns about cultural bias in current theories, data, and research (Kunst *et al.*, 2021). They suggested that the focus on psychological studies is being narrowed to a small sample, and even worse is the adoption and application of foreign concepts and tools when studying other cultures which are culturally inappropriate (Kunst *et al.*, 2021). It is assumed wrong to study or attempt to understand a group while ignoring their norms, values, behaviour, and basically their culture (Kunst *et al.*, 2021).

Transitional Entrepreneurship

Raimi *et al.* 2023 explored ethnic minority entrepreneurship through a thematic review that focused on transitional entrepreneurship. Transitional entrepreneurship is described as a concept and a process where disadvantaged groups, for example, ethnic minorities, venture into business to improve their personal situations or as a career change (Raimi *et al.*, 2023). Their study produced six reasons or motivations for transitional entrepreneurship, which include: institutional environment, push and pull factors, ethnic resources dependence, cultural inheritance, and gender issues. However, transitional entrepreneurship appears to be a recircled concept because it bears a resemblance with the aforementioned ethnic minority entrepreneurship theories in this study. The concept of transitional entrepreneurship supports and agrees with other ethnic minority entrepreneurship theories that suggest that ethnic minority entrepreneurship is influenced either by the push or pull factors, also known as necessity or opportunity factors (Kloosterman *et al.*, 1999; Mohan *et al.*, 2018; Ram *et al.*, 2017; Raimi *et al.*, 2023; Ramadani *et al.*, 2014). This theory suggests that ethnic minorities engage in business activities for personal and survival reasons or to take

advantage of unexplored opportunities in the market environment (Raimi *et al.*, 2023). Also, their decisions are influenced by cultural and institutional factors and the market environment (Raimi *et al.*, 2023).

Ethnic entrepreneurship gives ethnic minorities a fighting chance for survival and prosperity in a new environment, and small businesses can help them provide for themselves and their families (Jones *et al.* 2019; Ram *et al.*, 2017). In a different light, survival can be viewed as fighting against discrimination in the labour market (Haq *et al.*, 2021). There is an argument that immigrants with qualifications find it hard to get a job because of their race and other reasons but have to fend for themselves and family, so they are pushed into entrepreneurship to survive (Haq *et al.*, 2021; Jones *et al.* 2019). Also, some ethnic minority business owners engage in business activities to attain self-sufficiency (Haq, 2015; Sithas & Surangi, 2021). They aspire to have the freedom to make decisions that impact their lives, be able to meet their needs on their terms, and take advantage of available opportunities (Haq, 2015; Sithas & Surangi, 2021).

According to multiple studies (Kloosterman *et al.*, 1999; Raimi *et al.*, 2023; Ram *et al.*, 2017; Solano, 2021; Verver *et al.*, 2019), culture has a significant influence on ethnic minority entrepreneurship. The cultural theory posits that ethnic and immigrant communities possess inherent cultural attributes, such as a strong work ethic, close ties within their ethnic community, prudent living practices, a willingness to take calculated risks, adherence to social norms, a sense of unity and loyalty, and a propensity for self-employment (Volery, 2007). These attributes represent a cultural capital that can foster and stimulate entrepreneurial behaviour while providing support for individuals engaged in ethnic entrepreneurship (Volery, 2007). It is often the case

that individuals from ethnic backgrounds may only fully recognise the advantage of their own culture after relocating to a new environment (Volery, 2007).

These theories revealed the strong presence of cultural influence and provided the reasons behind ethnic minorities and immigrant entrepreneurship. However, they don't address the cultural influence and the leadership behaviour of the leaders of ethnic minority-led micro-businesses. According to Gbadamosi (2015), culture plays a key role in entrepreneurship. To examine this cultural influence on the leadership approach of ethnic minority micro-business leaders, this study focused on Hofstede cultural framework and its dimensions in relation to the leadership style of ethnic minority micro-businesses.

2.5 Hofstede Cultural Dimension

Hofstede's cultural dimensions theory, developed by social psychologist Hofstede, offers a comprehensive framework for understanding cultural differences across societies (Hofstede, 1983). This influential model identifies six dimensions- Power Distance, Individualism vs. Collectivism, Masculinity vs. Femininity, Uncertainty Avoidance, Long-Term Orientation vs. Short-Term Orientation, and Indulgence vs. Restraint (Hofstede, 1983; Hofstede, 2011). By dimension, it means aspects of a culture that are more pronounced, dominant, and visible as they relate to a particular country (Hofstede, 2011). Each dimension provides insights into how cultures shape values, behaviours, and organisational dynamics (Hofstede, 1983). It is widely utilised in cross cultural management, leadership, and international business studies (Hayton *et al.*, 2002; Kreiser *et al.*, 2010; Muenjohn & Amstrong, 2007). Hofstede's framework continues to enhance the understanding of the diverse ways in which cultures

influence leadership, individuals, and society globally (Beugelsdijk & Welzel, 2018; Hofstede, 1983; Jackson, 2020; Kreiser *et al.*, 2010; Sent & Kroese, 2022).

No two cultures are the same, and their distinctiveness is in their values and behaviour, even in similar circumstances (Tayeb, 1994; Williams, 2011). Hofstede (1983) defined culture as a “collective mental programming” (Hofstede, 1983, pg. 76). It is a shared conditioning within a nation, region, or group and encompasses traditions and common ways of thinking specific to a culture, differing from those of other nations, regions, or groups (Hofstede, 1983). Culture is a belief system guide, directs and shape behaviour and constantly evolving (Kreiser *et al.*, 2010; Williams, 2011). It influences leadership styles, wisdom, and music, reflecting the meaning assigned to actions and interpretations (Geertz, 2008, Hofstede, 1983). Culture, as described by Schein (2010), is shared beliefs and knowledge accumulated over time, formulated into rules, and taught as the right approach to life. Yu & Miller (2005) alluded that culture strongly influences people’s behaviour and activities. It is described as a way of life (Ardichvili *et al.*, 2009; Williams, 2011). However, this present study adopts the definition of culture as a way of life that shapes, guide and influences behaviour and activities of people in society.

National cultural significantly impact human behaviour, reflecting shared believes and cultural ideals (Archer, 1996). Van Oudenhoven (2001) defined national culture has profound beliefs, values, and practices shared by a large group of people from a specific country, expressed in behaviour and reinforced by the government and social institutions (Hofsted, 1983; Hofstede, 2006). People's views and actions are shaped by their in-group ideology and environments (Williams, 2011). Further, Hofstede (1983) elaborated on this point when he stated that the purpose of cultures

is for collective mental programming. He highlighted the importance of nationality in management for political, sociological, and psychological reasons. Nations, as political units, have unique institutions, while sociological, shared symbolic values creates national identity (Hofstede, 1983). Psychologically, national cultural influences human thinking and shapes behaviour through life experiences and institutions (Hofstede, 1983).

Hofstede cultural dimension rankings in Table 4 offers valuable insights into societal values and behaviour. It is a critical tool for understanding cultural variation by facilitating cross cultural comparisons, helping businesses, researchers, and policy makers, in navigating or investigating diverse cultures or environments (Hofstede, 1983). Table 4 features the countries represented by this present study's participants, providing insights into their culture and behaviour. This information is crucial for understanding the leadership and cultural dynamics in ethnic minority micro-businesses.

Table 4. Selected Hofstede Cultural Dimensions Rankings

	India	Pakistan	Bangladesh	Nigeria	Jamaica	Philippine	Sri Lanka	Sierra Leone	Morocco
Power distance	77	55	80	80	45	94	80	70	70
Individualism	24	5	5	0	39	17	35	20	24
Masculinity	56	50	66	46	68	64	62	-	53
Uncertainty Avoidance	40	70	60	55	13	44	45	50	68

Source: Hofstede-insight.com

Hofstede's Cultural Framework is a widely recognised model that analyses cultural dimensions to understand how societies and organisations differ in terms of their values and behaviour (Beugelsdijk & Welzel, 2018; Hofstede *et al.*, 2006). While Hofstede's framework primarily focuses on national or regional cultures, it can be applied to study how cultural dimensions influence leadership styles within ethnic minority groups (Hofstede, 1983). However, Hofstede was criticised for stereotyping, characterising people in a particular manner based on expected behaviour and practices, which Hofstede's framework seems to suggest as a result of the views or information gathered from individuals from various nations (Smith, 2006). Also, Collins & Fakoussa (2015) argued against reducing culture to a few dimensions, highlighting that culture is complex. They mentioned that some researchers have tried to explain individual attitudes, values, and behaviour with average scores, emphasising that values are national, not universal. Also, they suggested that subcultures, socially dominant and inferior cultures, can undermine cultural homogeneity (Collins & Fakoussa, 2015). Nevertheless, examining the influence of culture on the leadership approach of ethnic minority micro-businesses in London will advance the knowledge of the significant role of culture in the leadership approach of ethnic minorities.

Schein (2009) emphasised the intertwining of culture and leadership, with culture being achieved over time and influencing expected behaviour. Hofstede (1983) stated that two dimensions, power distance and collectivism vs. Individualism are very significant to leadership, as leaders need power to lead and people are unequal, and leaders are part of a group or society, and they embody what that group or society is about (Hofstede, 1983). To comprehend the leadership behaviour of the leaders of ethnic minority micro-businesses in London, this present study adopts Hofstede's cultural framework with the focus on three of his dimensions power distance,

collectivism vs. Individualism, and uncertainty avoidance but will discuss all four, which helps to understand human behaviour and culture (Hofstede, 1983).

Power Distance

Power distance can be observed in how people express themselves, relate with one another, how decisions are made, the level of respect for authority or hierarchy and how people lead (Sent & Kroese, 2022). Hofstede suggested that developing countries which are the majority of countries that make up ethnic minorities in the UK exhibit high power distance. Janićijević (2019) claimed that power distance is a significant cultural dimension that profoundly influences leadership styles. It reflects a society's acceptance of unequal power distribution, with high power distance cultures regarding such disparities as natural, while low power distance cultures aim for equality (Dorfman *et al.*, 2012; Janićijević, 2019).

According to Wanasika *et al.* (2011), Sub-Saharan African countries such as Namibia, Nigeria, South Africa, Zambia, and Zimbabwe all have a high-power distance culture (Wanasika *et al.*, 2011). Dissanayake *et al.* (2015) in a study, investigated the national culture of Asian countries and concluded that most Asian countries practise a high power distance culture. Countries such as Bangladesh, the Philippines and Sri Lanka all scored high on the power distance index of the Hofstede cultural dimensions (Dissanayake *et al.*, 2015). According to Table 4 in this study, countries such as India, Nigeria, China, and Malaysia scored high in power distance. These countries accept a hierarchical social structure, inequalities in power distribution, and centralisation of power, subordinates expect clear instructions, and a benevolent autocratic leader is considered an ideal boss (Dissanayake *et al.*, 2015; Hofstede, 2011). Also, power

distance can be observed in cultures that practise age-based status or gerontocracy (Wanasika *et al.*, 2011).

In high power distance cultures, leaders tend to adopt authoritarian styles, making decisions without followers' input, and often practising paternalistic leadership behaviour (Janićijević, 2019). Even in businesses, there's a clear distinction between the boss and employees because of a centralisation of power and authority which also reflects in the interactions and relationship between the bosses and employees (Tehseen *et al.*, 2021). Paternalistic leadership is a non-Western leadership style that is prevalent in high power distance society because it is embedded in the cultural beliefs of a people (Aycan, 2006; Farh & Cheng, 2000, Mansur *et al.*, 2017).

According to Mansur *et al.* (2017), paternalistic leadership is effective and a suitable leadership approach in a high power distance culture because human and power inequalities are not questioned and power is centralised. This view is supported by empirical studies that paternalistic leadership is an appropriate leadership approach in high power distance cultures (Aycan, 2006; Pellegrini & Scandura, 2006; Wanasika *et al.*, 2011). A leader's authoritative behaviour is accepted and respected by subordinates in a high power distance culture, which portrays submissive behaviour from the subordinates (Mansur *et al.*, 2017). According to Wanasika *et al.* (2011), most Sub-Saharan African countries are cultures with the presence of high power distance which encourages paternalistic leadership behaviour. The paternalistic leadership approach is common in high power distance and collective society (Mansur *et al.*, 2017). However, high power distance culture can discourage innovation and creativity (Tehseen *et al.*, 2021).

Collectivism

The duality of individualism and collectivism highlights the rich diversity in human cultures (Hofstede, 2011). These cultural orientations significantly impact societal norms, familial ties, and workplace dynamics, shaping how individuals interact, collaborate, and perceive their roles within their communities (Hofstede, 2011; Sent & Kroese, 2022). Understanding these cultural dimensions is essential in leadership and fostering effective cross-cultural communication and collaboration in society. Collectivism paints a picture of tightly woven communities where cooperation and unity are paramount (Haq *et al.*, 2023; Hofstede, 2011; Sent & Kroese, 2022). In collectivist societies, individuals belong to in-groups, which can take the form of extended families, tribes, or villages, while some become members through birth. In collectivist cultures, expressing personal opinions freely is discouraged; adherence to the rules, values, and norms of the in-group takes precedence (Hofstede, 1983). Collectivist societies operate on the principles of mutual support and reciprocal care, and members are expected to look out for one another, and in return, they receive protection and support from the in-group (Hofstede, 1983). It was suggested that countries like Bangladesh, Pakistan, Taiwan, Nigeria, China, India, and Jamaica, hold collective values and practise a collectivist culture (Hofstede, 1983).

Collectivism plays a significant role in shaping social relationships within communities (Hofstede, 1983). The emphasis on mutual support, interdependence, and cooperation creates robust social networks (Ram *et al.*, 2017). Social networking is crucial for ethnic minority small businesses, extending beyond their immediate circle to encompass local communities and socio-cultural institutions like religious organisations (Dabić *et al.*, 2020; Razzak *et al.*, 2023). These networks act as essential support systems, providing emotional, financial, and practical assistance during challenging times (Dabić *et al.*, 2020; Ram *et al.*, 2017). This trend is particularly

noticeable among South Asian minority groups in the UK, who actively engage in self-employment and small-scale enterprises (Deakins *et al.*, 2007; Fadahunsi *et al.*, 2000; Ram & Jones, 2008; Razzak *et al.*, 2023). For example, the entrepreneurial spirit of South Asians is partly due to their close-knit co-ethnic networks, which significantly facilitate their business endeavours (Dabić *et al.*, 2020; Altinay, 2010). Entrepreneurs from Bangladesh, for instance, maintain strong ties within their cultural networks, primarily centred around their co-ethnic community (Razzak *et al.*, 2023). Collectivism reinforces the notion of communal responsibility, encouraging individuals to contribute to the welfare of the entire community (Hofstede *et al.*, 2005). Just like ethnic minority enclaves where they look out for each other by providing support to both new and existing ethnic businesses to grow and become a haven for members (Jones *et al.*, 2019; Ram *et al.*, 2017).

Also, the influence of collectivism extends far beyond familial contexts and permeates into the workplace dynamics of these societies (Sagie & Aycan, 2003). A prime example of collectivism in action can be observed in Japanese organisations. Japanese culture is profoundly collectivist and high in power distance, meaning that teamwork is highly valued (Hofstede *et al.*, 2005; Sagie & Aycan, 2003). However, this emphasis on teamwork coexists with a submissive and conforming relationship towards authority figures. Japanese leadership styles are often paternalistic and autocratic, mirroring the collectivist values of the society (Sagie & Aycan, 2003). Paternalistic leadership view the workplace and society as an extension of the family (Northouse, 2020; Wanasika *et al.*, 2011). The paternalistic leadership approach is endorsed in collective cultures because of the benevolent behaviour of the leader and the emphasis on familism which involves treating subordinates like family and being actively involved in their personal lives (Aycan, 2006; Farh & Cheng, 2000; Mansur *et*

al., 2017; Wanasika *et al.*, 2011). This leadership approach is not only being practised in China, but also prevalent in other continents (Aycan *et al.*, 2000; Farh & Cheng, 2000; Jackson, 2016; Pellegrini & Scandura, 2008; Wanasika *et al.*, 2011).

Masculinity vs Femininity

This explains the disparity in the roles and characteristics of the sexes in society as they are socially constructed. The division of the roles and characteristics of the sexes depends on society (Hofstede, 1983). Societies with high characteristics and role division for the sexes are masculine, while those with low characteristics and role division are feminine. Masculine culture views society as competitive and favours discipline, authority, heroism, physical acquisitions, and reward for success. Feminine society shares values such as equality, caring for employees, a conducive working environment and cooperation (Hofstede, 1983). Some societies are concerned about the distribution of values between male and female genders and can go as far as making a clear distinction in the roles of both males and females in society (Hofstede, 2011). Masculinity is more about competition and assertiveness. In masculinity culture, caring can be seen as a weakness, and femininity is about caring. Countries such as Japan, Nigeria, China, Jamaica, and India can be referred to as masculine societies because of their high score on the Masculinity scale (Hofstede, 1983), and these are the countries that make up the ethnic minority community in the UK (Carter *et al.*, 2015).

Uncertainty Avoidance

Uncertainty avoidance is based on how society deals with uncertainty and the reality that the future is unknown and always will be (Hofstede, 1983). It is an approach

to make followers adhere to a strict and unified way of doing things, to condition their behaviour and actions and not unsettle them during uncertainty (Hofstede, 1983). In cultures with a high uncertainty avoidance, there is a significant emphasis on predictability, explicit instructions, and well-defined expectations, all of which are regarded as societal standards or norms (Jang *et al.*, 2018). Conversely, in cultures with lower uncertainty avoidance, there is a preference for unstructured situations and broad guidelines (Jang *et al.*, 2018). According to Jang *et al.* (2018), these cultural norms are likely to strongly shape an individual's mental framework or cognitive abilities and may also have a subtle impact on their values and responses (Jang *et al.*, 2018). However, it is important to note that uncertainty avoidance and risk avoidance are different concepts both in theory and in practice (Jang *et al.*, 2018). Risk avoidance refers to the unwillingness to take risks, a distinct concept from uncertainty avoidance, although they are frequently confused (Hofstede *et al.*, 2005; Jang *et al.*, 2018). For instance, people in cultures with high uncertainty avoidance might be open to taking risks if these risks help reduce overall uncertainty (Jang *et al.*, 2018).

It was suggested that African societies exhibit a culture characterised by a high uncertainty avoidance (Anedo, 2012). This implies that there is a tendency among Africans to avoid unnecessary risks and resist changes (Anedo, 2012). This behaviour reflects a preference for stability and predictability, leading individuals within these societies to approach unfamiliar or uncertain situations with caution (Hofstede *et al.*, 2005). Consequently, embracing new or untested ideas might be met with reluctance, emphasising the value placed on tradition and established practices within African communities (Hofstede *et al.*, 2005). In a study on Malaysian ethnic entrepreneurs, Tehseen *et al.* (2021) discovered that Malaysian Chinese and Indian entrepreneurs exhibit a preference for explicit laws and organised institutions. They claimed that

these choices are rooted in the need for security, stability, and clearly defined regulations and these preferences strongly indicate a high level of uncertainty avoidance (Tehseen *et al.*, 2021).

Also, according to Hofstede *et al.* (2005), religious teachings offer a profound sense of security to individuals through messages that instil a sense of order and meaning. This profound psychological reassurance becomes particularly prominent in societies characterised by strong uncertainty avoidance tendencies (Hofstede *et al.*, 2005). The discomfort people experience in the face of uncertainty often drives them toward religious beliefs, seeking solace from the negative emotions associated with ambiguity (Engstrom & Laurin, 2020; Hofstede *et al.*, 2005). While empirical evidence on this connection is limited, religion serves as a means to alleviate uncertainty (Engstrom & Laurin, 2020). They concluded that informational uncertainty which refers to fear of the unknown prompts individuals to regain a sense of control through religious beliefs. GÜmÜsay (2019) corroborates Hofstede's assertions, highlighting the practical significance of religion during periods of uncertainty. Religious beliefs not only provide a sense of security and moral direction but also serve as a source of community and belonging (GÜmÜsay, 2019; Hofstede *et al.*, 2005). In times of crisis, communities can become even more vital, fostering a sense of unity and solidarity among believers (Hofstede *et al.*, 2005).

Religion holds immense importance and exerts significant influence on the lives of ethnic minorities, as indicated by studies conducted (Nwankwo *et al.*, 2012; Van Buren III *et al.*, 2020). Most ethnic minorities are devout followers of their respective religions, shaping their lives according to the doctrines prescribed by these faiths

(Nwankwo, 2013). Ethnic minorities rely on God, rather than planning, to gauge success or failure in their lives and business (Nwankwo, 2013).

2.6 Religion as a culture

Historically, religion has played a significant role in most civilisations regarding cultures, politics, economics, and social life, influencing human behaviours, changing general views of life, and adapting cultures (Beyers, 2017; Gaitho, 2019; Sobolewska *et al.*, 2015; Van Buren III *et al.*, 2020). Religion is an ambiguous concept to understand, and difficult to ascertain what religion contains or what makes religion (Beyers, 2017). From an anthropological perspective, religion is connected to culture (Beyers, 2017). Religion is a cultural expression and provides an avenue for expressing ethnic differences (Beyers, 2017). It will not be easy to comprehend religion without adequately understanding its connection with ethnicity and culture (Beyers, 2017).

Religion was described as the practices and beliefs of people of a particular body of faith (Phipps, 2012). It is a social force influencing businesses, as it plays a vital role in shaping societies, and it is a source of moral standards and beliefs that mould and guide human behaviour (Fry *et al.*, 2017; Van Buren III *et al.*, 2020). As a source of inspiration, religion inspires institutions such as government, family, education, and businesses that incorporate religious beliefs in their activities (Sobolewska *et al.*, 2015; Van Buren III *et al.*, 2020). However, in this study, religion is defined as any religious affiliation, beliefs and practice undertaken by an individual. The discussion of the interconnectedness of culture and religion in this study is purely from a socio-cultural perspective, for example, social norms, values, attitudes, and practices.

According to Saroglou (2011), 72% of the world's population is religious and has four major religions, Christianity, Islam, Hinduism, and Buddhism. In Africa and Asia in particular, there has been an increase in the practice of religious activities, and this highlights the high levels of commitment to personal faith, strong and shared behavioural norms, and a show of collective religious experience (Henley, 2017; Nwankwo *et al.*, 2012). In England, Christians constitute less than half of the population, totalling 27.5 million people, while 6.5% identify as Muslims with 3.9 million (ONS, 2021b). The religious landscape also includes approximately 6000 Rastafarians, 32,000 Agnostics, and 14,000 Atheist in the UK (ONS, 2021b). London emerges as the most religiously diverse region in the UK with 25.3% of its residents identifying with religions other than Christianity (ONS, 2021b). Notably, London hosts substantial Muslim and Hindu communities, constituting 15% and 5.1% of the population respectively, and are predominantly Asians (ONS, 2021b; Rafiq, 1992).

Over time, religious institutions have transitioned, and married people's social and cultural aspects of life and the effects are long-lasting (Beyers, 2017). Religion has managed to survive for an extended period (Beyers, 2017). In many parts of the world, the people's national, regional, and indigenous cultures are heavily influenced by religious beliefs (Beyers, 2017). In some cases, they are very present in business affairs by prescribing expected business behaviours (Van Buren III *et al.*, 2020). Being an entrepreneur or self-employed can be seen as a positive within certain religions (Rafiq, 1992). For example, being an entrepreneur is encouraged and accepted in the Muslim, Sikh, and Hindu communities, where they have many successful and devoted members as a frame of reference (Rafiq, 1992; Porter, 1998). For Muslims, Prophet Mohammed (their leader) was an entrepreneur. The Hindu Guru Nanak was also an

entrepreneur, and Sikhs have a caste system, the Vaishyas, who are known for their entrepreneurial activities. Believers of these religious bodies are most likely to want to engage in entrepreneurial activities as it is a common practice in their community and religion (Rafiq, 1992).

Religion is not only about prayers and God, but it also has a high social significance to ethnic minority groups as it assists in forming communities, provides support, security, moral compass, and is an identity marker for members (ONS, 2021b; Rafiq, 1992). People practise religion as a way of life and follow specific rules and guidelines that dictate how they behave and engage with their environment regarding moral obligations, food, music, and fashion. For example, Muslims are only allowed to eat Halal meat, while pork is forbidden (Rafiq, 1992; Theisen, 2020). Hindus are encouraged to be vegetarian, and Sikhs can eat animal meat killed with a single blow (Rafiq, 1992). Religion can have a significant cultural presence, especially in a society where there is a high level of commitment to religious practices and it is essential in creating culture as it unifies people with common and shared values (Beyers, 2017; Henley, 2017; Pellegrini & Scandura, 2006). For example, Islam is a unifying force for countries that practise Islam. It shapes and influences their behaviour based on how they dress, talk, and interact with people, what they eat, the kind of business they operate and how they lead (Pellegrini & Scandura, 2006).

On the compatibility of Christianity in business, (Porter, 1998) attempted to dismiss the notion that Christianity and business are incompatible. He acknowledged that there are studies out there that disapprove of his perception. He examined the difficulty that may surface when trying to integrate all the teachings of Christianity into business. He implied that it is also based on interpretation, as not all aspects of

business are addressed in the holy book. According to ONS 2021b, London is the most religious city in the UK, and it has a large Muslim community mostly Asians (ONS, 2021b; Rafiq, 1992). Also, there are three core religions that are central to Asian culture: Islam, Hinduism, and Sikhism (Peach, 2006; Rafiq, 1992). These religions are very influential in the everyday life of Asian people in Britain. These three religious bodies impose some restrictions on followers, and such religious practices have been absorbed and incorporated into their everyday lives (Rafiq, 1992; Theisen, 2020).

Spiritual leadership is the capability of a leader to motivate people through supernatural purpose alongside organisational culture guided by unselfish love (Fry *et al.*, 2017). It is regarded as essential for leaders and subordinates to satisfy spiritual needs through calling or being a member of a spiritual group which can encourage higher performance, social relations, and organisational commitment (Fry *et al.*, 2017). Spiritual leadership entails moral values, integrity, humility, altruistic love, and calling (Fry *et al.*, 2017). Calling, which is also authority or power that most spiritual leaders require to lead (Fry *et al.*, 2017). In comparison, paternalistic leadership embodies spiritual leadership because it is based on Confucius's ideals, a spiritual and cultural system (Farh & Cheng, 2000; Tu, 1998). It involves morality which is all about moral values and benevolence that suggests care, love, and humility (Farh & Cheng, 2000). Authority is similar to calling and represents power (Farh & Cheng, 2000). They both share similar features, the leader is seen as a role model, respected, create a team or family-like environment, and participates in the lives of subordinates (Farh & Cheng, 2000; Fry *et al.*, 2017). According to Gaitho (2019), the influence of religion on leadership can be observed in most leadership styles, whether autocratic, democratic, charismatic, servant, strategic or transformational. He elucidates the strong influence

of religion on leadership styles and roles, stating that large aspects of leadership attract influence from religion. Leaders are people, and religion shapes the values and personal beliefs of people and society, which goes to show why leaders may exhibit religious beliefs in their leadership style (Gaitho, 2019). This can be the case for most ethnic minority micro-business leaders whose behaviours may have been shaped by religious values.

2.7 The relationship of culture and leadership

Many researchers have suggested that there is a strong interplay or connection between culture and leadership styles (Byrne & Bradley, 2007; House *et al.*, 1999; House *et al.*, 2002; Li *et al.*, 2018; Schein, 2010; Xenikou & Simosi, 2006), which explains attempts to understand the relationship between the two concepts. Ke & Wei (2008) said that culture could be intentionally designed, and leadership is the tool for its implementation. Hofstede (1983) emphasised the need to understand the cultural context of a person before their behaviour can be interpreted or perceived. According to Li *et al.* (2018), leadership style is associated with culture. Similarly, paternalism is culturally connected (Farh & Cheng, 2000). It cannot be studied without exploring its cultural context, which brings a better understanding of the word's meaning (Farh & Cheng, 2000; Mansur *et al.*, 2017). Also, management and organisations are culturally dependent because the people in organisations are from cultural backgrounds that shape their belief systems and behaviour that may be incorporated into management practices for effective management (Hofstede, 1983). A good example is the successful Japanese integration of American management practice, the Quality Control Circle, with Japanese culture. Hofstede explains that the lack of cultural sensitivity in importing foreign management ideas to developing countries is partly due

to their massive failure. He insisted on the importance of cultural sensitivity in implementing foreign management ideas. Also, as Mendy & Hack-Polay (2018) reiterated that cultural issues are part of the leading causes of ethnic minority business failure.

Understanding the way of life of a person or group of persons as a leader in order to easily motivate and sell an idea to them with little or no resistance is one element of cultural intelligence (Earley & Mosakowski, 2004). It is advantageous if leaders or managers know how to harness this power of culture (Earley & Mosakowski, 2004). Cultural intelligence is using cultural knowledge to your advantage or working successfully with people (Afsar *et al.*, 2019; Earley & Mosakowski, 2004). As a cultural leadership approach, a paternalistic leader adopts cultural knowledge in leadership. However, emotional intelligence is one behaviour overlooked by scholars in paternalistic leadership, as paternalistic leadership is described as a father and son relationship, the leader blends strong discipline with fatherly benevolence and morality to lead, and the leader is involved in both the private and public lives of employees (Aycaan, 2006; Farh & Cheng, 2000). Thus, applying emotional intelligence is a way to support and motivate subordinates to gain trust and loyalty, and generate high performance. Adopting all or any of the dimensions of paternalism at any time by a paternalistic leader is emotional intelligence. According to Alkahtani (2016), the leadership style of a leader is guided by emotional intelligence based on temperament and situation, and high emotional intelligence leaders are effective and influential leaders (Alkahtani, 2016).

Culture can be a mechanism or a manipulative tool to control people, and followers will accept the norms and behaviour of their society without question

because they believe it is the right thing to do (Geertz, 2008). Dominant culture can influence an individual's behaviour and leadership approach (Eagly & Chin, 2010). It can be seen in individuals from society with strict cultural values and norms. This is true in paternalistic societies where leaders use culture to control and achieve harmony (Farh & Cheng, 2000; Mussolino & Calabrò, 2014). Schein (2010) agrees that culture influences people's perception, using norms, values, and beliefs to shape and direct behaviour. The reason people can easily be identified as originating from a particular country, tribe or clan is because of the strong influence of their culture, that part of them that cannot be hidden and can be evident in their leadership behaviour (Eagly & Chin, 2010). According to Wendt *et al.* (2009), the way leaders approach their roles can be influenced by the cultural values of their respective countries. Also, the group a leader belongs to or the neighbourhood he or she resides in can provide a good understanding of his or her leadership behaviour. While Kargas & Varoutas (2015) emphasised the relevance and impact of cultural values and norms in forming leadership styles. People learn and follow from what they see in their communities, they imbibe these practices, and it becomes normalcy, which in the long run, shapes the kind of person they become (Hayton *et al.*, 2002).

Culture represents the totality of an individual and not just his or her personality (Hofstede, 2010). Schein (2010) described culture as a stabiliser, a sense-making mechanism used to preserve the way of life of a people. A strong culture effectively sustains an established process and has a long-lasting effect on the established way of life. He argued that culture and leadership are two sides of a coin (Schein, 2010). Leaders create cultures through followers or subordinates, and after achieving an established system, culture provides a system of leadership and a process of deciding

who becomes a leader (Schein, 2010). This demonstrates the interrelationship between the two concepts.

2.8 Leadership

Leadership is significant for micro-businesses, SMEs, ethnic minority-led small businesses, and any organisation (Birbirs & Lakew, 2020; Eagly & Chin, 2010; Franco & Matos, 2015; Garavan *et al.*, 2016; Nabella *et al.*, 2022). Leadership is control, relational, a process, and directional, and can lead to growth (Nabella *et al.*, 2022; Northouse, 2021; Ospina & Foldy, 2009). Control, relationships, direction, and growth are essential for any business, especially small businesses, where managing limited resources to achieve growth and gain profit in a competitive market with minimal experience rests on one man (Del Giudice *et al.*, 2017; Franco & Matos, 2015; Leitch *et al.*, 2009; Morrison, 2003; Özer & Tinaztepe, 2014). Small businesses are experiencing more challenges in the drive for success in the present business world. So, it has become paramount to understand the leadership of micro-businesses besides the commonly researched areas of small businesses such as finance, innovation, and strategy, which are considered factors for sustainability and competitive advantage (Franco & Matos, 2015; Haq *et al.*, 2023).

Ethnic minorities operate mostly in small businesses, so they share some similarities in experiences with small business owners (Haq *et al.*, 2023). So, having the right leadership approach that can address the situation at hand and diversity is important (Chin, 2013; Eagly & Chin, 2010). However, Alves *et al.* (2006) suggested that present leadership theories are based on American ideas and a true reflection of the American perspective of leadership and represent American culture (Adler, 1997). Thus, the applicability of these Western leadership theories in developing countries in

Africa and East Asian countries will not be a good fit due to cultural differences and their understanding of leadership based on power or authority, trust and the relationship between a leader and followers or subordinates (Adler, 1997; Alves *et al.*, 2006; Chin, 2013; Eagly & Chin, 2010).

2.8.1 Definition of leadership

Leadership is a misunderstood concept (Gandolfi & Stone, 2018; Harrison, 2017) with an array of proposed definitions (Northouse, 2021). Despite the huge volume of scholarly works on leadership, leadership is still a complex and compound concept with no universally agreed definition (Adler, 1997; Alves *et al.*, 2006; Ciulla & Ciulla, 2020; Franco & Matos, 2015; Harrison, 2017; Krapfl & Kruja, 2018; Northouse, 2021). Leadership is a duty, a responsibility, not just a position (Udovita, 2020). It emerges from the need to achieve a goal or satisfy a certain need at a particular time and place (Gini, 1997). It is a collaborative experience where a leader influences the behaviour and character of followers (Udovita, 2020). Leadership is interactive and collaborative as leaders need followers, which is the most crucial element in leadership because, without followers, a leader is powerless (Burns 1978; Gini, 1997). The relationship between a leader and followers is interdependent; the role and rights of followers need to be recognised because followers are fellow partners with the same aspirations (Burns 1978; Gini, 1997; Udovita, 2020). Also, leadership has spiritual responsibilities (Nabella *et al.*, 2022).

The focus on leadership demonstrates how significant leadership is to any society or business (Franco & Matos, 2015; Gandolfi & Stone, 2018; Nabella *et al.*, 2022; Northouse, 2021). The early study of leadership started from the Great Man theory and trait theory, which emphasises a leader's personality and physical

attributes (Gandolfi & Stone, 2018; Harrison, 2017; Northouse, 2021). The Great Man theory is a popular leadership theory by Thomas Carlyle, who explored great leaders. As the name suggests, the Great Man theory is about successful great leaders (Harrison, 2017). This leadership style suggests that people are born as leaders, and they are men (Spector, 2016). However, there is gender bias at its heart along with the premise that people are brought into this life with natural traits or abilities that make them stand out and be great leaders (Harrison, 2017; Northouse, 2021). It was suggested that emulating great leaders can make a person a great leader, however, this fails to recognise the structural inequalities that influences whether one is able to access the required social and financial capital to achieve greatness. Similarly, the Trait theory focuses on specific traits of a leader that differentiate him or her from others (Bass, 1990; Harrison, 2017; Northouse, 2021). Having a particular trait does not make a person an effective leader; instead, it is the relevance and usage of the acquired traits in situations that matter (Harrison, 2017; Krapfl & Kruja, 2018; Northouse, 2021). However, Bolden & Terry (2000) are convinced that traits and behaviour can define leadership.

Also, scholars have attempted to differentiate leaders from followers with specific leadership traits (Bass, 1990). However, Barker (2001) queried old assumptions of the definition of leadership, arguing that leadership traits highlighted by some scholars that differentiate an effective leader from other people: motivation, self-confidence, honesty, integrity, cognitive abilities, drive, and business knowledge are not necessarily true because, in reality, these traits cannot be separated from traits shown by people who are presumed not to be an effective leader. Similarly, Harrison (2017) suggested that having certain traits does not determine the success of a leader but, rather, depends on the leader's ability to apply the appropriate traits that the leader

possesses in the right situation (Krapfl & Kruja, 2018), the possessed traits must be relevant to the situation the leader is addressing.

Barker (2001) mentioned that leadership is a job, not a position. In other words, this could mean the responsibilities that come with the position or the requirements of that position, and maybe the demands of that position are what leadership means. When studying people, attention should be on what matters the most to them, as the individual's will, and ethics are vital (Barker, 2001). He further explained that ethics is the base for values that shape people's character and provide a sense of purpose and direction (Barker, 2001). Ciulla & Ciulla, (2020) viewed leadership from a moral perspective, stating that leadership involves the relationship between people. Ethics, also known as morals, guide human interactions. Therefore, morality is critical to understanding leadership as it relates to a leader being fair, responsible, and working for the good of all (Ciulla & Ciulla, 2020).

Leadership viewed as a social construct is influenced by the common interests and values of people in society (Northouse, 2021). Accordingly, leadership is a process of transformational change where the values of individuals are integrated into that of a community to effect social development (Barker, 2001; Nabella *et al.*, 2019). People can adjust their personal goals to shared goals when they know they can accomplish their interests by following a collective movement. There is motivation to pursue that course as it aligns with their interests. Leadership is relational and requires leaders and followers to work together to achieve a joint goal (Nanjundeswaraswamy & Swamy, 2014; Northouse, 2021). Similarly, Amanchukwu *et al.* (2015) implied that leadership is a responsibility that involves a joint effort from a leader and subordinates to meet identified goals with a well-thought-out or strategic plan. Burns (1978)

leadership is a collaboration between a leader and followers. They both need each other for the process of leadership to work (Burns, 1978). Leadership is present at all levels of social institutions in society, and it is the ability of a leader to direct and influence his or her followers to achieve a shared goal (Asree *et al.*, 2010; Gandolfi & Stone, 2018).

Northouse (2021) suggest that leadership is a complex process consisting of various dimensions and encourages cooperation or collaboration of the parties involved, leaders and followers. Also, norms, values and beliefs are key to the definition of leadership as leadership behaviour and practice are shaped by cultural values (Ardichvili, 2001; Bresnen, 1995; Burns, 1978). While Krapfl & Kruja (2018) argued that a leader can affect, modify, and determine culture (Gandolfi & Stone, 2018). A leader can achieve this influence through his or her features, attributes, behaviour, and situation (Asree *et al.*, 2010). Leadership is an interaction, relationship that involves power and persuasion, it is an ability to motivate and command compliance, and it is a tool for achieving results (Franco & Matos, 2015). Recurring themes from these definitions of leadership are that leadership is a behaviour, a process, it influences, it requires followers, and strives to attain clarified joint goals. However, this study defines leadership as a cultural behaviour that can influence and can be influenced.

2.9 Ethnic minority leadership

The paucity of literature on ethnic minority leadership style and the assumption that the Western leadership approach is far more suitable in all cultures is questionable (Chin, 2013; Ospina & Foldy, 2009). When addressing leadership as it relates to people of colour in research, it is treated like a special case instead of a source for

developing, theorising, conceptualising, and understanding leadership experiences from a different perspective (Chin, 2013; Ospina & Foldy, 2009). However, while some studies have investigated leadership within ethnic minority contexts (Okoyi *et al.*, 2009) and leadership in micro and small businesses (Al Mamun *et al.*, 2018), none have specifically examined the cultural influence of leadership within the context of ethnic minority micro-businesses in London.

Chin (2013) stated in a review of leadership literature in education on the effect of race and ethnicity on leadership, that race and ethnicity were perceived as a constraint that needs to be managed. A set of studies looked at race and ethnicity as a personal resource where leaders transform negative experiences into constructive change. These studies approach race and ethnicity as socio-political issues with collective meaning (Chin, 2013). Another set of studies looked at how the social identity of a group can become a personal resource for racial and ethnic leaders while grappling with power dynamics within their immediate environment (Chin, 2013). Also, current studies on leadership from a social and ecological context suggest an explicit bias in the definition of leadership based on gender, race, and ethnicity, portraying the behaviour and leadership effectiveness of women and people of colour in a limited way (Chin, 2013).

However, limited empirical studies have explored the likely result of race on leader-subordinate relations (Parker, 1976). He investigated the behaviour and lack of black and other minority groups in supervisory and managerial positions in three industrial plants using four managerial measures: managerial support, goal emphasis, work facilitation and interaction facilitation among Black, White, and American-of-Mexican origin subordinates of Black and White supervisors. Among the four

managerial measures, black supervisors were highly ranked in managerial support, goal emphasis and work facilitation than their white counterparts but on the same level in interaction facilitation (Parker, 1976). This suggests that the black managerial leadership approach is impactful; it is people and goal-oriented because it encourages subordinates, prioritises task completion and eliminates any obstacle that may obstruct task completion and work as a team. Accordingly, the leadership style of ethnic minority leaders was described as inspiring, nurturing, and inclusive, similar to the four managerial behaviours (Okoyi *et al.*, 2009). Also, it can be likened to paternalistic leadership, as a paternalistic leader is supportive, actively involved in the private and work lives of subordinates and achieves goals (Aycan, 2006; Farh & Cheng, 2000; Mansur *et al.*, 2017).

There is a discontinuity in research on race and ethnicity in leadership studies despite the initial attention it gained from leadership scholars (Ospina & Foldy, 2009). They suggested that it was the opinion of some leadership scholars that the study of non-White leadership would produce less knowledge about what is assumed to be leadership based on the traditional leadership studies field (Ospina & Foldy, 2009). Ospina & Foldy (2009) explain that Traditional leadership theories and leadership research represent Western ideas, which partly explains the colour-blind and gender-blind approach towards traditional leadership theory. They implied that race and ethnicity should be considered in the exploration of leadership as most leadership theory claims implicitly or explicitly to be identity neutral but, in large part, do not consider or incorporate other cultural beliefs in the meaning and development of leadership theories (Ospina & Foldy, 2009).

Also, they argued that leadership literature should move beyond viewing leadership as a relational property of a system that manifests in a collective shared interest of a group to viewing leadership from a race and ethnicity point of view (Ospina & Foldy, 2009). Leadership is more than just the relationship between leader and followers and the collectiveness of a group. Leadership on race and ethnicity will provide a much richer context to understand human experiences and leadership (Ospina & Foldy, 2009).

2.10 Leadership Style / Approach

Most of the current leadership styles are based on Western or American constructs, with little attention given to the possibility of non-Western leadership styles or understanding of the leadership perceptions of other cultures (Alves *et al.*, 2006; Ardichvili, 2001). Hence, the leadership style of ethnic minority groups has received less attention (Okoyi *et al.*, 2009). Although, there is evidence that ethnic minority leaders embrace a nurturing, appealing, inspiring and comforting leadership style in the form of transformational leadership (Okoyi *et al.*, 2009). Leadership style is a reflection and expression of the actions of leaders (Alkahtani, 2016; Franco & Matos, 2015; Wendt *et al.*, 2009). Leadership styles or approaches cannot be fully explored without referring to traditional leadership theories such as the behavioural theory of leadership.

The behavioural theory of leadership, also known as the style theory, was a major shift from the trait theory that focuses on attributes and the personality of a leader to the actions of a leader (Horner, 1997). This shift was due to the inconsistencies and unsuccessfulness of the trait theory, which led to the emergence of behavioural leadership, which approached leadership in organisations from a social

angle concentrating on the behaviour or actions of leaders that enhance organisations (Harrison, 2017; Horner, 1997; Northouse, 2021). Behavioural leadership hold the assumption that leadership behaviour can be imbibed and emulated through observation and learning. Northouse (2021) suggested that leaders adopt two types of behaviours: task behaviour and relationship behaviour. The behaviour of a leader can be used to evaluate the leader's influence, and it can determine the success or performance of a leader in an organisation (Horner, 1997).

Prominent among behavioural leadership theories is the classical leadership styles of democracy, autocracy, and laissez-faire (Lewin, 1939). Democratic leadership style encourages or promotes the participation of subordinates in decision-making. While autocratic leadership entails giving orders to people on what to do, and Laissez-faire leadership is a hand-off leadership style where the leader delegates more (Harrison, 2017). Also, the Michigan and Ohio State leadership studies posit that leadership performance is influenced by different leadership behaviour. Also, these studies suggested that leadership can be learnt and developed, and they do not support the idea that leaders are born (Horner, 1997). These studies were conducted simultaneously between 1946 to 1956. They identified several leadership behaviours that were grouped into two leadership dimensions, initial structure or task-oriented and consideration behaviour or interpersonal relations, which can either be high or low or a combination of both (Harrison, 2017; Horner, 1997). The initial structure consists of a group of leadership behaviours directed at creating a clear pattern or system of work in an organisation. For example, making clear organisational goals and expectations, establishing organisational policies and procedures, controlling, supervising, and setting clear targets. Consideration behaviour is a leadership behaviour that emphasises interpersonal relationships with employees or subordinates and focuses

on their welfare and well-being. Another significant behavioural leadership is Blake & Mouton leadership or managerial grid, a behavioural leadership model that viewed effective leadership as task-oriented and people-oriented (Harrison, 2017). Blake & Mouton's behavioural leadership model or managerial grid is one of the early empirical studies of leadership that became a framework of reference for effective leadership and was mostly adopted for leadership training (Harrison, 2017; Horner, 1997).

According to Amanchukwu *et al.* (2015), leadership style is the approach adopted by a leader to manage and support a group of people. Sometimes it determines the type of leadership style a leader adopts and helps shape his or her leadership behaviour (Alkahtani, 2016). Emotional intelligence could guide and direct a leader towards adopting an appropriate leadership style (Alkahtani, 2016). He defined emotional intelligence as a leader's capability to identify, observe and control his or her emotions and that of others to attain loyalty, realise certain objectives and improve performance (Alkahtani, 2016). The appropriate leadership style that fits the ever-changing business environment is necessary to tackle the challenges it brings and maintain stability in the process (Alkahtani, 2016). Therefore, achieving and maintaining balance within a firm and its environment depends on the leader's leadership style (Alkahtani, 2016; Franco & Matos, 2015; Porter, 1998; Yahaya & Ebrahim, 2016). Leadership helps to foster longevity and organisational resilience by adapting to external changes, thus promoting sustainable growth (Yahaya & Ebrahim, 2016).

The two most researched and used leadership theories are transformational and transactional leadership theories (Alkahtani, 2016; Franco & Matos, 2015; Gandolfi & Stone, 2018; Schimmoeller, 2010; Yahaya & Ebrahim, 2016; Yukl, 2008).

Although there are others, these two are more effective in achieving organisational performance and understanding leadership behaviour. They also said the two significant leadership behaviours are task and relationship-oriented, equivalent to transactional and transformational leadership styles (Wendt *et al.*, 2009). According to Amanchukwu *et al.* (2015), some factors can help determine an effective leadership style or when to adopt one or a combination of leadership styles. The following are the factors:

- Size of an Institution and Organisation

The decision-making process could be centralised as an organisation experience growth and expansion, which may result in low participation in decision-making.

- Degree of Interaction/Communication

Due to the uncertainty surrounding many organisational situations, leaders must interact and be involved with their employees. By doing so, leaders can concentrate on serious matters and make sure that organisational learning can take place. The quality of communication or relationship between leaders and employees in an organisation tends to influence the organisation's management style, with the primary issue being how to get the employees to work as a team and accomplish stated goals.

- Personality of Members

The attitude and character of a leader and employees in an organisation can influence the leadership style of that organisation. Some people often respond more positively to certain leadership styles than others. Individuals who rely on orders are generally reluctant to partake in organisational matters because they

would instead be told what to do than take the initiative and prefer a structured organisation. Those with a good sense of direction, who want to advance their career and participate in decision-making processes in the organisation, are more receptive to open and collaborative leadership styles. Leaders are expected to adjust to these situations, encourage those who participate in the decision-making process and direct those who are more comfortable being told what to do.

- Goal Congruency

It is the consistency of harmony in an organisation where the parties involved ensure that all its activities are compatible with achieving its goals. Organisations with a high degree of balance of objectives assess their operations to ensure that nothing impedes their ability to achieve their goals.

- Level of Decision Making

Distinguishing effective leaders from inadequate leaders is a significant problem for management. An excellent way to differentiate is the quality of decision-making, as an effective leader makes good decisions that produce a favourable result for the organisation. Also, employee reasoning and the ability to perceive things play a vital role in the application, execution, and result of decision-making. Also, in an organisation where power is centralised, there needs to be more provision for lower-level employees to contribute to decision-making. In such situations, instructions are given, and employees are expected to comply without hesitation or complaint.

There are various leadership styles, and recently many more approaches to leadership have emerged, such as leader-member exchange, transactional leadership, transformational leadership, and entrepreneurial leadership (Harrison, 2017; Omeihe *et al.*, 2020; Northouse, 2021). Franco & Matos (2015) concluded,

based on empirical research carried out on three Portuguese firms, that there is no pure leadership style that SME owners resolutely adopt, and the appropriate leadership style depends on the owner, market environment, industry, and location. Different leadership approaches have different outcomes in different situations (Franco & Matos, 2015). Therefore, leadership styles should be selected and adapted to suit an individual, situation, and organisation (Amanchukwu *et al.*, 2015; Franco & Matos, 2015).

According to Wang & Poutziouris (2010) and Yukl (2008), there is no panacea to all business problems with a single leadership style (Franco & Matos, 2015). Transactional and transformational leadership styles could be more effective and appropriate for small businesses due to their small size and flexibility, as suggested by (Franco & Matos, 2015; Love & Roper, 2015; Matzler *et al.*, 2008). Ethnic minority incorporate their cultural beliefs into their business and leadership approach and engage mostly in small businesses due to a combination of socio-economic factors as highlighted earlier in this chapter (Fadahunsi *et al.*, 2000; Ram & Jones, 2008). Based on the suggestions by (Franco & Matos, 2015; Love & Roper, 2015; Matzler *et al.*, 2008), it means that ethnic minorities are more likely to adopt either transformational or transactional leadership approaches. At the same time, the paternalistic leadership style is a recognised non-Western leadership style, culturally bounded, dominant, and effective, and a common feature and practice in African and Asian small businesses (Farh & Cheng, 2000; Jackson, 2016; Wanasika *et al.*, 2011). However, Chen *et al.* (2014) claimed that both transformational and paternalistic leadership styles have some common attributes, such as motivating, stimulating, and providing individualised care to followers.

2.10.1 Transactional Leadership Theory

The transactional leadership theory was introduced by (Burns, 1978). It is a contractual relationship between a leader and subordinates where reward and punishment are applied to achieve performance. Transactional leaders focus more on tasks and are very responsive to the performances of their followers (Bass, 1997). They make clear goals, assign roles and lead followers towards achieving established goals (Jansen *et al.*, 2009). Also, they practise the reward system, where employees are rewarded for their effort, a give-and-take process based strictly on performance (Aziz *et al.*, 2013; Harrison, 2017). The transactional leadership style is a relationship of exchange, and rewards are given for positive results achieved by subordinates (Franco & Matos, 2015; Harrison, 2017; Yahaya & Ebrahim, 2016). According to Harrison (2017), the transactional leadership style is built on two core behaviours, contingent reward, and active management by exception. The relationship could be in the form of a contingent reward where tasks and rewards are explained and directives and instructions are given to subordinates on how to achieve the expected performance (Jansen *et al.*, 2009). While active management by exception is monitoring performance, and measures are taken to correct or improve bad performances when required (Baškarada *et al.*, 2017; Harrison, 2017; Jansen *et al.*, 2009). The relationship between the leader and subordinates in transactional leadership does not go beyond the agreed exchange of value (Yahaya & Ebrahim, 2016).

Empirical research on three Portuguese firms suggests that there is no one clear leadership style that small business owners strongly practise, and the most suitable leadership style depends on factors such as the owner, location, Industry, and

market environment (Franco & Matos, 2015). Different leadership styles have different outcomes, for example, the transactional leadership style produced better leadership results in a case study investigated among three Portuguese firms (Franco & Matos, 2015). They cited corporation, determination, motivation, and some level of satisfaction from employees as an added result (Franco & Matos, 2015). Under the transactional leadership style, employees were focused and determined to achieve the company's goals and expressed satisfaction with the results attained and with the company's leadership. In contrast, a transformational leadership style is more effective in a dynamic or challenging atmosphere that requests motivational and inspiring leadership to encourage better performance (Franco & Matos, 2015).

The relationship between leaders and followers in transactional leadership is mutual and beneficial to both the leaders and followers (Rodrigues & Ferreira, 2015; Yahaya & Ebrahim, 2016). Hard-working employees are crucial to achieving organisational goals through effective leadership by the leader, and the incentive for hard work and meeting targets are either financial or non-financial rewards. The transactional leader is task-oriented, whose sole purpose or motive is to set and accomplish targets, and the motivation for subordinates is the promised reward (Franco & Matos, 2015). Further, Harrison (2017) stated that using contingent rewards in transactional leadership to motivate subordinates is a significant source of controversy. Although, it is effective in improving organisational effectiveness and job attitude and achieving results in the short term. The consequences in the long term may result in a robotic attitude and the suppression of the need for competition, where subordinates only perform when there is a reward (Harrison, 2017).

2.10.2 Transformational Leadership Theory

For the past two decades, organisational researchers have been more intrigued by transformational leadership and transactional leadership style, amongst other theories (Franco & Matos, 2015; Sakiru *et al.*, 2013). Bass (1997) argued that the transformational leadership approach can achieve improved performance in most situations and can be democratic, autocratic, directive, and participative. Also, Franco & Matos (2015) concluded that the transformational leadership approach is result related, encourages risk-taking and achieves job satisfaction, while the transactional leadership approach is effective in a result and performance-based working environment. Aziz *et al.* (2013) claimed that transformational and transactional leadership approaches are suitable for SMEs for one primary reason, both styles can positively impact the performance of individuals and organisations. But the transformational leadership approach is more prevalent in a collectivist culture where leaders tend to believe they have a moral responsibility to their subordinate's welfare (Bass, 1997). It is participative in an individualistic society and more directive in a collectivistic society (Bass, 1997).

Most Asia national cultures have a high degree of collectivism based on their belief and family system, which promote absolute loyalty, teamwork, harmony, and strict respect for seniority (Shim & Steers, 2012). For example, India, Pakistan, Bangladesh, China etc., are all collectivistic societies where family or the group's interest comes first before personal matters. Everyone endeavours to support each other and are willing to be led and guided towards a common goal (Hofstede, 2006). Transformational leadership behaviour is effective in inspiring and encouraging subordinates to accomplish goals beyond their expectations (Afsar *et al.*, 2019;

Yahaya & Ebrahim, 2016). Their behaviour suggests support while catering to their follower's or subordinates' needs and development (Nanjundeswaraswamy & Swamy, 2014). They utilise inspiration, motivation, intellectual stimulation, and individualised consideration on subordinates to drive and achieve high performance (Bass, 1990; Burns, 1978; Harrison, 2017; Yahaya & Ebrahim, 2016).

Further, transformational leaders employ inspirational motivation, idealised influence, intellectual stimulation, and individual consideration to achieve cooperation and success in the workplace (Bass, 1990). The four core dimensions mentioned are essential elements in transformational leadership behaviour (Bass, 1990). Inspirational motivation is the level at which a leader can inspire followers or subordinates with his or her vision by creating a strong sense of purpose for them to be wholly committed to the group goal. Through idealised influence, transformational leaders command respect and inspire followers with their behaviour and mission. They uphold high moral standards and are seen as role models by followers who strive to emulate them. While intellectual stimulation is the ability of a leader to influence followers to innovate and achieve creativity. Creating opportunities for growth by delegating responsibilities to subordinates and challenging them to be independent. Finally, individualised consideration is the emotional impact of a leader on his subordinates, empathetic to their situations and supporting them to achieve their personal needs and corporate goals (Bass, 1990). Transformational leaders transform people to reach far beyond their expectations and give a sense of purpose through clear goals and vision (Yahaya & Ebrahim, 2016).

2.11 Paternalistic leadership, a cultural leadership

There has been an increase in interest in understanding cultural influences on leadership behaviour (House *et al.*, 2001; House *et al.*, 2002; Byrne & Bradley, 2007; Wendt *et al.*, 2009). The lack of empirical studies into ethnic minority leadership styles raises more questions about the generalisation of leadership styles in minority groups by scholars from social and organisational fields (Parker, 1976). These scholars ignore vital but unique elements that are particular to certain racial groups (Jackson, 2016). Cultural perspective is strong in recognising cultural values and attitudes in different societies (Tayeb, 1994). It exposes the differences in the behaviour of cultural groups, even in similar circumstances, due to the underlying differences in their values and attitudes (Tayeb, 1994). Leaders are by-products of their culture (Wendt *et al.*, 2009); ethnic minorities depend on their indigenous culture to lead, so based on that, the ethnic minority leadership style is culturally grounded (Ospina & Foldy, 2009). Hence the expected and encouraged behaviours such as respect by their respective cultures and societies (House *et al.*, 1999).

Suriyankietkaew & Avery (2016), in their findings, acknowledged that culture plays a pivotal role in leadership. They asserted that some leadership styles might not be effective in some cultures due to cultural differences. They insinuated that some Western leadership styles might not be productive in the East because of cultural differences. For example, paternalistic leadership is a cultural leadership suitable and applicable in other societies worldwide (Aycan, 2006; Jackson, 2016; Pellegrini & Scandura, 2008; Wanasika *et al.*, 2011). Even though Paternalistic leadership is synonymous with China and has its roots in Confucianism (Aycan, 2006; Farh & Cheng, 2000), it transcends beyond Chinese indigenous culture (Pellegrini &

Scandura, 2008; Wanasika *et al.*, 2011). Paternalistic leadership is an intricate network of different dimensions, such as morality, benevolence, and authority (Farh & Cheng, 2000). It is a cultural leadership, and it flourishes in the culture of the people where it is practised (Ayman *et al.*, 2000). Hence the review of paternalistic leadership in this study.

According to Alves *et al.* (2006), research aimed at analysing the application of leadership theories across cultures implies that leadership practises are culturally bound. It is a confirmation that culture influences leadership and is significant in understanding leadership (Eagly & Chin, 2010). This suggests that Hofstede's cultural framework and the GLOBE study acknowledge that leadership is culturally bounded (Javidan *et al.*, 2016). However, there is no universal leadership theory (Alves *et al.*, 2006). So, the attempts to impose Western leadership constructs in other societies by some scholars show bias and will eventually fail due to cultural differences (Ardichvili, 2001; Harrison; 2017; Jackson, 2016). These cultural differences are evident in a leader's behaviour which is shaped by cultural values (Ardichvili, 2001; Eagly & Chin, 2010).

Alves *et al.* (2006) posited that there is no global leadership even with the numerous leadership theories. However, the GLOBE study identified the charismatic/transformational leadership approach as a universally endorsed leadership style (Javidan *et al.*, 2016; House *et al.*, 2004). Despite the importance of cultural differences across nations, some leadership approaches enjoy a popular endorsement and are preferred universally across nations (House *et al.*, 2004). This contradicts the assumption that cultural differences play an integral role in shaping distinct leadership behaviour and that there is no global leadership (Alves *et al.*, 2006;

Ardichvili, 2001; Chin, 2003). However, paternalistic leadership is a recognised cultural leadership but with less acceptance and promotion, or the creation of awareness of it from Western scholars (Ardichvili, 2001; Aycan, 2006; Jackson, 2016; Mussolino & Calabrò, 2014). The GLOBE study was criticised for merely mentioning paternalistic leadership in their cross-cultural study (Jackson, 2016) with the claimed that paternalistic leadership was not incorporated in the GLOBE study but rather, a connection with paternalistic leadership was drawn with humane orientation. Even the GLOBE study admitted to cultural differences across nations in the attributes and characteristics of a leader (Ardichvili, 2001; Javidan *et al.*, 2016). So, it is surprising that a widely used cross-cultural study by academics such as the GLOBE study ignores one of the recognised non-Western cultural leadership styles in paternalistic leadership (Aycan *et al.*, 2000; Wanasika *et al.*, 2011). Hence, the present study aims to address the critique of the GLOBE approach by bringing an explicit exploration of paternalistic leadership in the context of ethnic minority micro-businesses.

2.12 Paternalistic Leadership

Paternalistic leadership suggests a dyadic and hierarchical relationship between a leader and a subordinate. It is endorsed in high power and collectivistic society, and it is culturally bound (Ardichvili, 2001; Aycan *et al.*, 2000; Mansur *et al.*, 2017). It is a familiar system in African and Asian cultures, mainly in the family unit (Jackson, 2016). Paternalistic leadership is thought to be a system of controlling or managing nations, individuals, or businesses in an invasive or fatherly benevolent way (Mussolino & Calabrò, 2014; Pellegrini & Scandura, 2008).

Literature on strategic management and leadership has shown that paternalistic leadership is not generally accepted (Ardichvili, 2001; Mussolino &

Calabrò, 2014). Despite the plethora of work in this field of research, there are limited empirical studies on paternalistic leadership (Pellegrini & Scandura, 2008). Aycan (2006) claimed that paternalistic leadership had received little attention from present scholars of management and psychological sciences even though paternalistic leadership is a dominant leadership style in Africa, Asia, and the Middle East (Aycan, 2006; Chen *et al.*, 2014; Farh & Cheng, 2000; Jackson, 2016). Also, it was revealed in cross-cultural empirical studies that countries such as Pakistan, India, China, Nigeria, Kenya, Taiwan, Zambia, Zimbabwe, South Africa, and South Korea all have high paternalistic values (Aycan *et al.*, 2000; Farh & Cheng, 2000; Pellegrini & Scandura, 2008; Wanasika *et al.*, 2011).

In line with previous studies, Chin (2013) implied that a leader's socio-cultural context and lived experiences could influence the leader's vision and relationships with followers. The cultural influence of the leadership approach of ethnic minorities makes for a different leadership experience which needs further investigation (Chin, 2013). However, current leadership theories are based on how the Western world, that is, America and the UK, perceive leadership (Chin, 2013; Ospina & Foldy, 2009). Chin (2013) suggested diversity in the approach towards leadership research in the area of race, ethnicity, gender and other dimensions of determining diversity in order to understand the complex nature of leadership behaviour. Due to increasing diversity in society and organisations, it has become necessary to understand the socio-cultural influence on leadership behaviour (Chin, 2013).

According to Farh & Cheng (2000), paternalistic leadership behaviour uses fatherly benevolence and moral integrity with strict discipline and authority to conjure obedience. They viewed paternalistic leadership from a three-dimensional

perspective, authority, benevolence, and morality. The authoritarian paternalistic leader demands and expects obedience. The benevolent paternalistic leader focuses on the well-being of subordinates, showing care and support and meeting their needs. While the moral paternalistic leader leads by example, gains respect and is a role model for subordinates. These are evident in the definition of paternalistic leadership style (Farh & Cheng, 2000).

The description of paternalistic leadership and the expected behaviour between a paternalistic leader and subordinates are summarised in the table 5 below, focusing on the three dimensions of paternalism. The descriptions Farh & Cheng (2000) provided in the table below define paternalistic leadership and the three dimensions used in this study to understand the influences on the leadership approach of ethnic minority-led micro-businesses in London. Farh & Cheng (2000) define paternalistic leadership style as a leadership style that combines strong discipline and authority with fatherly benevolence and moral integrity. Paternalistic leadership is not a unified construct, instead, it consists of three dimensions of authority, benevolence and morality that are based on Confucian beliefs, as highlighted earlier (Chen *et al.*, 2014).

Table 5. Paternalistic leader behaviours and subordinate responses

Leader behaviour		Subordinate response
<p>Authoritarianism</p> <p>Authority and control</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Unwilling to delegate • Top-down communication • Information secrecy • Tight control <p>Underestimation of subordinate competence</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ignore subordinate suggestions • Belittle subordinate contributions <p>Image building</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Act in a dignified manner • Exhibit high self-confidence • Information manipulation <p>Didactic behaviour</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Insist on high performance standards • Reprimand subordinates for poor performance • Provide guidance and instructions for improvements 		<p>Compliance</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Show public support • Avoid open conflict with boss • Avoid expressing dissension Obedience • Accept leader's directives unconditionally • Loyal to leader • Trust in leader <p>Respect and fear</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Show deep respect • Express fear in awe of the leader <p>Have a sense of shame</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Willing to confess mistakes • Take leader's instructions seriously • Correct mistakes and improve
<p>Benevolent Leadership</p> <p>Individualised care</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Treat employees as family members • Provide job security • Assist during personal crises • Show holistic concern • Avoid embarrassing subordinates in public • Protect even grave errors of subordinates 		<p>Show gratitude</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Never forget leader's favours <p>Strive to reciprocate</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sacrifice self-interest for leader • Take assignments seriously • Meet leader's expectation • Work diligently
<p>Leader Morality and Integrity</p> <p>Unselfishness</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Does not abuse authority for personal gain • Does not mix personal interests with business interests • Put collective interests ahead of personal interests <p>Lead by example</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Act as an exemplar in work and personal conduct 		<p>Identification</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identify with leader's values and goals • Internalise leader's values Modelling • Imitate leader behaviour

Source: Farh & Cheng, 2000

2.12.1 Morality

The dimension of morality is portrayed as a leader's behaviour that suggests superior personal moral values, discipline, unselfishness and leading by example (Cheng *et al.*, 2004; Farh & Cheng, 2000; Pellegrini & Scandura, 2008). A moral leader is expected to be a good example to subordinates in work and personal conduct and not to use or abuse his position of power for personal benefit or mix personal interest with business interest (Farh & Cheng, 2000). Moral leadership is associated with building trust and being a good example to subordinates (Northouse, 2021). This dimension of paternalistic leadership focuses on the leader's behaviour and the leader's moral expectations, such as setting high standards and displaying integrity (Farh & Cheng, 2000; Pellegrini & Scandura, 2008).

2.12.2 Benevolence

Benevolence suggests that a leader shows genuine care and concern for the well-being of subordinates (Chen *et al.*, 2014; Farh & Cheng, 2000; Pellegrini & Scandura, 2008). It is a key dimension of paternalistic leadership. Benevolent values are love, generosity, family, and community, and it is suitable in a humane orientation which is a society that encourages love, caring, generosity and being kind to others (Mansur *et al.*, 2017). The leader forms personalised relationships with followers or subordinates in their public and personal life (Aycan, 2006; Farh & Cheng, 2000). Benevolence spurs performance and creates a good relationship between the boss and subordinates. This relationship can take the form of a social exchange where the followers are willing to respond positively to and enjoy the benefits of the benevolent behaviour of a paternalistic leader (Cheng *et al.*, 2014; Farh & Cheng, 2000). This social exchange is also known as *bao*, which means reciprocity (Farh & Cheng, 2000).

One good turn deserves another. Paternalistic leadership without benevolence is incomplete because it is the nurturing aspect of paternalistic leadership. It is the dimension compensating for the paternalistic leader's authority (Mansur *et al.*, 2017). Benevolent leaders are generous towards subordinates and expect respect and loyalty in return (Mansur *et al.*, 2017).

2.12.3 Authority

The dimension of authority is the only constant in the definition of paternalistic leadership by scholars (Aycan, 2006; Farh & Cheng, 2000; Mansur *et al.*, 2017). Authority relates to a leader's behaviour that signifies control, the centrality of power and the ability of a leader to demand respect and obedience from subordinates (Mansur *et al.*, 2017). This dimension is essential to paternalistic leadership (Farh & Cheng, 2000) as it supplements the other two dimensions and makes the leader stand out as a leader because it gives the leader the authority to be in charge. The conceptualisation of the dimension of authority is why paternalistic leadership has attracted so much negative attention from Western scholars (Aycan *et al.*, 2000; Jackson, 2016; Mansur *et al.*, 2017). This dimension suggests power distance between the leaders and subordinates (Cheng *et al.*, 2014). In paternalistic leadership, the leader is expected to show authority to represent firm control, power, and discipline (Farh & Cheng, 2000), and the leader exercises power to achieve discipline from subordinates (Cheng *et al.*, 2014). However, authority is associated with authoritarian leadership and fear, which does not promote a free exchange of ideas and concerns in the relationship between the leader and subordinates (Cheng *et al.*, 2014).

The paternalistic leadership style is also described as a fatherly leadership style where people in positions of power or authority make decisions for their subordinates

without their consent (Mussolino & Calabrò, 2014; Pellegrini & Scandura, 2008). Subordinates are expected to show loyalty and obedience and have absolute trust in the judgement of their leader. They are not expected to express alternative views that may conflict with that of their leader in public, and the leader is believed to be infallible (Mussolino & Calabrò, 2014). Nevertheless, it may be an immoderate show of concern as it may interfere with the freedom of the individuals involved (Pellegrini & Scandura, 2008). The key to the definition of paternalistic leadership is the combination of two essential dimensions that must coexist: control and care (Mansur *et al.*, 2017).

To explore the endorsement of paternalistic leadership dimensions among clusters, Mansur *et al.* (2017) gathered data from 59 countries and created ten cultural clusters. It is a semblance of the GLOBE study. 1. Anglo 2. Confucian, 3. Eastern European, 4. Germanic European, 5. Latin American, 6. Latin European, 7. Middle Eastern, 8. Nordic European, 9. Sub-Saharan Africa, 10. Southeast Asia. However, this study concentrated on four of the ten cultural clusters; Southeast Asia, Sub-Saharan Africa, Confucian Asia, and Middle Eastern because they represent the majority of ethnic minority groups in the UK and are part of the focus of this study. These clusters consist of countries from specific regions that are grouped into clusters representing the people and culture of that region. The following cluster includes:

- Southeast Asia: India, Indonesia, Malaysia, Philippines, and Thailand.
- Confucian Asia: China, Japan, Taiwan, Hong Kong, South Korea, and Singapore.
- Sub-Saharan Africa: Black South Africa, Nigeria, Zambia, and Zimbabwe
- Middle Eastern: Egypt, Kuwait, Morocco, Qatar, and Turkey

Mansur *et al.* (2017) explored the dimensions of paternalistic leadership as an independent leadership style. Morality was replaced with integrity. It was used to explain the motive and intention of the leader when applying care and control (Mansur *et al.*, 2017). They claimed that integrity is an essential characteristic of paternalistic leadership, and high integrity represents the likelihood of acting on behalf of others or being selfless. In their findings, the four societal culture clusters that make up and closely represent the majority of ethnic minority groups here in the UK scored high in the three dimensions of paternalistic leadership. The Confucian Asia cluster scored much higher on the endorsement of authority compared to the other three clusters. This may be due to their hierarchical and patriarchal leadership system. The Southeast Asian, Sub-Saharan, and Middle Eastern clusters scored high on paternalism, which is a positive endorsement and means they regard all three dimensions as vital to effective leadership.

However, Weber (1947) had a contrary view of paternalism. He described paternalism as a legitimated authority, a traditional form of control or domination that will not stand the test of time as it will be replaced with a new model of leadership approach in the workplace where rules and protection of human rights will be prioritised. He painted paternalism as authoritarian. However, this view was disputed and argued that the paternalistic leadership approach gives care and support to subordinates (Aycan, 2006; Farh & Cheng, 2000; Mansur *et al.*, 2017; Pellegrini & Scandura, 2008). Aycan (2006) posits that, although paternalism is controversial and ineffective in the West, it is an effective leadership style in the socio-cultural contexts where it originated. In agreement, Pellegrini & Scandura (2008) suggested that

paternalistic leadership is an effective leadership style in many non-Western countries. It has a positive impact when rooted in the people's culture.

Jackson (2016) suggested that the meaning of paternalism has been misconstrued to connote negativity. Likened to authoritarianism and not favoured in the Western world. He further stated that Western cross-cultural literature has ignored exploring paternalistic leadership styles in non-Western cultures, for example, Africa, instead of proffering Western leadership styles as alternatives. This may be due to their bias or democratic and individualistic mindset in society (Harrison, 2017; Jackson, 2016). Attempting to apply Western leadership concepts in other countries without acknowledging cultural differences is a remedy for failure (Ardichvili, 2001). A more recent cross-cultural study from fifty-nine countries suggested paternalism as a less authoritarian leadership style (Mansur *et al.*, 2017). They claimed that there is no paternalistic leadership without benevolence and emphasised the need for a leader's integrity. Further, these divergent views on paternalistic leadership are based on the perception or construct of the scholars because it all depends on which angle, they are looking at paternalism. If the focus is on authority, the outcome might be negative, but if it is on benevolence, it may be positive (Jackson, 2016; Pellegrini & Scandura, 2008). Also, the misconception and lack of support for paternalistic leadership may result from scarce empirical and comparative studies across multiple and diverse societies and the numerous forms it can assume (Mansur *et al.*, 2017).

The paternalistic leadership style is prevalent in collectivist and high-power distance societies where it is rooted in the cultural and traditional beliefs of the people (Ayca, 2006; Farh & Cheng, 2000). In such a society, the leader believes he or she has power and is obligated to care for and make decisions for persons under his or

her care (Mansur *et al.*, 2017; Pellegrini & Scandura, 2008). The leader is also involved in the working life of subordinates and their personal life. It violates privacy in an individualistic society (Jackson, 2016; Pellegrini & Scandura, 2008). In collectivist cultures, the emphasis is on family and teamwork. Family acts like a cushion, a support group that provides protection, care, and guidance to address the need for regular contact and personal relationships among members. It enables paternalistic leadership to prevail in collectivist cultures (Aycan, 2006; Mussolino & Calabrò, 2014). Further, respect for the dignity of others, group solidarity, teamwork, service to others and a spirit of harmony and interdependence are five identified core values of African leaders (Wanasika *et al.*, 2011). These core values of African leaders suggest that they will be more accepting of a paternalistic leadership approach based on benevolence and morality.

Nevertheless, paternalistic leadership is a standard approach among African leaders, even with the negative perception associated with it in Western culture (Aycan, 2006; Jackson, 2016). Paternalistic leadership may sound problematic as it contains elements of authoritarianism as presume by Western scholars, but it is not an authoritarian leadership style because of its benevolent behaviour (Aycan, 2006; Jackson, 2016). It is more effective when adopted with morality and benevolence (Mansur *et al.*, 2017; Mussolino & Calabrò, 2014). According to Pellegrini & Scandura (2008), paternalistic leadership has been researched in detail mainly by (Aycan, 2006; Farh & Cheng, 2000). They proposed frameworks for paternalistic leadership consisting of three dimensions: authority, benevolence, and morality.

Mussolino & Calabrò (2014) explored paternalistic leadership from an organisational perspective, looking at the role of paternalism in family business

succession, the transfer of power or control within the family and the relationship between a leader and subordinate. This can further explain the leadership style in small and family businesses (Mussolino & Calabrò, 2014). They asserted paternalistic leadership is commonly observed in family businesses' organisational structure and culture. It can also dictate the behaviour of the present and next generation of family business members. This leadership style is also referred to as a parent-child relationship, where a dominant leader nurtures and takes decisions in favour of employees (Mussolino & Calabrò, 2014).

Familism or family ties are also important in paternalistic leadership (Mussolino & Calabrò, 2014). The head of the family can influence both the personal and business life of members as he provides safety and care to members and expect loyalty and obedience back from them (Mussolino & Calabrò, 2014). This relationship is mostly with in-group members (Jackson, 2016). There is also a high power distance in this system because of the unequal power relationship between leaders and followers. Typically, subordinates are constantly reminded that their role is to follow and show loyalty; anyone who goes against the leader may be punished, and insubordination is not tolerated (Farh & Cheng, 2000).

Paternalism (paternalistic leadership) is more receptive in a society with high collectivism and high power distance, where people in authority relish having such power and take advantage of it (Aycan *et al.*, 2000; Jackson, 2016). A crucial part of paternalistic leadership is the intention of the leader as they can adopt dual responsibilities of control and care or be authoritarian and benevolent (Mussolino & Calabrò, 2014). This depends strongly on the motivations behind the leader's kindness and care, whether exploitative or benevolent. The leader's motivation is exploitative if

it is strictly based on organisational goals but benevolence when there is a genuine and individualised concern for the well-being of the employees. The motivation behind the actions of a paternalistic leader is another area of paternalism that has been heavily criticised (Aycan, 2006). Paternalistic leadership has similarities with most leadership styles making it more relevant and appropriate for this study.

2.13 Rationale for the choice of paternalistic leadership

Cheng *et al.* (2014) suggested there are some conceptual elements of similarities between transformational leadership style and ethical leadership style with paternalistic leadership style, yet distinct. Transformational leaders provide individualised care but are limited to the work environment. The emotional effect aroused by transformational leaders on their employees is that of optimism or stimulation. They transform followers into leaders, challenge them intellectually and inspire them to accomplish goals beyond their imaginations. In the paternalistic leadership approach, leaders show genuine and individualised care through benevolent leadership. Individualised care can be intrusive because the leader is involved both in work and non-work activities of employees, and the emotions caused by a paternalistic leader are that of respect, security, and fear (Chen *et al.*, 2014; Cheng *et al.*, 2014; Farh & Cheng, 2000). Employees depend heavily on the leader in a paternalistic leadership style, and the relationship between them is like that of a parent and a child (Chen *et al.*, 2014).

Also, the moral dimension of paternalistic leadership relates to ethical leadership. This link suggests that a leader is supposed to uphold high moral standards and lead by example (Chen *et al.*, 2014). Further, there are similarities between paternalistic leadership and transactional leadership styles. Power is

centralised, rewards and punishments are used for compliance, and focus on performance, loyalty and obedience is expected from employees or subordinates both in paternalistic leadership and transactional leadership styles (Jensen *et al.*, 2009; Mansur *et al.*, 2017).

Paternalistic leadership has been compared to leader-member exchange (LMX). Pellegrini & Scandura (2006) looked at the relationship between paternalistic leadership and LMX as paternalistic leadership is highly personal. The connection between both leadership approaches is their dyadic relationship with their subordinates and how they interact with them (Harrison, 2017). Further, Jackson (2016) highlighted a connection between situational leadership and paternalistic leadership. He suggested paternalistic leadership is situational due to how the leader relates with subordinates in exercising authority and expressing care. This leadership style suggests that different situations require different leadership styles (Ardichvili & Manderscheid, 2008). This shows that paternalistic leadership approach embodies elements of other leadership styles.

Also, Ospina & Foldy (2009) implied that ethnic minority leaders rely on their cultural beliefs and experiences to lead. Religion is a culture for most ethnic minorities (Nwankwo *et al.*, 2012). Through religion, people's behaviour is shaped and guided to follow set rules obediently with trust and faith (Parboteeah *et al.*, 2015). Leaders can express their religious beliefs through leadership (Gaitho, 2019). Their religious beliefs partly shape their leadership style, and they apply and promote their religious beliefs even in their firms. As mentioned earlier, the paternalistic leadership approach is rooted in a people's indigenous culture and embodies some religious elements

(Ayca, 2006; Farh & Cheng, 2000). Paternalistic leaders epitomise the culture of the people.

2.14 Summary

The importance of ethnic minority-led micro-businesses cannot be overemphasised. They account for a large of private enterprises in the UK, and the number will continue to grow as it is easy to establish a small business, but at the same time, they fail easily. They experience the most challenges of all businesses based on leadership, size, finance, unfavourable government policies, direct and indirect discrimination, and intense market competition (Achanga *et al.*, 2006; Love & Roper, 2015). In a way, SMEs and ethnic minority small businesses share similar challenges apart from the issue of ethnicity. Ethnic minorities are entrepreneurial partly due to discrimination in the labour market and the need to meet their basic needs in life (Haq, 2015; Jones *et al.*, 2019). Their businesses struggle to grow because of their ethnicity, and the government has attempted to address these challenges but mostly adopted the same approach used with SMEs.

There are different ethnic groups under the umbrella of ethnic minorities, and each has a unique experience that demands a particular approach suitable to them. However, with all these challenges, both ethnic minority-led micro-businesses and SMEs in general, are still increasing in numbers and contributing immensely to the UK economy in many ways, and they require dedicated assistance from the government to provide an enabling environment for continuous growth.

In this chapter, culture is highlighted as instrumental in shaping societies and that religion shapes culture (Mohdali & Pope, 2010; Saroglou, 2011). People apply their cultural values and religious beliefs to navigate through life because it shapes

their beliefs and understanding of life (Beyers, 2017). Culture and religion influence human behaviour (Beyers, 2017; Van Buren III *et al.*, 2020) and so it stands to reason that these concepts will influence the behaviour of ethnic minority micro-business leaders. Hofstede (1983) posits that people come from various cultural backgrounds that shape their belief systems and behaviour and are incorporated into business practices and leadership. Also, ethnic minorities are cultural people, as suggested by (Ospina & Foldy, 2009). They rely on their cultural beliefs and values to lead. However, there is sparse literature describing the leadership style of ethnic minorities and its influence on their businesses, even with the plenitude of leadership literature. There is an argument that Western leadership scholars push and promote their perception of leadership and give less attention to ethnic minority leadership style and non-Western leadership, for example, paternalistic leadership (Chin, 2013; Jackson, 2016).

Paternalistic leadership is a recognised non-Western leadership style rooted in the culture of the people and prevalent in non-Western countries but with less attention (Aycañ, 2006; Chin, 2013; Farh & Cheng, 2000; Jackson, 2016; Mansur *et al.*, 2017). Western scholars mainly criticise it for its authoritarian elements and less on its effectiveness (Aycañ, 2006; Pellegrini & Scandura, 2006). Many cross-cultural studies have attempted to understand leadership in different countries and cultures, looking at different cultural attributes, values and characteristics but applying Western leadership theories, for example, transformational and transactional leadership approaches when there is already a connection with paternalistic leadership by ethnic minorities.

With the previous discussion in mind, the thesis will go on to present the methods and findings for the exploration of the influence of culture on experience of ethnic minority micro-business leaders in London.

3. Chapter Three: Methodology

3.1 Introduction

This chapter discusses the methodology underpinning this present research, the philosophy and strategy adopted for recruitment, data collection and analysis and the rationale for selecting these approaches. Also, the theoretical underpinnings, ethical considerations and limitations of this research are addressed.

Selecting a research methodology is a challenging decision for a researcher, and it should be grounded in the researcher's epistemology considerations, personal convictions, beliefs, interests, and the research's aim and objectives (Opoku *et al.*, 2016). The methodology includes the research philosophy and framework, which is integral to the entire research process (Opoku *et al.*, 2016). Like in the context of this present study where the aim is to capture the essence of the experiences of the leaders of ethnic minority-led micro-businesses in London from their viewpoint. Research design, as a significant component of a research methodology, outlines the strategic course that connects philosophical assumptions to methods that, in turn, refer to the specific technique employed for data collection and analysis (Opoku *et al.*, 2016).

The philosophy for this study is interpretivism using a qualitative phenomenology method. Phenomenology is chosen because it seeks to understand and interpret the essence of human experiences (Creswell & Poth, 2016; Scotland, 2012). Therefore, this study aims to capture the experiences of the leadership style of the leaders of ethnic minority-led micro-businesses. Also, the qualitative approach is employed in this study as it enquires about the meaning assigned to social or human

problems by individuals and describes and interprets human experiences (Creswell & Poth, 2016).

3.2 Research Paradigm/Assumption

This study does not intend to go into the dichotomy between epistemology and ontology or social constructivism and interpretivism. However, it draws knowledge from these assumptions to direct and guide this present study. A research's epistemological and ontological assumptions shape the methodology selection process (Gill, 2014). These assumptions guide the actions of a researcher and explicitly reveal their position based on their choices (Creswell & Poth, 2016). This study supports the assumption that not all human experiences can be quantify

This study leans towards an epistemological stance as it aims to gain knowledge about the lived experiences of ethnic minority micro-business leaders in London from their perspectives. Epistemology is the theory of knowledge that seeks to understand human perspective of the world and their knowledge about the world (Creswell & Poth, 2016). It assists in answering questions about acquiring knowledge and justifying the known knowledge (Creswell & Poth, 2016). The breakdown of the research philosophy of this study can be seen in Figure 1.

This study aims to understand and interpret the meaning of the lived experiences of individuals from their perspective, therefore, an interpretivist approach is adopted. Human beings are complex beings, and each one views the world from different perspectives because they experience it differently (Scotland, 2012), just like how ethnic minorities are complex with different identities, experiences and cultural/religious beliefs that shapes their world (Berthoud, 1998; Carter *et al.*, 2015).

To comprehend their experiences and the significance they attach to their experiences, interpretation becomes essential (Scotland, 2012).

Figure 1: Research Philosophy

Thus, the best way to understand human experiences and behaviour is to see it through the eyes of the person having that experience (Scotland, 2012; Smith *et al.*, 2009), which aligns with the aim of this present study and the qualitative approach (Creswell & Poth, 2016). In contrast, positivists hold views that reflect the scientific method of investigation, using fixed variables, mathematical calculation, and deductive reasoning (quantitative approach) to reach a generalisable conclusion in research (Goldkuhl, 2012). This study does not intend to quantify variables or generalise experiences (Bryman & Bell, 2007) but to understand the ascribed meaning given to experiences and tell it from the point of view of the person experiencing it.

Qualitative and phenomenological approaches are in support of the method of seeking an understanding of human subjective experiences from their perspective (Creswell & Poth, 2016; Neubauer *et al.*, 2019; Sanders, 1982; Smith *et al.*, 2009). Phenomenology should not be informed by any assumption, philosophy, scientific theory, or deductive reasoning process as it is embedded in epistemology (Neubauer *et al.*, 2019; Sanders, 1982). Since there is no clear and precise methodology for phenomenology, the commonalities in the methodology will guide this study, as the research method for phenomenology depends on the phenomenon being studied (Sanders, 1982), which in this case is ethnic minority micro-business leaders in London.

The qualitative interview, particularly the semi-structured interview is a widely employed tool for collecting and capturing comprehensive, detailed data about individuals' experiences is used in this study. Given that this study is a phenomenological study, it is only right to adopt the phenomenological analysis as the method of choice to gain an in-depth understanding of the participants experiences.

3.3 Interpretivism

Epistemology and ontology are interrelated in interpretivism, and both assumptions seek knowledge and understanding of the meaning assigned to human experiences (Goldkuhl, 2012; Scotland, 2012; Smith *et al.*, 2009). According to Cardoso & Ramos (2012), interpretivists believe that knowledge about the world is socially constructed through language and shared meanings. It focuses on human circumstances and the meaning assigned to the circumstances (Cardoso & Ramos, 2012). They believe the role of the researcher is to interpret the meaning others have of the world. Scotland (2012) stated that ontologists view interpretivism from a relative position. They believe people have multiple views of the world and reality is subjective. Each experience is distinct; it helps shape an individual's consciousness; without consciousness, the world is meaningless. Consciousness is the totality of lived experiences that shape a person's personality (Neubauer *et al.*, 2019).

Similarly, the epistemology position of interpretivism is also subjective but established on real-world phenomena (Scotland, 2012; Smith *et al.*, 2009). Conversely, positivists mainly adopt statistical and experimental approaches where they analyse large amounts of data in a confined or controlled environment to find underlying regularities and reach a generalised conclusion (Weber, 2004). They believe that reality is separate from the researcher. This is why this study has adopted an interpretivist approach to better understand the meaning associated with the lived experiences of the leaders of ethnic minority-led micro-businesses in London.

According to the Interpretivist perspective, knowledge of the world is perceived as not existing independently outside of the world (Scotland, 2012; Smith *et al.*, 2009). According to Scotland (2012), a tree is a tree because people discovered it and named

it a tree. Therefore, human beings construct their reality - just as an example, the concepts of leadership and culture and the meaning associated with them by ethnic minorities. Realities are socially constructed through the interaction of people and their environment using language. This means that meaning and knowledge are formed from human experiences, gained through interactions with their world, and conveyed in a social context (Scotland, 2012). This present study employs an interpretivist approach to comprehend and interpret the perspectives, meanings, and shared experiences of leaders of ethnic minority micro-businesses in London regarding the influence of their leadership styles on their businesses.

Further, interpretive research is a qualitative study that explores the meaning and tries to understand a phenomenon from a subjective point of view in its natural place to have more knowledge about it (Smith *et al.*, 2009). The interpretive research approach is suitable to understand a social construct such as leadership (Bresnen, 1995). It is instructive in addressing societal issues affecting underrepresented and marginalised groups regarding gender, race, religion, sexuality, geography, and class. This approach explores questions that seek to comprehend specific topics about disadvantaged individuals or cultures, for example, leadership, inequality, unequal power relations, racism, and sexism in society (Creswell & Poth, 2016). It gives a broad perspective on every aspect of qualitative research. The combination of data collection and analysis, audience and participants, ethics and standard evaluation are all informed by interpretive position (Creswell & Poth, 2016). Interpretivism has been criticised for its lack of standardisation in its approach and the issue of generalisation (Scotland, 2012). He mentioned that interpretivism could not be judged by the same rules as scientific research because it does not accept pure scientific approaches.

Also, interpretivists believe in multiple realities and focus on individuals' subjective realities, which raises concerns for consensus in a research study (Scotland, 2012).

Qualitative researchers conduct research to be nearer to the participants being studied to get first-hand knowledge from participants in their natural environment (Creswell & Poth, 2016). An approach this study applied by conducting a face-to-face semi-structured interview with ethnic minority micro-business leaders in their place of work, in London. Qualitative researchers welcome the idea of multiple realities in research (Creswell & Poth, 2016). One of the characteristics of the epistemology assumption is that the distance between the researcher and the phenomenon being researched is minimal (Creswell & Poth, 2016). This point is also reiterated by (Finlay, 2013) as he implied that the researcher must acknowledge that distance from the phenomenon is inevitable, and researchers should be self-aware of this during research. This is in line with Goldkuhl (2012), who encourages the interaction between the researcher and the subject that is being studied in the data collection process.

Additionally, in a phenomenological study, the researcher cannot separate himself or herself from the phenomenon under investigation. A comprehensive understanding is achieved in a phenomenological study when the researcher is engaged with the phenomenon, cares and is open to new knowledge about the phenomenon without interfering (Finlay, 2013). However, Cardoso & Ramos (2012) suggest that there should be a critical examination of data obtained from social construction through the interaction between the researcher and participants to eliminate concerns about research validity and quality.

3.4 Research Method and Design

Qualitative research is a multi-research method that involves an interpretive and naturalistic approach to studying complex phenomena in their natural settings to gain an understanding of the meaning attached to their experiences (Gill, 2014). Qualitative research focuses more on context, the thickness and richness of data rather than sample size. Phenomenology is a qualitative approach that prioritises the richness of data to quantity (Gill, 2014). Phenomenology studies human experiences, cultural influences, and it is a qualitative approach (Gill, 2014). To an extent, the understanding of an individual's lived experience is shaped by that person's culture and traditions because he or she exists in a culturally conditioned environment (Gill, 2014). Therefore, to have an insight into the impact of the leadership style of the leaders of ethnic minority-led micro-businesses will mean understanding what shapes their experiences. Culture is about the lived experiences of a people, which can be seen through their feelings and behaviour (Gill, 2014). Leadership cannot be understood without first exploring the cultural aspects of people (Bresnen, 1995). Schein (2009) stated that culture and leadership are interrelated. Phenomenology seeks to reveal or bring to light that which cannot be seen by ordinary observation (Creswell & Poth, 2016), as in every experience, there is someone experiencing it (Sanders, 1982). This study will embrace Sander's fundamental components for approaching a phenomenological study, which includes deciding who is to be studied, the number of what is to be investigated, data collection and the phenomenological analysis of data collected.

3.4.1 Qualitative Research

Qualitative research is suitable for exploring issues and problems from the perspective of those experiencing them, focusing on the meaning people attributes to social or human problems (Creswell & Poth, 2016). This approach is exploratory, produces rich data, and unveils the world through interpretation, emphasising participants' views, meaning, and lived experiences, without influencing them (Bryant, 2006; Creswell & Poth, 2016; Rowland, 2005; Walle, 2015).

According to Creswell & Poth (2016), qualitative research begins with an assumption to inquire about the meaning people assign to human experiences, allowing for adaptability and the accommodation of new information in the field (Walle, 2015). Subsequently, face-to-face data is collected in the natural settings follows, leading to pattern and themes identification during analysis. while data analysis establishes patterns and themes. Finally, narratives are constructed from the essence of the people's experiences and expressed through interpretation or description (Creswell & Poth, 2016).

Bryman *et al.* (1996) and Walle (2015) advocate for qualitative research in business and leadership topics for its sensitivity and focus on context. However, they recognise the predominance of quantitative research approaches in leadership literature as confirmed by a study that reviewed sixty empirical studies on leadership and twenty-four leadership styles (Ngoc Khuong *et al.*, 2022). The findings in that study reveals the prevalence of quantitative methods in leadership literature, with only one out of sixty literature that adopted a qualitative research approach. Ngoc Khuong *et al.* (2022) argued that over-reliance on quantitative methods has thwarted the growth of leadership research, recommending qualitative method for an in-depth

analysis of leadership styles, and for its suitability for exploring leadership behaviour, traits, skills, and abilities.

This study adopts a qualitative research approach to comprehend the meaning of the lived experiences of the leaders of ethnic minority-led micro businesses and the cultural influence of their leadership approach. Qualitative research delves into the deep feelings and experiences of people, aiming for a profound understanding rather than generalisation typical in quantitative research (Creswell & Poth, 2016). Quantitative method, with its logical approach and emphasis on empirical data collection is unsuitable for this study, as the focus for this present study is on social interactions, values and meanings which may be challenging to capture statistically (Creswell & Poth, 2016).

The qualitative approach is a regular or familiar approach in business research (Fossey *et al.*, 2002; Walle, 2015), with an array of data collection processes to understand behaviours, performance, cultures, and leadership (Walle, 2015). Qualitative research is adopted in various disciplines, no matter the topic, as qualitative research is designed to aid the understanding of the behaviour or experiences of people through interpretation and description (Fossey *et al.*, 2002). This approach creates a detailed description of leadership and culture, communicating experiences in the form of interpretation from the perspective of the individuals having the experiences (Bryman & Bell, 2007). The focus is on the lived experiences of people being studied instead of the researcher. It is exploratory, it does not aim to influence or interfere with the phenomenon or participants under study or investigation (Scotland, 2012; Dasgupta, 2015).

Figure 2: A flow chart of data Analysis Process

Source: Adaptation of (Smith *et al.*, 2009)

3.4.2 Emergent Design

The emergent framework is used for this study as it is incorporated in a qualitative and phenomenological study that allows for flexibility. Its inclusiveness will be essential for new information in a research process. According to Creswell & Poth (2016), the qualitative research process is emergent and adaptable and accommodates changes or new information in the research process. They stated that additional information might emerge when the researcher gets to the field to collect data that may require a change in the research question or data collection strategy.

3.5 Research Approach/Method

The research entails a comprehensive study of a phenomenon (individual, groups of individuals, societies, or objects) to gather information or gain a new understanding of the phenomenon (Neubauer *et al.*, 2019). This approach will produce a deep understanding of the leadership styles of ethnic minority micro-businesses as it will assist in unravelling the essence of their experiences. This study will not be testing predetermined hypotheses; instead, it will adopt the qualitative research method in order to explore and understand the human experience from their perspective in their natural setting and not using predetermined information (Bryant, 2006; Creswell & Poth, 2016).

3.5.1 Phenomenology

Phenomenology is adopted in this research as it focuses on understanding the lived experiences of a phenomenon and provides a description and interpretation of the experience through the person who had the experience (Creswell & Poth, 2016; Groenewald, 2004). It allows for the use of both description and interpretation for describing and interpreting people's views about their experiences (Gill, 2014). This approach concentrates on experiential meaning (experiences) to gain detailed descriptions that give the foundation for reflective analysis, which reveals the essence of an experience (Moustakas, 1994; Finlay, 2013). Different phenomenological methodologies have been adopted in qualitative research to investigate human experiences (Gill, 2014). Ethnography was considered for this study but was discarded due to the global pandemic (COVID-19) that restricted physical contact, and movement. This made it difficult for me to spend time in research sites to observe the participants, which is critical in an ethnography study. According to Creswell & Poth

(2016), good ethnography research demands a lengthy stay or for the researcher to spend an extended period in the research site. Ethnography was initially considered for this study because observation and cultural theories are the foundation of a good qualitative ethnographic study (Creswell & Poth, 2016).

Phenomenology is a human science that believes human experiences can be explored and expressed consciously by those who have experienced them (Van Manen, 2016; Creswell & Poth, 2016). Consequently, it accommodates the use of descriptive and interpretive analysis of the meaning of experiences and makes the invisible visible (Neubauer *et al.*, 2019). This present study's philosophy is interpretivism and informs the phenomenological methodology. This is supported by different schools of philosophy that influence phenomenology (Neubauer *et al.*, 2019). Therefore, the philosophical stance of the researcher informs the kind of phenomenological approach the researcher will adopt (Neubauer *et al.*, 2019). As a qualitative approach, phenomenology enquires about people's experiences and how to learn from them (Gill, 2014; Neubauer *et al.*, 2019; Sander, 1982). This approach describes the essence of human experiences based on what happened and how it happened (Neubauer *et al.*, 2019). Phenomenology was initially engaged as a purely descriptive research approach to explore phenomena from a scientific perspective (Cope, 2005; Sanders, 1982). Nonetheless, this approach is presently adopted by researchers from different disciplines, such as sociology, psychology, education, and health science (Neubauer *et al.*, 2019). This shows its flexibility and ability to cut across different disciplines.

According to Sanders (1982, pg.354), "*phenomenology is a broad stream with many current*". This means it is a broad term that envelops different research

approaches, for example, interpretive, descriptive, poetic, and scientific. It explores everyday human experiences that are taken for granted (Finlay, 2013). Neubauer *et al.* (2019) acknowledged the existence of different types of phenomenological approaches. However, they concentrated on the transcendental and hermeneutic approaches of phenomenology. They highlighted a common aspect of both approaches, which is to understand the subjective human experiences, which this study aims to achieve.

Transcendental / Hermeneutic

Phenomenology is usually associated with Edmund Husserl (1859-1938), a German philosopher and mathematician (Sanders, 1982). His work was later expanded by one of his students Martin Heidegger, who propagated a hermeneutic perspective to phenomenology. To Husserl, phenomenology is the thorough study of a phenomenon in its actual or pure state to understand human experience (Sanders, 1982). Husserl believes that an authentic understanding can be reached about a phenomenon if the researcher can put aside his or her preconceptions about the phenomenon or object and see it for what it is. He proposed an essential phenomenology attitude called *an epoch*, also known as bracketing, to eliminate biases and make it a normative research practice. Researchers are expected to self-examine themselves and peel-off prior knowledge of a phenomenon so that they can approach the phenomenon with an open mind (Sanders, 1982). According to Finlay (2013), there is no consensus on what should be bracketed. He argued that hermeneutic phenomenologists believe that a researcher's influence on research is unavoidable and must be acknowledged. He stated that the stronger the passion, the more profound the knowledge. A researcher can understand a phenomenon better

when the researcher is passionate about the topic. It creates a strong connection between the researcher and the topic because the purpose is not to isolate or detach oneself from the research study.

Neubauer *et al.* (2019) claimed Husserl refused the pure positivist approach to investigating external reality through objective observation. Instead, he insisted that the focus of objective scientific study should be on the perception of an individual's experience of a phenomenon, from a purely scientific and objective approach to a phenomenon to approaching a phenomenon from a subjective perspective of consciousness, seeking inner evidence. This paradigm shift collaborates with Husserl's view of knowledge as objective and subjective. For Husserl, the subjective and objective aspects of a phenomenon are together and to genuinely understand the actual situation of a phenomenon. The lived experiences and environment of the phenomenon, need to be discovered. The essence of a phenomenon is the real identity, and generalisation can be achieved from identified commonalities in experiencing a phenomenon (Neubauer *et al.*, 2019).

Hermeneutic phenomenology, also referred to as interpretive phenomenology, was promoted by Martins Heidegger. He was a student of Husserl but did not agree with every aspect of his former teacher's transcendental phenomenological approach. He introduced hermeneutic phenomenology into modern philosophy by insisting on the use of interpretation in the study of human beings (Gill, 2014). Heidegger focused on the relationship between people and their lifeworld. He sees human beings as active participants in the world, and their experiences are influenced by the world they live in (Gill, 2014; Neubauer *et al.*, 2019). This means that conscious lived experiences cannot be separated from the person experiencing them as it forms the personal

history and culture of that person (Neubauer *et al.*, 2019). Hermeneutic phenomenology seeks to understand the deep, concealed, or hidden meaning of human experiences as influenced by their environment or the world. This approach studies the experiences of individuals from their perspective in order to understand the meaning of their experiences. Heidegger's approach transcends beyond the description of experience to interpreting experiences. His background in theology may explain why he favours interpretivism (Neubauer *et al.*, 2019).

Phenomenology focuses on the lived experiences of people. It pursues and focus on the meaning of human experiences from their point of view (Smith *et al.*, 2009). Sanders (1982) mentioned that there are three fundamental components in a phenomenological research design, namely:

- Decide the number of who and what is to be investigated
- Data collection
- Phenomenological analysis of data collected

Anything that cannot be easily quantifiable is deemed an appropriate research topic. Only those with the essential characteristics for the research or who have experienced the phenomenon under investigation should be selected because their information is dependable (Sanders, 1982). A major rule for phenomenology researchers is that more subjects do not necessarily mean more information; quantity should not be mistaken for quality (Sanders, 1982). According to Lincoln & Guba (1986), quality and trustworthiness can be achieved in qualitative research through four criteria: credibility, dependability, transferability, and confirmability. Similarly, (Black *et al.*, 2013) mentioned that prolonged engagement, triangulation, and member checking enhance the credibility of research, while (Cope, 2005) stated that credibility

is achieved when the researcher can explicitly show the audit trail and the research method used for data collection.

Phenomenological researchers should carry out an in-depth investigation of a small number of participants (Sanders, 1982). She suggested three to six individuals as sufficient to gather quality information. On data collection (Sanders, 1982) suggested in-depth semi-structured interviews as one of the data collection methods, and she recommended taping the interview for systematic data analysis purposes. Finally, the phenomenological analysis consists of four levels. Level one is a description of the phenomenon as it is in the tape. Level two identifies themes that appear from the description, and number three is developing a relationship between *neotic* and *neomatic*. *Neoma* is the perception or judgement held of an actual object, while *Neosis* is the act of an intentional experience. This reflects the subjective meaning that emerges from the themes identified from the data as they relate to leadership styles, ethnicity, and evidence of the influence of national culture. Lastly, level four is the process where essence is derived from people's experiences through intentional reflection.

3.6 Sample/Participants

This study utilises a sample size of fifteen of the leaders of ethnic minority-led micro-businesses in London, they were selected through purposive and snowball sampling techniques. The participants are mostly people from South Asia, followed by Africa and Caribbean as seen in Table 6. Also, the participants reside and operate their businesses in various borough in London such as Barking and Dagenham, Central London, Lambeth, Merton, Newham, Southwark, and Tower Hamlets.

Table 6. Participants demographic information

Name	Age	Gender	Nationality	Religion	Position	No. of Staff	Business Type
Sam	20-25	Male	India	Pagan	Manager	0	Tea outlet
Michael	20-25	Male	Sierra Leone	Muslim	Owner	1	African Foodstuff
Hamed	25-30	Male	Bangladesh	Muslim	Manager	5	Asian Foodstuff
Musa	20-25	Male	India	Muslim	Owner	0	Phone Accessories
Abdul	20-25	Male	Bangladesh	Agnostic	Manager	0	Grocery shop
Jane	30-35	Female	Jamaica	Christianity	Owner	0	Cosmetics
Malik	30-35	Male	Sri Lanka	Hindu	Manager	9	Restaurant
Peter	25-30	Male	Philippines	Christianity	Manager	3	Food outlet
Aminat	20-25	Female	Nigeria	Muslim	Manager	0	Food outlet
Gloria	30-35	Female	Jamaica	Christianity	Owner	1	Boutique
Halima	30-35	Female	Bangladesh	Atheist	Manager	0	Honey shop
John	55-60	Male	Jamaica	Atheist	Owner	0	Vintage clothes
Saheed	50-55	Male	Morocco	Muslim	Owner	0	Art and craft
Gedeon	40-45	Male	Jamaica	Rastafari	Owner	0	Natural products
Mary	20-25	Female	Cameroon	Christianity	Manager	6	Food shop

Smith *et al.* (2009) implied that researchers using a phenomenological approach should recruit a reasonably homogeneous sample in that they should share similarities in terms of demographic characteristics. The criteria for the sample includes, ethnicity, business size, location, and industry. This study's target population are the owner and managers of ethnic minority micro-businesses, in the retail sector with less than ten employees in London. This target population shares similar characteristics and experiences, so they can assist in creating a better understanding of ethnic minority-led micro-businesses in the retail sector in London with less than ten employees. This aligns well with Smith's idea of homogeneity (Smith *et al.*, 2009).

3.6.1 Purposeful Sample

The sample for this study is purposive and snowball sampling. These techniques are used to investigate and recruit an identified group with specific characteristics who have experienced the phenomenon being researched to give rich and relevant information (Creswell & Poth, 2016). Therefore, only firms meeting this study's required criteria were recruited. The criteria are, only ethnic minority-led micro-businesses with no employee or less than ten employees, in the retail sector, in London were considered and recruited for this study. Purposive sampling is a vital non-probability sampling used to identify a research study's primary participants (Groenewald, 2004).

The sample size used in this present study is fifteen. This is deemed appropriate to establish a degree of credibility by interviewing a larger sample size to gain a better understanding of the research topic involving the experiences of the leaders of ethnic minority-led businesses. The research design was carefully considered with the goal of understanding participants' experiences. This involved

adopting the interview strategy as the primary data collection method and focusing on both the homogeneity and variation of the sample population, which contributed to the determination of the sample size for this study (Sandelowski, 1995). Also, Baker & Edwards (2012) mentioned that having varied perspectives on the subject makes the research rich and informative. Informational redundancy can also help form a sample size in qualitative research (Sandelowski, 1995). Smaller numbers have been suggested as suitable for phenomenological studies as they generate extensive, in-depth, rich data. Sanders proposed between 3 to 5 interviews, (Smith *et al.*, 2009) suggested between the range of 4 to 10 interviews, (Sandelowski, 1995) mentioned 6, while (Creswell & Poth 2016) stated from the range of 5 to 25 is an appropriate number for phenomenological interview.

Baker & Edward (2012) implied that there is no agreed number of qualitative interviews to engage in. However, they agreed that there are various factors that can influence a sample size that needs consideration before settling for a sample size that is assumed to be appropriate, for example, research topic, research question, research approach, time constraint, quality of the work, access to participants and the unknown, which can surface on the field. The research topic is not sensitive and does not involve sensitive groups. So, access issues were approached on the willingness of participants to participate in this study and my ability to convince them to voluntarily participate as there is a large pool to pick from. I was flexible throughout this research process so that this study could adapt and be in a position to address unforeseen challenges.

Also, this study did not apply the concept of saturation as the foundation of this study rest on interpretivism and this is a phenomenological study that focused on the

essence and lived experiences of the participants as interpreted by the participants. Saturation is often considered as a key element of rigor in qualitative research, but the concept of saturation is situated within the neo-positivist, discovery-oriented framing of qualitative research, and so is at odds with the more interpretivist position of phenomenology (Braun & Clarke, 2021). Saturation attempts to align with the concept of generalisability, through the argument that no more new codes or meaningful data exist, making the findings more easily applied to a wider population (Braun & Clarke, 2021). Further, Saunder *et al.* (2018) argued that achieving saturation is not a typical goal in interpretative phenomenological analysis. This argument arises from the emphasis on acquiring rich and detailed data which underscores the phenomenological study and its specific focus on individual lived experiences (Saunder *et al.*, 2018).

Phenomenology seeks to understand the lived experiences of a sample (Braun & Clarke, 2021). Meaning is not self-evident in data, but it is generated through the researcher's interpretation (Braun & Clarke, 2021). Therefore, new meanings are always possible rendering the concept of saturation redundant (Braun & Clarke, 2021). Also, it is more challenging to identify a clear purpose for achieving saturation in narrative research (Saunder *et al.*, 2018). Additionally, Saunder *et al.* (2018) shared their concern on saturation losing its effectiveness if its conceptualisation and application are overly broadened.

3.6.2 Snowball Sampling

Snowball sampling is a popular research technique used in qualitative research. This technique is applied to recruit participants for a research study by asking recruited

participants to recommend or help recruit new participants who meet the specific requirements for research before they can voluntarily participate (Groenewald, 2004).

The snowball technique was adopted in this study. The researcher established connections with individuals from ethnic minority backgrounds as well as owners and managers of ethnic minority-led micro-businesses in London by talking about their struggles in their businesses and in life. These initial contacts facilitated further introductions to additional ethnic minority micro-business owners and managers. For instance, the researcher befriended an individual from an ethnic minority background at a market in London. This person, in turn, guided the researcher to other ethnic minority-led micro-businesses within the market, claiming he is related to the researcher, aiding in the recruitment of participants for the study.

Research is a social construct, meaning human interaction or interpersonal relationships are integral in data collection, including in the snowball sampling technique (Browne, 2005). Through social networks, snowball techniques facilitate issues of accessibility to a unique group (Browne, 2005), which is relevant to this study as ethnic minority-led micro-businesses are a unique, small, and close-knit group who support each other (Basu, 2004; Ishaq *et al.*, 2010).

3.6.3 Recruitment

The participants for this study were recruited based on their level of understanding of the English language, ethnicity, the number of employees, the business sector, and location. Participants with a basic understanding and can communicate with the English language, were recruited for this study. At the same time, leaders of ethnic minority-led micro-businesses with zero to nine employees in the retail sector in London were approached initially to request their voluntary

participation in this research verbally and establish a relationship for the purpose of this research. Afterwards, they were presented with a letter formally asking them to participate in this study. A consent form was made available to them for completion, that explained the rationale behind this research, their rights, and the potential risks involved. The participants were allowed to decide the time and place for the interview, and follow-up communication ensued as a reminder of their commitment to the study.

3.7 Mode of data collection

This section provides a clear insight and explains the data collection process used in this study. Every research approach has certain requirements for data collection (Larkin *et al.*, 2021). The data collection design is meant to collect rich data where participants can freely express their ideas and concerns (Smith *et al.*, 2009). The data collection design for this qualitative phenomenological study involved the invitation of owners and managers of ethnic minority-led micro-businesses in London to voluntarily partake in this study to provide and share their first-hand experiences after their rights had been explained to them. The next step was recruitment. As mentioned, and explained earlier in this chapter, leaders of ethnic minority-led micro-businesses in London were recruited for this study. Further, the mode of data collection suitable for a qualitative phenomenological study that will capture the participants' lived experiences and is adopted in this study is an in-depth interview, a semi-structured, face-to-face interview (Smith *et al.*, 2009). Finally, the data analysis and interpretation.

3.7.1 Data Gathered

The data for this study was gathered between the period of June 2021 to September 2021. The interview questions were centred on the leadership behaviour

and cultural influence of ethnic minority micro-business leaders in London, and to explore how their leadership behaviour and culture influence their businesses. In total 16 interviews on ethnic minority micro-business leaders in the retail business in London were conducted, but one was rejected because the participants did not want to be audio recorded. So, notes were taken, but at the analysis stage, the data was regarded as insufficient for this study because it was not rich and detailed enough, and its credibility could be challenged, which left this study with 15 useable interviews. Out of the 15 useable interviews from ethnic minority leaders of micro-businesses who voluntarily participated in this study, seven are owners of their businesses, while eight are managers. All managers reside and conduct their businesses in different boroughs in London, such as Barking and Dagenham, Central London, Lambeth, Merton, Newham, Southwark, and Tower Hamlets. They are all in the retail business, providing or selling one or more of the following: food and foodstuffs, art and craft, cultural and religious artefacts, natural products and cosmetics, educational and wellbeing services, vintage clothes, and accessories and operate a boutique.

A phenomenological analysis is adopted in this study, which is guided by the six steps prescribed by (Smith *et al.*, 2009). Below are Smith *et al.* (2009) six steps.

- Reading and re-reading
- Initial noting
- Develop emergent themes
- Searching for connections across emergent themes
- Moving to the next case
- Looking for patterns across cases

The first step requires reading and rereading to familiarise with the body of data gathered before carrying on with the analysis process. Also, notes of first impressions were made and any relevant information that came across. The next step was to generate initial codes from the data collected. This stage involves systematically organising the large body of data, by compressing them into smaller meaningful parts guided by the research question. Any meaningful information identified as it relates to this study's research question was highlighted later under a theme. Subsequently, the third stage entails searching for themes. This stage is where patterns and relevant information are captured to make sense of the initial codes generated from the data gathered. As an inductive approach, the data determined the themes (Creswell & Poth, 2016; Scotland, 2012; Smith *et al.*, 2009). This stage lays the foundation of a systematic arrangement that enables the determination of which code goes under what theme.

Next is the fourth stage, the review of themes and searching for connections. The identified themes from the earlier stage were reviewed, modified, and grouped based on relevance. The association of the coded data to each theme or how sub-themes relate to the central theme and how the themes connect to the entire data set is identified. At this stage, the phenomenological analysis map starts emerging or becomes clearer. Braun & Clarke (2006) explained that this stage has two levels. The first level involves reading all coded data under each theme to ascertain if they make sense. The second level also requires rereading to capture missed themes and make modifications by re-coding or creating new themes or sub-themes. Maguire & Delahunt (2017) stated that qualitative data analysis software could be very efficient in this stage but optional.

After careful review of the data, which is a continuous process in phenomenological analysis (Smith *et al.*, 2009), the themes are defined to understand what each meant or represent and how they relate to this present study. This marks the final stage of refinement, aiming for coherent and consistent data representation, including the connection between themes and sub-themes, as well as aligning with the research question. Lastly, the final stage, which is the write-up. This is the stage where the experiences of the participants are interpreted and explained in a simple and comprehensible way to assure readers of the merit of the analysis in the present study

3.7.2 Interview

A reliable source of data collection methods in phenomenology is the semi-structured interview (Creswell & Poth, 2016; Moustakas, 1994; Smith *et al.*, 2009). It is effective in collecting qualitative data like reflective recollection (Creswell & Poth, 2016; Scotland, 2012; Van Manen, 2016). The reflective interview data requires an interpretive analysis for the researcher to vividly describe the participants' lived experiences (Van Manen, 2016). The interview research strategy was adopted for this study to seek an understanding of how leadership style affects ethnic minority firms. New and relevant information can be revealed through semi-structured interviews based on the open nature of the questions (Moustakas, 1994). It is a conversation designed to seek and expose deep meaning from participants based on the topic of interest (Doody & Noonan, 2013; Smith *et al.*, 2009).

The semi-structured interview is appropriate for phenomenology study as it focuses on the deep meaning of human experience (Moustakas, 1994; Van Manen, 2016). Data was collected using a semi-structured interview through a voice or video recording with permission from participants. Semi-structured interviews are preferable

and mostly used in qualitative research. They achieve answers and understanding in an exploratory way with open-ended questions (Doody & Noonan, 2013). This process is flexible, creates dialogue and gives room for spontaneity to explore new information (Doody & Noonan, 2013). Phenomenological researchers mainly utilise open-ended questions in qualitative interviews to inquire from participants what they experienced, how they experienced the phenomenon and what influenced their experiences (Creswell & Poth, 2016).

The interview questions were written beforehand to help guide the conversation and were confirmed through a pilot test. A pilot test interview was conducted in this study with a family member that lasted for 20 minutes to test the interview questions, which exposed the unsuitability of a couple of questions in this study. For example, one of the questions was, would you describe your leadership style as transformational or transactional? The questions did not obtain appropriate responses. This family member is an ethnic minority person, and a manager of a small business in London. The result of the pilot test helped and was instrumental in constructing and testing the validity of the research questions for this qualitative phenomenological study. A pilot test is a tool for ensuring validity in research and is a mini version (Dikko, 2016). It can be used to pre-test a particular research instrument or as a trial run before engaging in full-scale research (Dikko, 2016). According to Dikko (2016), a pilot test is essential and applicable to both qualitative and quantitative research because it assists in identifying likely flaws in a research instrument and can reveal questions that could be added to a research interview. Further, it can help to organise and validate the use of semi-structured one-on-one interviews.

The questions are structured to target specific topics that are important to this research, for example, ethnic minorities, leadership approach, and national culture to capture the experiences of the leaders of ethnic minority-led micro-business and how it relates to their leadership style. According to Creswell & Poth (2016), the literature informs the research interview questions. They further mentioned that there is a connection between research purposes, research questions and methods to achieve a cohesive research study. The construction or formulation of the research questions for this study was centred on the issues related to the research topic, methodology, population, location, phenomenon being studied, research aim, objectives, and question. The interview questions are arranged to start in a friendly way to relax participants before delving into the core questions that address specific issues related to the experiences of ethnic minority-led micro-businesses in London, as seen in appendix 3. Also, probing questions were designed as follow-up questions for participants to elaborate and explain responses in depth. The interview process, especially the semi-structured interview is not rigid but adaptable, allowing participants to express themselves freely and allowing the researcher to follow up on new information provided by the interviewee (Creswell & Poth, 2016; Moustakas, 1994).

3.8 Data Analysis

3.8.1 Phenomenological Analysis of data

A phenomenological analysis was applied in this study to gain an understanding of the experience of the influence of leadership styles of the leaders of ethnic minority-led businesses. The phenomenological analysis process helped explicate data collected where patterns and themes were identified, arranged, and interpreted systematically to achieve meaning or understand participants' experiences (Smith *et*

al., 2009). There is no generally accepted method of applying phenomenological analysis (Smith *et al.*, 2009). They suggested that there are several ways to approach a phenomenological analysis and that researchers should be creative in how they approach the phenomenological analysis and how they apply its strategies. The purpose of the phenomenological analysis strategy is to encourage deep and flexible thinking and active participation with the data. Phenomenological analysis aims to understand or capture the lived experiences of participants and the meaning attached to the experiences by the participants (Smith *et al.*, 2009).

However, thematic analysis is different from other approaches using qualitative data that intend to describe or attempt to look for or pursue patterns, such as phenomenological studies, which prioritise experiences as they seek to understand people's lived experiences (Braun & Clarke, 2006). Also, it is the reason thematic analysis is not adopted in this study. Similarly, the extant literature on phenomenological study cannot agree on a single approach to data analysis (Smith *et al.*, 2009). Just like any other qualitative study, the purpose of a phenomenological study is its focus on analysis and its connection with the participant's experiences (Smith *et al.*, 2009).

Phenomenological analysis can be identified or described by a group of common processes and principles for example, going from descriptive to interpretive and understanding participants perspective to personal sense-making and can be adopted flexibly based on the purpose of the task (Smith *et al.*, 2009). The phenomenological analysis is a popular and flexible qualitative analytical approach that serves as a technique or systematic procedure employed to identify and interpret repeated patterns and themes found in qualitative data and extract the meaning within

the data (Smith *et al.*, 2009). The reason for the phenomenological analysis is to identify and interpret relevant and essential data guided by the research question and not to summarise (Smith *et al.*, 2009). This is why it was described as an inductive circle, a process that is guided by or data-driven (Smith *et al.*, 2009). The inductive approach was defined as themes derived from data collected in a study as guided by the research question for that study (Braun & Clarke, 2006). Smith *et al.* (2009) acknowledged the complexity in conducting a phenomenological analysis, so they prescribed or provided a guide, a six-step approach to a phenomenological analysis that will assist a first time or novice researchers in data *analysis* in a phenomenological study. They stated that the steps are a guide, and researchers do not have to follow the steps as highlighted. They can be innovative about it. Therefore, Smith *et al.* (2009) six steps phenomenological analysis strategy is used to guide the analysis approach adopted in this study as seen in Figure 2.

The data analysis process involves several steps or stages, as illustrated in Figure 2 above. The first stage involved familiarisation with the data by reading it several times. At this stage the researcher was trying to get acquainted with the data by reading and rereading it. The second stage comprised writing down first impressions as codes, just any thoughts that came to mind during the familiarisation process of reading and rereading. The second stage involved any relevant information that came across to the researcher. This stage assists in the generation of initial codes from the data collected. First impressions and thoughts such as effect of COVID-19, family support, team player, conducive working environment, local community, respect for elders, national culture, religious activities, being the boss, government assistance, and future thinking were noted. The next stage is contextual meaning, which is the third stage. This is a sense-making stage where the researcher looks at the data to

identify elements relevant to the research question which are used to formulate new themes based on participants' expressions and the surface meaning of their words. For example, the show of care, friendship, family, respect for people, treating people right, religiosity and being incharge or the boss.

The fourth stage is reflective interpretation. In this stage, the data are reviewed in a deep reflective thought by the researcher, and an Interpretation of the experiences of the participants, what they meant and suggested based on the context it was said and expressed as it relates to the research questions are used to formulate themes. For example, one of the participants was asked about taking government support and the response was "I don't like it, to be honest, I don't because I am Muslim that's why I don't like get interest or something like that". This behaviour suggests religious influence and was grouped under the sub-theme, religious influence. It is a reflective process of the participant's words and how they said them and looking for the connection of their experiences with the earlier stage and the research questions. This is a continuous process in phenomenological analysis (Smith *et al.*, 2009), where codes and themes are constantly reviewed and modified as new information is constructed or a better understanding is achieved. For example, religion was not identified as a theme initially. However, upon review of the text and codes, its omission became evident due to the frequency of religious influence and its significance to the participant's experiences. As an inductive approach, the data determined the themes (Creswell & Poth, 2016; Scotland, 2012; Smith *et al.*, 2009).

In the fifth stage, common themes are identified and recorded down on a sheet of paper. They were organised and modified into sub-themes based on relevance by the researcher. For instance, participant behaviours such as being incharge,

micromanaging, displaying assertiveness, and the show of power indicate leadership qualities. These behaviours contributed to the construction of the theme authority, one of the four main themes in this study. While the themes that are viewed as irrelevant, such as gender and government assistance for example, are disregarded. This process centres on the research question and literature review, ultimately leading to the final stage of developing the main themes. The main themes were constructed from the most frequently appeared themes that are related to the research question, aims, objective and literature review. Four main themes were constructed: Morality, Benevolence, Authority, and Religion. These four principal themes were constructed from the codes and sub-themes with behaviours that suggest genuine care, friendliness, assertiveness, power, show of respect and religiosity. These themes and their relevance are further discussed in Chapter 3 and 4.

3.9 Trustworthiness

To ensure rigour in qualitative research, the researcher must attend to the reliability and validity issues in research (May & Pope, 1995). They stated that reliability in qualitative research could be enhanced by having an assessment of transcripts by an independent skilled qualitative researcher. Qualitative validity can be achieved by soliciting feedback from participants with findings generated from the research to confirm if the findings represent a good account of their experiences.

According to Fossey *et al.* (2002), to establish quality and sound qualitative research, a thorough approach is required towards the design, data collection method, data analysis, interpretation, and reporting of findings. In a similar view, May & Pope (1995) mentioned that the issue of reliability and validity of research should be addressed by the researcher, as it is paramount for the credibility of a research. They

stated that to improve the quality of a qualitative research study requires having an independent but skilled qualitative researcher review the study. Also, Lincoln & Guba (1986) recommended four criteria to tackle questions of trustworthiness in research: credibility, transferability, confirmability, and dependability. They suggested that the four criteria should address issues ignored by scientific researchers regarding rigour in research, for example, multiple realities and social pluralism. Multiple realities are socially constructed and cannot be investigated in variables or parts, and it need to be approached holistically as parts influence the whole (Lincoln & Guba, 1986).

This study addressed the issue of trustworthiness following the criteria suggested by (Lincoln & Guba, 1986). Credibility, the recorded, transcribed, and analysed data for this study were assessed on an ongoing basis by my supervisors, who are skilled qualitative researchers and have discussions with me about my interpretation of the data. Also, prolonged engagement was adopted to pursue and capture relevant or salient information and aspects of participants' lived experiences by using interview time to know participants better and through the analysis of data to identify patterns and themes. Triangulation was attained in this study in the form of data collected and some of the criteria for rigour, which are interview data, peer debriefing and member checks. Triangulation is the use of different methods of investigation in research to draw conclusions and triangulation ensures dependability (Lincoln & Guba, 1986).

- Credibility

The credibility of this study was through peer debriefing. The whole research process was supervised by qualified researchers in qualitative and phenomenological studies. They ensure that the right research topic,

methodology, data analysis method, and sampling were chosen. They constantly made corrections and suggestions to enhance the credibility of this study. Elo *et al.* (2014) suggested that credibility can be ascertained in research through the adoption of the most suitable data collection method. In this study, the semi-structured interview was chosen as it is a common practice and recognised approach in qualitative research used to collect rich data and to have a deeper understanding of a research topic or phenomenon (Van Manen, 2016).

- Dependability / Transferability

Refers to the stability and consistency of data when applied in similar situations (Elo *et al.*, 2014; Lincoln & Guba, 1986). Dependability and transferability can be achieved in research when another researcher can confirm the research trail of each stage of a research process. Also, it requires clarity in research design and process for transferability to be attained in research (Elo *et al.*, 2014). This study is a qualitative phenomenological study, and fifteen leaders of ethnic minority-led micro-businesses in London were recruited for this study. A semi-structured interview was employed to gather a rich data set, and phenomenological data analysis was applied to gain insight into the lived experiences of the participants from the participants. This is how this study ensured dependability and transferability because this process can be adopted by any researcher to explore human lived experiences.

- Confirmability

Confirmability is also known as external reliability (Lincoln & Guba, 1986). It shows how conclusions and interpretations of findings are from the

participants and not the opinion of the researcher (Elo *et al.*, 2014). The recognition, acknowledgement, and check of personal biases assisted in achieving confirmability in this study, as the researcher made sure through the help of experts in qualitative and phenomenological studies that the interpretation of the findings and constructed conclusions reflect the original views of the participants, leaders of ethnic minority-led micro-businesses in London, and not that of the researcher. Also, the researcher provided a clear picture of the data analysis process that described how the original data from the participants were interpreted and constructed following a phenomenological data analysis approach, as demonstrated earlier in this chapter.

3.10 Ethical Consideration

This study adhered to the guidelines provided by the University of the West of Scotland Ethics Committee to ensure the appropriate research approach, design, and data collection methods are adopted, participants' privacy and confidentiality are protected, and potential harm is limited. All data gathered about participants during this study were kept strictly confidential and processed in accordance with the General Data Protection Regulation 2016 (GDPR) and the Data Protection Act 2018. Participants' data are anonymous and represented with pseudonyms rather than real names. Participant data is securely stored using a password-protected computer system, safeguarded on a USB drive in a secure location, and archived on cloud storage for a minimum of three years before they are destroyed.

The global pandemic COVID-19 made it more critical to observe one of the essential principles of ethical research which is to limit or cause no harm to participants. Although, the pandemic disrupted access to the research sample, a

snowball sampling strategy was used to minimise the impact, as avoiding, or limiting potential harm to participants in any form during this research is crucial to the success of this research. This research study has some ethical considerations critical to it, for example, beneficence and non-maleficence, informed consent, and justice.

Beneficence and Non-Maleficence

It is the responsibility of the researcher to protect the welfare of participants and minimise risk whether emotional or physical that can lead to stress, discomfort, or potential harm to the participants in the cause of conducting research (Cugini, 2015). This study followed the principles of beneficence and non-maleficence to limit and cause no harm to participants and prioritise their welfare. The participants were informed they are free to ask questions and withdraw their consent at any time in this study without pressure. Also, regarding potential harm, unfortunately, this study was conducted during the global pandemic (COVID-19). Therefore, both institutional and governmental precautionary measures were required and observed to limit the risk to the participants and to the researcher such as the use of face mask, hand gloves, hand sanitiser, COVID testing and social distancing.

Autonomy / Informed consent

Autonomy and informed consent involve respecting and recognising the dignity and rights of individuals, people, or participants to freely express themselves, decide their actions, and expect their choices to be respected (Cugini, 2015). The participants in this study were treated ethically and fairly, as verbal consent was agreed upon face-to-face with them before the interview. Subsequently, participants were given an official consent form, asking them for voluntary participation in the research. The consent form contained detailed information about the study and the risks and benefits

involved in simple English for easy understanding. The choice of participants who declined the offer to participate in this study was respected.

Justice

Justice entails the equal distribution of both benefits and burdens of research on each individual participant of research (Cugini, 2015). In this study, the participants were treated equally and fairly for the sake of transparency of the purpose of the study. Each participant had the same consent form, was asked the same interview questions, and chose the time and place for the research interview. The participants were informed of the potential risks and benefits of this research through the participant information sheet provided to them after they volunteered to participate in this study. The participation of the participants in this study was voluntary and not under duress.

3.11 Summary

This chapter shows a clear road map of the research process applied in this study. The research process was steered and directed by the research topic which seeks to understand the lived experiences that influence the leaders of ethnic minority-led micro-businesses. A qualitative phenomenological study was adopted to understand the subjective meaning of participants' experiences from an interpretivist perspective. The intention is to interpret the participants' experiences from their perspective and capture the essence of their experiences. This means that a face-to-face semi-structured interview was adopted to enable the participants to freely express themselves. However, the COVID-19 pandemic was a big concern for this study because it led to the change of the research design for this study from ethnography to phenomenology. The pandemic made movement and access to people, ethnic minority small business owners, and managers in London difficult due

to nationwide government restrictions in the UK. Notwithstanding, measures were taken to address these challenges as highlighted earlier in this chapter. This study considered the guidelines provided by the University Ethics Committee - to respect and protect participants and to produce an ethical and credible study.

4. Chapter Four: Findings

4.1 Introduction

This purposeful qualitative phenomenological study aims to explore, understand, describe, and interpret the lived experiences of the leadership approach of ethnic minority-led micro-businesses in London. In this chapter, the findings from the data gathered from the semi-structured interviews conducted with 15 leaders of ethnic minority-led micro-businesses within London will be presented and analysed. The phenomenological analysis of the data in this study resulted in the emergence of four main themes shown in Table 7 (morality - leading by example, benevolence – a show of genuine care, authority - as a display of power and control, and religion as a guiding light) that addressed the research question. The meaning of morality, benevolence, and authority, three of the four main themes, were used as ascribed by (Farh & Cheng, 2000) in Table 5, Chapter 2.

Table 7. The four main themes

Main Themes
1. Religion as a guiding light Sub-theme <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Strong faith in God ● Religious practice
2. Morality: Experiences of moral influence
3. Benevolence: Show of genuine care and kindness
4. Authority: Experiences with power and authority

The analysis and interpretation of the data in this study as seen in Figure two are based on the adaptation of the six-step phenomenological data analysis process outlined by (Smith *et al*, 2009). The first step is to become familiar with the data. The second step is to generate initial codes, followed by the search for themes, after reviewing themes, then define themes and lastly, write up. Also, pseudonyms are adopted in this study to maintain the anonymity of the participants. Also, extracts from the interview data that represent the participants' lived experiences in this study were used to support the claims, analysis, and interpretation of the findings of this study. This chapter includes a brief description of each participant in this study. Then, acquaint the readers with the participants, followed by the presentation, analysis, interpretation, and discussion of the themes, and then a summary.

4.1.1 Participants

The participants' experiences are critical to a phenomenological study (Gill, 2014). So, the focus of this study is on the lived experiences of the participants who are leaders of ethnic minority-led micro-businesses in London and share their experiences in a descriptive and interpretive manner, so the participants' voices can be heard.

4.2 Religion as a Guiding Light

Religion is one of the main themes developed from this study's data, and it means spiritual affiliations and practices. It influences how participants conduct their lives and businesses, and it is essential to human civilisation because it has become a way of life by shaping human behaviour (Beyers, 2017; Gaitho, 2019; Phipps, 2012). Two additional sub-themes emerged from the main theme: experiences of strong faith in God and religious practices. The two sub-themes further explain how religious

beliefs and practices influence the behaviour of the leaders of ethnic minority-led micro-businesses in London.

4.2.1 Experience of strong faith in God

This sub-theme explains the meaning and role of religion and how it shapes the participants' experiences. This study explored the views or perceptions of participants to capture their belief in a supreme being as it relates to the influence it has on their business decision making and interactions with their environment.

Some participants revealed during the interview process how their religious belief in a supreme being shaped their behaviour and lives in terms of trust, serenity, divine intervention, and prosperity. It shows how their survival and success partly depend on their religion because they expect divine intervention from a supernatural being to protect and correct any wrong in their lives. When the participants were asked to share their experiences, their social construction of the meaning and their understanding of religion and faith and how it shapes their lives and businesses, their responses revealed and confirmed their affiliation to a religious organisation and their acceptance and devotion to a supreme being (God) and the significant influence of religion in their lives.

Malik "Yeah, I do have a faith, I do accept that statement, I believe in God. As a person it shapes my life it gives me certain kind of.. religious wise.. because I do go to temple, we do prayers on a regular basis so from the temple, they advise, our religion always say love and calm and peace".

Aminat “Yeah, 100% we’re Muslim, so my whole family is Muslim, even the ones back home. Having religion on our side, we need the business to flourish, we need God on our side, definitely. Our beliefs definitely influence, like I said, in the morning, me and my dad always pray”.

Gloria “I am a Christian. I have faith, I have a very strong faith. I wouldn’t have done as much as I have done if it wasn’t for my faith in God and putting my faith into action.... I believe God is with me. I believe he is honouring me through my faithfulness. You know, I am a praying woman, i consult with God with everything. God is first in my life, you know. I’m faithful, i trust God, you know, and i try to honour God with everything i do. I believe he just honours me right back and just shows favour in my life”.

These three participants are from different countries and follow different religions. Aminat is Nigerian and a Muslim, Malik is Sri Lankan and a Hindu, and Gloria is a Christian from Jamaica. One thing they all have in common is faith and belief in a supreme being. They all pray and admit the existence of God. Also, it is evident that they are active religious people, and religion is essential to them. There is a strong sense of commitment by the participants to their different religious orientations. The three participants who shared their experiences showed an affiliation and commitment to certain religious bodies. They have an unwavering belief in a supreme being (God) that is connected to their religious organisations and the practise of its teachings. Religion gives meaning to the life of the participants. It is not just about church going; it is a source of moral rectitude and physical and spiritual strength. It has a significant meaning to them as they rely upon it to tackle life challenges through prayers to

achieve divine security, prosperity, serenity, and a sense of community.

The experiences of Malik, Aminat and Gloria highlight religious influence in the form of adaptation of behaviour and the utilisation of religion as a survival tool to face life challenges. Several participants rely upon and trust that a supreme being will intervene and make their life challenges tolerable.

4.2.2 Religious Practise

The participants in this study see religion as a way of life. They practise it daily and agree it influences their behaviour. They apply their religious principles and values in their lives because of their strong faith and commitment to their religion, which in turn influence their behaviour and their views of the world. The following narratives of participants, when asked about their experiences of the influence of religion in their leadership and business, demonstrate the integration of religious values with business activities which reflect a strong behavioural influence by religion.

Malik “As I mention, yeah, for the business, like we don’t do the pork and we don’t do the beef, so that’s religious.... We don’t cook beef and then pork because normally like, Hindus otherwise, they won’t do the beef, and the Muslim, we thought they don’t do the pork, so we’re just covering both base customers, no beef and no pork. The Islam people, they don’t eat pork, so we say it’s a Halal restaurant... as Hinduism, they don’t eat beef, so we don’t cook beef as well. So, that is for the business. It is strictly no meat, that is, no beef and pork”.

Aminat “For one, we only sell halal food here because we are Muslim. We also do not

eat food that's not halal because that is in our religion, and we also do not sell any alcohol because Muslims actually should not be able to hold alcohol bottles, so it does not really make sense for us to sell alcohol".

The narratives of Malik and Aminat show their perception and reliance on religion and elucidate the strong influence it has on them in the way they uphold and apply the core principles of their religion in their business. Religion shapes their thinking and behaviour. They see their religious practice as an obligation they are willing to carry out voluntarily. The way the participants rely upon and apply God in their business demonstrates absolute trust, strong faith and commitment. Both participants shared similar experiences. They showed significant commitment to their various religions based on how they interpret them in their business. These ascetic religious behaviours can be a personal decision sometimes. It unconsciously influences an individual to conform to the norms and values of a dominant religion in society.

As seen in the experiences of the participants, religious principles may restrict or hinder the growth of businesses, for example, in the experiences of Malik and Aminat, where both are prohibited from selling pork, alcohol and beef. It will be counterproductive for a business owner to establish a business in an environment where pork, beef and alcohol are included in their main dish but excluded from the business owner's menu on religious grounds. These religious norms and principles influence a business owner's business options, collaborations, and practices. Nevertheless, the participants in this study do not seem bothered by the limitations of integrating their religious values into their business as they do business to cater for

the needs of people in their communities with similar faith and shared beliefs.

When asked about taking up loans, there is a strong rebuff towards the idea by some participants. They were clear about their conviction about taking loans based on religious and personal beliefs, but the majority involved the latter. Personal beliefs and entrepreneurial thinking can be influenced by religion (Gaitho, 2019; Parboteeah *et al.*, 2015), which happens to be an essential element in the formation of societal culture (Mohdali & Pope, 2010).

Ali will not accept or apply for a loan whether the survival of his business depends on it because it is against his religious belief. According to (Rafiq, 1992), Islam does not encourage members to take out loans because of the interest on loans, and this point is reiterated by (Parboteeah *et al.*, 2015), that Islam prohibits the payment of interest. When Ali was asked if he had taken any loans he said,

“I don’t like it, to be honest, I don’t like, we are Muslim, that’s why I don’t like get interest or something like that”.

From the use of the words “I don’t like” by Ali, it seems there is a feeling of dislike towards the concept of a loan. It feels like it has a negative implication for him and, most importantly, is frowned upon by his religion which he is a devoted and proud member. In that response, he repeated the words “I don’t like” three times, which emphasised his discomfort about the idea of a loan. A feeling he was able to express explicitly and partly cultivated by his religious teachings. He does not like the idea of a loan because his religion says so.

Similarly, Gedeon does not condone the idea of asking for a loan. He said,

“I would not be going to anybody to ask for any money, for me that is a sin to ask for money or ask for a loan. It’s a sin for me. If you have to do that, then you shouldn’t be doing what you’re doing”.

He feels that taking a loan is a sin. It is against his philosophy of life, which is informed by his Rastafari beliefs, which forbid alcohol drinking. He does not understand why anyone should borrow money or spend beyond their financial capability for any reason. Gedeon expects everyone to be disciplined, manage their lives and financial resources efficiently, and not put themselves in debt. Gedeon is a Rastafarian, and he would not call his spiritual path a religion, but he calls it a concept. His spiritual path substantially influences how he lives his life because he is selfless and does not drink alcohol. He believes in helping people in his community and only sells natural products based on his spiritual beliefs. Although not all participants in this study are actively religious, some proclaim their lack of interest in religion and religious practices, but interestingly, they believe in God. These participants revealed they are from a religious background but chose a different path for personal reasons. Also, they admitted to still carrying remnants of their old religion because the connection is still there. The norms and values of their previous religion are deeply ingrained in them. In some cases, the participants are constantly reminded of their prior beliefs in the community in which they reside. It shows how much of an influence religion can have even on people who are not actively practising any religion.

Peter *“Me personally, I grew up as a Catholic. But when I left the Philippines, I kind of just dissipated.... I would love to go back, but basically, I can't commit ...as I was back in the days. I do have a belief system, Yeah. But, I think partially it lies on Catholicism, touching that”.*

Abdul *“Um, I grew up obviously like, I was brought up obviously a Muslim, like more agnostic than, so that means Obviously, I'm not religious, but obviously I do believe that there is a God but I don't follow a religion..... I have a very very very strict Muslim parents so obviously I'm not Muslim myself but I am agnostic. So it stuck with me like obviously I'm not religious like I'm not following, I'm not Muslim, but I do believe like obviously that there is a God and everything there is a creator basically”.*

From the statements above, there is a feeling of uncertainty, indecision, and lack of commitment from Peter regarding religion. He comes across as indecisive on the topic of religion, as his statement is inconsistent. There is evidence of religious affiliation, as his upbringing is based on Catholicism which also forms part of his present belief system and indicates an acknowledgement of the existence of God. Moreover, he does not want to commit to the Catholic faith but would love to return to practising Catholicism. His behaviour changed when he left the Philippines for the UK, leaving behind a strong religious environment for a more relaxed one in the UK. He is struggling and trying to rediscover his faith, but there is no motivation to pursue that course, partly due to his new not-so-religious environment. If a non-religious person

resides in a religious environment, that person's behaviour will be influenced one way or another (Parboteeah *et al.*, 2015). The reverse effect is what the participant is experiencing here in the UK. Perhaps he has not come to terms with the fact that he is no longer as religious as he used to be but still holds some religious values from his Catholic faith.

Also, during the interview, Abdul repeatedly mentioned that he is not religious and does not follow any religion but belief in God. He stressed that his parents are strict Muslims by using the word "very" three times but admitting the teachings and his knowledge of Islam stuck with him. He believes in God's existence but has no religious affiliation. There is a sign that Abdul struggled with his feelings as he tried to separate himself from his parent's religion, though he still lives with his parents in that religious environment. He unconsciously confirmed the influence of religion in his life because his knowledge of Islam would stay with him forever. His knowledge will make him respect and tolerate the Islamic teachings, and it will modify his behaviour and interactions with Muslims because he knows what to do and what not to do around them. Abdul still lives with his parents, who are strict Muslims, and he resides in a very religious environment where religion has a dominant cultural presence (Henley, 2017).

4.3 Morality: Experiences of moral influence

Participants' experiences showed that Some of the participants in this study shared experiences that illustrate the influence of national culture in their lives. They hold and apply these cultural and moral values in their daily interactions with people and their environment, consciously or unconsciously. What they deem as appropriate behaviour is partly based on their cultural beliefs. Even when the participants disagree with aspects of their culture, they still exhibit and uphold specific cultural values and

norms. Morality in this study means any unselfish or exemplary act.

As a Sri Lankan, Malik tried to explain the cultural expectation of people from Sri Lanka, where respect for elders is paramount and a cultural obligation. As a restaurant manager, he has to manage everyone in the business, both young and old. He works with some staff members older than him, who are chefs from Sri Lanka, and he struggles to give them orders. On other occasions, he finds it hard to tell them what to do.

Malik is having this experience because, culturally, in Sri Lanka, young people are supposed to respect and obey adults or any person older than them, not the other way around. So, he had to balance his business responsibilities and cultural beliefs to achieve his goal, as he struggled to get the older staff members to listen to him or do as instructed. Also, in Sri Lanka, the first name-calling of adults by younger people is frowned upon, so Malik is not allowed to call the older Sri Lanka staff members by their first name. He can only address them as Sir or Uncle, even though he is the manager of the restaurant. As he said,

“They are not going to be friendly because they are elder. As I mentioned, the head chefs, so they have their own view of their management...they don’t want another person to come and be involved in there. It’s kind of cultural, as I’m going to mention the culture because they think they are the head chefs there, they know much more than me, it’s maybe this kind of point older than me as well. And also apart from that culture base how we like calling our elders, we never call from the name, we say uncle or just sir or like that’s the way we calling the elder people”.

Similarly, respect for parents and elders is a crucial part of Indian culture, as demonstrated by Sam. He regularly consults with his parents for advice about most decisions before taking them. He listens to his parents and does as they wish, as his culture expects, which is also a sign of respect. He said that in India and some Asian countries, parents are very involved in the life of their children because they care and want to know what their children are up to so they can guide them through life.

Sam manages a tea shop in London, selling Chai tea. He is passionate about Chai and very connected to his Indian culture. He mentioned that drinking tea (Chai) is a cultural behaviour in India. He plans to introduce local Indian cuisine to the shop's menu to enhance the customer experience as he shares his culture. In his response to the question of how dominant his national culture is in his life, he said,

Sam "In India and some Asian countries, the parents have influence on the life, so they want us to make sure that we take a right step, we don't take a wrong step in the life...Yeah, even now, I take advice from my parents.... So if I have to take a step I just make sure that they know about it".

Sam's parents and his Indian culture are influential in his life. He relies on his parents for their expert opinion or wisdom to guide his decisions in life. He is obedient and respectful to his parents, an essential Indian cultural value that he claimed is a standard behaviour among Indians and Asian people. He feels it is his responsibility to inform his parents about happenings in his life and seek their approval to make certain decisions in his life. Also, he is selfless and treats his colleagues with respect.

He asserted, *"You know it's not about myself. I don't want to show off to my bosses that I am doing best. I want everyone to do well"*. He does not use his power as the manager or his knowledge of Chai as a person from India for personal glory. Sam is very helpful to his colleagues and shares tips to help them be more effective at work. He does not let his interest overpower the business interest, and he leads by example.

According to Sam, *"I am a science student yeah, so you know, I am more into the science stuff"*. He was talking about how science helped shape his reasoning. He claimed not to be religious, so his behaviour is not based on religious beliefs except his culture. His conduct, for example, being respectful, polite, and selfless, indicates cultural influence, which is evident in his relationship with his parents. Even the Chai tea is not just tea to him. He said, *"I think it is like a culture thing I can connect to myself"*. This statement suggests that the Chai tea reminds him of India and reignites that unique feeling of being back home in India, drinking tea and sharing it with friends and family. He is genuinely proud of his culture because he wants to share it with the world as he implies, *"I want people in the Western countries to taste it"*. He is excited about people experiencing his culture even more when he meets people from India who relate to the Chai experience.

Halima's experience involves caring for her ill and ageing parents, a responsibility she took as a moral and cultural obligation. Although she claims that her culture has minimal influence on her life and that she is agnostic, she still upholds high moral standards in every aspect of her life. Based on the findings in this study, Halima's moral behaviour may not be shaped by any religion because she said she is not affiliated with any religious organisation. However, her behaviour is significantly influenced by her cultural beliefs. When asked about her culture, she said,

Halima *“It has not been, but technically it is ruling my life because one of the big things about Asian culture, not just Asian culture, everywhere that is not really the West is looking after your parents. So I was abroad during my actual career, then I came back because my parents were unwell and they needed to be looked after, and that is a big part of our culture where you look after your own parents. National culture is looking after your family, that’s like the biggest thing”*.

Making sacrifices for her parents is an unquestioned cultural obligation, a moral responsibility Halima took upon herself to fulfil. It is a reciprocal behaviour expected in a collective culture, family unit or community where parents cater for their children and expect their children to look after them in their old age. Most Asian cultures encourage this behaviour. Halima said she is 30 years of age and considered a spinster in her culture because traditionally, women are expected to marry early in Bangladesh’s cultural beliefs. Although Halima is not bothered about not being married, she understands the cultural implications, and there is a feeling that she questions the cultural traditions that dictate her behaviour and decide her future. She confirmed that she smokes and drinks, which is against her cultural beliefs. Whilst Halima is aware of cultural interpretation prohibiting smoking and drinking alcohol, she does not interpret her culture that way.

However, she believes in doing good and freedom of expression. This is something she applies in her everyday interactions with people. Halima manages a honey store alone. She is very knowledgeable about honey. She believes in doing the right thing and holds everyone to a high moral standard. She claimed, *“I really like my*

bosses because they do the right thing and they pay what the honey is worth to the suppliers....I would not work here if they did not have standards.... I would say if you believe in what you're selling, the morality and it is ethical, you will be more confident in your selling". The sentiment about doing the right thing is shared by the owners and has made her job more fulfilling and has created a happy working environment for her. She believes in being reasonable and treating people fairly. She is courteous, selfless, very principled, and honest.

However, her cultural beliefs may be a fusion of traditional Bangladeshi culture and Islamic principles because Bangladesh is a predominantly Muslim country. To reaffirm that she is not religious, she questioned the idea of religion and its beliefs and has the same attitude towards certain aspects of her culture. However, there are shreds of evidence that suggests her display of high moral standards is shaped and influenced by her culture. Notwithstanding, the findings in this study revealed that the moral values of some of the participants are influenced by their various religious organisations. Religion is instrumental in the behaviour of these participants because, in their experiences, several of them demonstrated they live and use their religion as a moral compass to guide and lead the kind of behaviour expected of them by their various religious bodies. The following statement illustrates the experiences of some of the participants.

Ali *"Always, when I give something to the customer, good thing, they always come and approach me, they look for me, wait for me ... Like my life, my religion shows, respect people, kind, give charity, so many thing...I do most of the things for my Islamic way, not in country way, for the Islamic way".*

Malik *“The religion taught me how to be patient, how to be calm when the people aggressive to you, you have to go calm down, and that is how that religion shaped, and that’s what it’s all about”.*

Aminat *“One hundred per cent, I feel like because in Islam charity and giving out is one of our pillars to do..... Giving to charity, giving out food...I feel like our religion always wants us to make our neighbours feel like family”.*

According to the responses, Ali does not see the role of his Indian culture in his life. He acknowledged the existence of cultural beliefs in India. However, he feels that his behaviour and lifestyle are mainly influenced by his Muslim religion. He sees himself first as a Muslim before recognising himself as an Indian. When asked about his Indian culture, he said, *“Yeah, I follow, but main thing we are Muslims first, then India”.* Ali is a very devoted Muslim and only views the world from a Muslim perspective. So, his moral behaviour, understanding and application are informed and guided by religion. His religion has control over his life and dictates and directs every aspect of his behaviour.

Ali follows his religious teachings of kindness, respect, and charity in daily dealing with people. He provides good customer service using his religious principles. He treats all his customers with respect and kindness. He builds trust by selling only quality products and is willing to replace faulty products with new ones in his shop. He will not take a loan because it is a sin in his religion. Further, he said that he does

almost everything in life according to the teachings of Islam, which means his moral behaviour is based on and shaped by Islam. This is interesting because Ali suggests that his culture and the culture of his host country (UK) hardly influence his moral behaviour in any way and that he needs his Islamic religion for sense-making and navigating the world around him and as an instrument for survival.

Also, some participants in this study adopt religious teachings in their lives, too, but less extreme than Ali. They admit religion plays a critical role in their everyday life as they use it to guide against immoral behaviour and seek divine intervention. In their experiences, the participants rely heavily on their religion for guidance in most parts of their life, using it as a daily tool for modelling their behaviour and coping with life challenges. For example, Michael said, "I pray, I ask Allah to protect me to bring customers for me". A narrative reiterated by Ali, he claims he does everything in his life according to his religious beliefs.

Similarly, Gloria responded that she would not have done as much as she has done in her life and be who she is today if not for her faith in God. As a member of Hinduism, Malik emphasises the need for patience in dealing with people and life challenges as instructed by his Hindu beliefs. Furthermore, Aminat alluded that her religion teaches selflessness and encourages members to look out for their neighbours. These are clear indications by the participants of reliance on a supreme being for character-shaping, security, and business prosperity.

These participants have accredited or used their cultural beliefs and religion to explain their moral behaviour and successes in life and business. Their understanding of morality does not come from their culture alone, but from a religious perspective too, because culture and religion are everyday practices for these participants. They

have imbibed their cultural values as reinforced by family and society and moral principles preached by their religious bodies and applied them in their daily activities, as evident in the above statements.

4.4 Benevolence - The show of collectiveness, genuine care, and kindness

The experiences of the leaders of ethnic minority-led micro-businesses in London as it relates to leadership behaviour reveal how the benevolent values of participants are integrated into their everyday behaviour. Most participants showed certain traits of benevolent behaviour as described in chapter three, such as treating employees as family members, being generous and compassionate, and giving one's time and resources to help other people, basically genuinely caring about people. Participants' acts of generosity, compassion and show of care, friendship, and family are key elements of benevolent behaviour. Also, benevolence is one of the three main dimensions of paternalism (Mansur *et al.*, 2017). This demonstrates that the participants place significant importance on benevolence values because they are frequently displayed. Also, these values influence how the participants express themselves and act towards others.

From the responses, some of the participants showed friendship, generosity, and a sense of family to their employees. The participants' harmonious relationship with their employees is built and sustained through acts of kindness, generosity and familism, which they have applied with a sense of duty like it is an obligation. There is an optimism in reciprocity from the employees in the form of respect and obedience, loyalty, and commitment. Being generous and caring to their employees, giving them time and money, treating them like family and forming bonds beyond their work life

into their private life are features of benevolence and are intended to get the best out of their employees. Therefore, building trust and loyalty with employees is fundamental for their businesses to continue to survive and grow because most micro-business seem to operate in a saturated market, increasing competition and chances of failure (Haq, 2015).

In the experience of Gloria, there is a strong sense of friendship and family. She described her experience and relationship with her only employee, whom she sees as a sister and treats like family. The relationship between them is not only contractual but a friendly one with a feeling of moral obligation from Gloria towards her employee. She claimed that her employee is fully committed and contributes greatly to her business. She sees her employee as part of the business, which explains why she would consider and treat her employee like family, and there is an element of trust too.

Gloria "I have given her bonuses, cash bonuses. When we've made you know when we've surpassed and gone above and beyond any daily target..... Yea so I try to recognise her in that way so either by verbally, you know, praising and picking her up but also financially..... Although, yes, she works for me, it does not feel like that, It feels like she is part of the team, it feels like she is part of the business".

Also, Gloria rewards her only employee, both verbally and financially, every time they make a profit or meet their daily target. It feels like a moral obligation, genuine care, and concern because she feels it is the right thing to do. As a devoted and active Christian whose lived experiences are heavily influenced by Christianity, as

confirmed in the interview data, a religion that preaches love and fairness and promotes high moral behaviour is where Gloria gets her inspiration and understanding of her world. So, it is not surprising that she cares for her employee and sees her responsibility towards her employee as a duty because to care, love, respect and embrace another as a family is a behaviour that is expected and central to her religion, Christianity.

Similarly, the findings suggest that the experiences of Hamed and Malik are that of a close-knit family. They both showed certain aspects of benevolence behaviour, generosity, and care. Malik is well involved in the lives of his colleagues who are from different countries and engages in after-work activities with them. They go out to picnics, attend family functions, celebrate birthdays and other holidays, and observe cultural and religious festivals. Also, they share personal and private information and, most importantly, show respect for one another. Malik genuinely cares about the well-being of his colleagues, as he is actively involved in their lives by participating in after-work activities with them because he sees them not only as colleagues at work but as a family too.

Hamed *“You know, like, basically, I will buy my colleagues drinks. I mean, I have grabbed my coke, I will buy them a drink and then you know, like, later during the evening, I’ll buy them another coke drink..... if I am getting something to eat, from going out to getting something to eat, I will be like, do you want a coffee sort of thing”*.

Malik *“As I mentioned, when it comes to personal life, we get together out of our*

working hours or whatever we do, any function or birthday parties or like our religious festivals, they choose to come to our home, or we choose to go there, or if it is summertime we plan the trip, we go to the beaches or something, we enjoying, we building strong relationship apart from this business”.

Also, Hamed was magnanimous towards his colleagues, whom he referred to as a family. They are friendly and playful with each other and work as a team. They are a close-knit group that shares the same ethnicity and religion, which helps to strengthen their bond. Like Hamed said, “it is a small retail store.... you work more as a family than you do as colleagues”. It is evident that they sincerely see and treat each other as family. For example, Hamed constantly gets his colleagues food and drinks whenever he goes out to get himself something to eat or drink. Such behaviour demonstrates generosity, care and a strong sense of family and community, which may be seen or attributed to the revival of his cultural and religious roots. Hamed’s behaviour became more visible as he got more involved in his large Bangladeshi community that promotes togetherness, sharing and support for one another and a strong Muslim community that preaches love and giving, as expatiated in chapter three. This behaviour has long-term consequences as this generous spending can negatively impact business.

In this study, community was identified as a recurring theme. Hamed mentioned the word “community” seventeen times during the interview, suggesting the word community has a special meaning to him. He sees community as an extension of the family, and it gives a sense of belonging, a feeling of being part of something bigger than oneself, like a big family, which Hamed alluded to and benefits from, that is, being

around and working with the group he is with presently. The concept of community is to expatiate the importance of family and people coming together, providing a safe and secure environment and job security, assisting one another in times of personal problems and genuinely caring for each other (Farh & Cheng, 2000).

By community, Hamed was referring to his ethnic group and their unconscious effort to create a safe and enabling environment for members of that ethnicity. He said, “the Asian community, not that we know, we are trying to stick together.” Also, he mentioned the patronage the store enjoys from the local community, which Muslims and people from Bangladesh majorly populate. The store provides personalised service that meets the specific needs of the people in that local community. An example is indigenous foodstuffs from Asia and the Halal meat they sell.

Shopping is not only an act of necessity but a form of socialising for the local community, and it is a way of meeting people. Hamed stated that his mother and sister do their shopping in the store. He described how he met relatives he did not know existed and how he constantly comes across customers who are happy to chat because they understand them and speak their native language. In the process, they ease the language barrier experienced by members of the local community who can only express themselves effectively in their native language because of their limited knowledge of the English language. More importantly, he is working in a more relaxed and supportive environment that is far different from his former fast-paced, high-pressure job.

In addition, a sense of community helped shape the experience of Malik too. He said, “Here we have like Sri Lankan community, that’s why we start up this business around this area..... where I’m staying we do have our own community so we go and

we just socialise with those kind of people so I not feel much different from our country”.

Malik lives and works in a geographical location in London, heavily populated by Sri Lankans and Hindus. His behaviour is influenced by his cultural and religious principles that propagate family, being supportive, respectful, and teamwork, as he indicated in the interview. He has used his cultural values and religious principles to guide his behaviour at work, where he has formed a small community with his colleagues. They have a common goal at work, to do things together and support each other outside and at work. Malik has created a supportive working environment by fostering togetherness and teamwork.

Faith in religion is an interesting discovery from the data that is significant in shaping the benevolence behaviour of participants. In terms of religious influence on the benevolence behaviour of the participants, it is observed that religion is key to their behaviour because it reinforces the need to give charity, care, forgive and love one another. It shapes their experiences in both salient and subtle ways. The participants, Hamed, Ali, Aminat, and Gloria, demonstrated that religion is a way of life for them, not just a religious organisation they attend. In their experiences, some of the participants revealed how significantly important religion is to them, and there is no clear demarcation between their religion and culture because it is integrated into their everyday life. Some of the participants do not recognise that they unconsciously display both their cultural and religious principles and values at the same time. They have managed to merge the two concepts and make them into one.

For example, Gloria consults God for everything in her life, whether private or general. She requests and waits for answers to her personal and business problems

from God before taking any action. Her character is modelled like that of an active religious Christian who believes in being graceful by showing love and treating people right. For example, she mentioned, “Basically, it is like trusting for me, personally, just trusting that God is going to see me through no matter what. So no matter what season I am in, no matter what season I am going through, whether personal or in my business..... I am a woman of faith, so i just trusted that, i laid the plans out to God and he would basically just show me the way forward and he did.”

She accredits all the success in her life to God. She is what she is today because of her faith, and amidst the negative impact brought about by COVID on businesses, Gloria was planning to expand her business because of her faith in God. Her business is doing well, and to her understanding, it is all possible because of God. She said, “I consult with God for everything, God is first in my life, you know.” Her character and behaviour, basically her life, is defined by her religion.

In a similar way, Hamed is using his religious principle to guide his life. He is rediscovering his Islamic roots after returning to his strong Muslim community from working in a major supermarket in East London, which led to a change in attitude and faith. He is more religious than when working for one of the major supermarkets in East London because he kept friends that are not actively religious and outside of his community, which took him far away from his religion and family. He admitted that his friends influenced him.

Hamed *“Leaving was probably the best thing that happened to me, leaving part of my friends, you know, like, was some of the best things that happened to me. I get to spend more time with my daughter now..... My personal experience, I would say I*

made a mess of my life, you know, in terms of who I chose to hang around with, you know, like, my faith was not as strong as it should be”.

He is more actively religious, prays, listens to prayers, and spends more time with family. He asserted that he is at peace with himself and that, through religion, a person can find peace. Due to his newfound faith in Islam, his benevolent behaviour is more pronounced as he has become very generous. A point reemphasised by Ali and Aminat, who are both Muslim. According to Ali, his religion said, “give charity,” and Aminat reiterated the same point that “charity and giving” are core to the teaching of Islam.

The findings illustrate that religion not only has negative implications on the participants and their businesses, but it also positively influences their overall behaviour, also reflects on their businesses. It helps them build a harmonious and conducive working environment where respect, fairness, genuine care, teamwork, and commitment exist. It is evident that these participants use their religion to guide and shape their experiences of benevolence. They willingly apply their religious beliefs that shape their benevolent behaviour in everyday activities. It is a way of life for these participants.

4.5 Authority as experienced in control and power

Authority emerged as one of the four main themes in this study, and it means control. It represents the unwillingness to delegate authority, assertiveness, a show of high self-confidence, act in a dignified manner and provide guidance and direction for improvement (Farh & Cheng, 2000). Authority provides an understanding of the

leadership behaviour of the participants in this study, and several participants' experiences showcase what authority represents to them.

In the data, Gloria alluded that she does not see herself as the boss but as part of the team, and she admits she listens to and takes advice from her employee, but she makes the final decision. She confessed that she is playful but very focused when it comes to her business. She considered her only employee a part of the business. Gloria treats her only employee fairly and with respect.

“If someone wants to observe me in the shop with the employee, i’m quite warm, relax, personable, and i’m not very serious, but i’m serious about my business, i’m serious about what I do. I do not behave in a way that is stern or authoritarian”.

The above statement indicates that Gloria creates a conducive working environment for her only employee to feel loved and appreciated. Although she still asserts her authority over her employee when necessary because it is her business, and she is the boss. She has a unique relationship with her only employee, whom she sees as a family member and treats like a sister. Gloria is friendly but not easily distracted when it involves her business because she is ambitious, motivated, and determined to succeed in her fashion business. She makes sure her authority is established between her and her employee, even though she displays it in a dignified manner.

As a manager, Hamed claimed, he does not attach any relevance to the title manager and does not see himself as the boss but as one of the guys. He is a team

player but assertive. He repeatedly mentioned that he is assertive and works systematically. Nonetheless, they all work as a family, a team with clearly defined roles and responsibilities.

Hamed *"I am very assertive, very assertive, a plan that, you know, like, You have to be mean to be kind or kind to be mean, if that makes sense. Yeah, I am very good. You know, I know how to prioritise my tasks. Like I said, I like to work systematically. So, that helps. Learning from that previous experience"*.

In the interview, He said that he became assertive because of his experience working in a different company where he has not been decisive and authoritative enough, and colleagues took advantage of his laid-back behaviour at work. Now, he is more systematic and assertive in his approach to work. He makes sure that there is a structure and an orderly way of working in the shop. Nevertheless, he still maintains a cordial relationship with his colleagues. He feels mature because he has gained experience from working in a different firm for many years and has brought those experiences to his present job. Although his present work environment is different and more challenging than his former job, he is coping. Being assertive is a sign of confidence, and Hamed has gained self-confidence from his experience.

For Aminat, taking the responsibility of getting things done herself is the right approach. She admits she needs more patience and does not trust anybody else to do the job correctly. She does not feel comfortable delegating duties to anyone, as she would rather do the job herself because she feels she can do it better.

“Sometimes I just go in and do it myself because that is me as a person, I do not like to wait on anybody. I do not have patience too much, so I am just let me just do it and get it over and done with. Sometimes I do not like putting too much responsibility on someone because I feel like if I do it, I will probably do it better. That is how I think of things sometimes”.

Aminat manages her family business with the help of her siblings. As the youngest, she acts like she is in charge. She is hard to impress and cannot stand and watch anyone do any job without interfering because she feels she is the only one who can do the job better. Although she works well in a team, that is, her family. She sometimes comes across as bossy but still listens and plays her role in the family business but will not hesitate to interfere. There is a clear sign of unwillingness to delegate responsibilities by Aminat. She wants everything to be done in a certain way, her way. She feels she must be in control of everything if she expects the job to be done right.

In paternalism, the leader ensures that everyone knows who is in charge (Farh & Cheng, 2000). There is a display of a high level of authority and control. The leader does not like to delegate duties, wants jobs done in a specific way, demands high standards of performance from subordinates and shows high self-esteem. Although Aminat is the youngest, she tells everyone what to do and whom to do it. She prefers to avoid delegating work and acting like the boss. As the youngest, she is loved by everyone in the house and given the liberty to express herself how she feels fit.

Several participants showed a high level of support to their employees and colleagues. They guide and direct them to do well in the firm. For example, Sam is very helpful to his colleagues, especially the new employees. He helps them seamlessly settle into the firm by being patient and showing them how to do their job efficiently. Sam is very enthusiastic about his job because the job is related to his Indian culture. Making Chai tea is a cultural behaviour in India. According to Sam, he has a vast knowledge of making Chai tea.

SAM "Because you know, I make sure that the person who is working show like, if they are slow, I do not mind, I do not expect to be, like if a newcomer, it takes time for them to learn things. I do not expect them to be like me, I do not, because people have their own way of coping with things. When it comes to newcomers, I just make sure that I teach them everything".

Having such tremendous knowledge about Chai tea puts Sam at an advantage in the firm, which is partly why he is the manager. He is a confident man who always wants to be the best but does not use his position of authority to intimidate or control his colleagues because he is also gracious. Sam has mastered the art of balancing authority and benevolence when dealing with subordinates. He is happy to share his knowledge about Chai with new employees and allow them to learn at their own pace, knowing that it takes time to master the process of making Chai tea. Sam is supportive and happy to share his culture with customers and colleagues.

4.6 Summary

This chapter presents the findings and interpretation of the findings to answer the research question. It provides a clear picture of the participant's profile and demographic information and the four identified themes. The chapter also portrays the experiences of participants and the meaning, interpretation and understanding of the experiences by the researcher and participants. This study explored the influence of culture and cultural beliefs on ethnic minority micro-business leaders and their experiences of leading their business in London. This chapter revealed that ethnic minorities are influenced by their cultural and religious beliefs which also informs their leadership approach. Also, this chapter identified four main themes: morality, benevolence, authority, and religion. The four developed main themes shape and influence the participants' experiences. The themes were viewed from a cultural leadership in paternalistic leadership, and the findings developed, supported, and extended extant literature. From the data analysis, a development of the interplay between culture and religion in the lives of the participants was observed as to how influential and vital these two constructs of culture and religion are perceived by the participants.

In this study, culture and religion are the two dominant concepts influencing how the participants display morality, authority, and benevolent behaviour. As seen in some of the experiences shared earlier in this chapter, cultural norms, values, and religious beliefs are constantly and subtly influencing the leadership behaviour of the participants. This suggests that these constructs of culture and religion are instrumental for ethnic minorities in sense-making, understanding, and experiencing life. This phenomenological study has aided a context-specific interpretation and

description of the experiences of the leaders of ethnic minority-led micro-businesses in London in the following chapter.

5. Chapter five: Discussions

This chapter extends the findings from chapter 4 through a discussion to understand the participants' lived experiences on the cultural influence of the leadership style of ethnic minority-led micro-businesses in London using a phenomenology approach. Fifteen semi-structured interviews were conducted with ethnic minority micro-business leaders in London. Four main themes were identified (religion, morality, benevolence, and authority) and discussed in detail, and excerpts from the participants' experiences were applied to support the discussions and justify the themes identified. Then the conclusion, which is the summary of the main points discussed in this chapter.

The findings in this study suggest that culture and religion significantly influence how the participants understand and express the behaviour of morality, benevolence, and authority in their experiences. There is a strong indication that the concepts of national culture and religion are the foundation and core to the participants' lived experiences. They shape and determine how the participants react and interact to their immediate surroundings, while displaying moral, authoritarian, and benevolent behaviours. This is illustrated in Figure 3 below, where the three main behaviours are identified and an arrow showing that both national culture and religion influences all three behaviours.

Figure 3: Framework of Findings

Source: Researcher

In this study, the concept of religion was developed during data analysis. It is not just about the frequency with which it appeared, but the meaning and importance accorded to it by the participants. The analysis in the previous chapter suggests that religion is a significant finding. It showed how influential religion is in the life of several of the participants, and it cuts across the other themes that were developed from this study as shown in figure three. Religion is interwoven into paternalistic leadership, as it is a core feature of paternalistic leadership (Farh & Cheng, 2000). It should be a recognised dimension of paternalistic leadership since it plays an essential role in shaping the behaviour of a paternalistic leader, as demonstrated in figure four. Ethnic minority small businesses endure many challenges to survive in a volatile and highly competitive market (Carter *et al.*, 2015). Many of the participants used religion as a guiding light to navigate through life. They also use it as a survival tool, a sense-making tool, and a torch to direct and guide them through life experiences. Further, religion

can enlighten and explain the leadership behaviour of some participants as they relied upon and practised their religion in every area of their life. According to this study, religion represents any religious affiliation, faith in a supreme or divine being (God) and active participation in religious activities.

It is not surprising that most ethnic minorities are religious because their religious behaviour has been well documented (Crockett & Voas, 2006; Henley, 2017; Nwankwo *et al.*, 2012; Van Buren III *et al.*, 2020). According to Nwankwo *et al.* (2012), Black Africans have always carried, expressed, and practised religion in every area of their life, while in the Middle East, religion is a way of life (Van Buren III *et al.*, 2020). Henley (2017) claimed that Africans and Asians are very religious people who see religion as a significant part of their life. At the same time, Crockett & Voas (2006) mentioned that ethnic minorities are religious.

5.1 Religion as a guiding light

Religious active people factor in their religious morals, norms and values when making decisions in their lives and businesses (Parboteeah *et al.*, 2015). Albeit it is not always straightforward because the strict application of these religious beliefs based on religious scriptures and teachings has implications (Rafiq, 1992). Ethnic minorities are not only religious but also have a rich culture and live in groups. Peace and order are maintained by family or community heads, and as a result, they help build and improve communities. They rely on family and friends for support; notably, they stick together and practise gerontocracy (Henley, 2017; Nwankwo *et al.*, 2012; Van Buren III *et al.*, 2020; Wanasika *et al.*, 2011).

A new form of ethnic minority leadership approach appears to be developing

with the help of religion/culture under the guise of paternalism. This may stir up fresh debate about paternalistic leadership and its dimensions. In the attempt to understand the influence of leadership behaviour of the leaders of ethnic minorities-led micro-businesses in London, a connection between paternalistic leadership style and religion was discovered in this study. The paternalistic leadership approach is culturally bound with traces of spiritual elements in the form of Confucianism, and it is prevalent in ethnic minority societies (Aycan, 2006; Farh & Cheng, 2000; Mansur *et al.*, 2017). Interestingly, religion provides new insight into the dynamics of paternalistic leadership style. Most literature on paternalistic leadership style has been from a culture-specific context (Farh & Cheng, 2000; Aycan, 2006; Mansur *et al.*, 2017). They did not take into consideration the significant influence of religion on paternalistic leadership style, even though paternalistic leadership is based on the ideals of Confucius (Farh & Cheng, 2000).

Confucianism is an ideology that transcends beyond the socio-political relations of society into the spiritual (Aycan, 2006; Chen *et al.*, 2014; Farh & Cheng, 2000). It is considered a religion like other major religious organisations, such as Christianity, Hinduism, and Islam, which helped to tie and integrate religion and culture into one (Tu, 1998). Culture and religion have similar moral values like respect and care. They are not only the foundation of society, but the two concepts are the mechanisms used to guide behaviour and control society at large (Hofstede, 2011; Schein, 2010; Schwartz, 2014; Tu, 1998; Wanasika *et al.*, 2011). Therefore, if paternalistic leadership is a by-product of Confucianism, and Confucianism is a cultural system and a spiritual path, it suggests that paternalistic leadership embodies both cultural and religious values (Farh & Cheng, 2000; Tu, 1998). Hence, it will be appropriate to consider

religion as an integral part of paternalistic leadership as it plays an influential and similar role to culture in society in shaping behaviour (Gaitho, 2019; Gbadamosi, 2015).

Therefore, this study spotlights how paternalistic leadership is situated within a religious foundation as represented in Figure 3. Most of the participants belong to a religious organisation and are actively religious. They conduct their lives and small businesses according to their religious principles and beliefs. The experiences of some participants in this study showed that religion is not just about going to a place of worship but is used as a wheel to steer and negotiate through life. Some participants held on to their religion like a torch to illuminate their path, give them a sense of direction and guide their leadership behaviour and experiences. They use their religion to lead and guide their decisions in their business. The participants pray to God for divine intervention in their businesses, like for an increase in sales. They believe that if they are faithful to God, God will honour or reward them.

In this study, God represents a source of hope to the participants as they use it as a business survival strategy, a consolation during unfavourable events or for the anticipation of a positive result in their business (Gbadamosi, 2015). For example, Hamed, a participant, said that when business is struggling, Muslims say, *Insha Allah*, which means if God wills it, according to the Islamic religion (Altinay *et al.*, 2011). This behaviour by the participants was described by (Altinay *et al.*, 2011) as fatalism, which means believing in fate and destiny. Altinay and colleagues stated that Muslims practise this behaviour, and the phrase *Insha Allah* was used to explain fatalism (Altinay *et al.*, 2011). This concept is supported by (Saroglou, 2011), who stated that Christians also ascribe events to fate because they believe in God.

5.1.1 Leading through Religion

The findings in this study support the claims that religion significantly influences leadership behaviour (Gaitho, 2019; GÜmÜsay, 2019). Gaitho (2019) claimed that religion is the foundation of ethics, morals, and values. Also, personal beliefs are shaped mainly by religion because one of the critical purposes of religion is to guide spiritual and personal beliefs (Gaitho, 2019). He further said that leaders tend to impose their religious beliefs in their leadership styles because of how dominant religion is in life. Similarly, GÜmÜsay (2019) claimed that religion influences leadership experience and behaviour. He recognised the domination of religion in most areas of human life as people use religion as a driver of their lives. Significantly, he suggested that religion should be integrated into leadership theories. According to Fry *et al.* (2017) there is a connection between effective leadership and spiritual practices and values, as integrity, honesty, and humility are regarded as core spiritual values that influence leadership effectiveness.

In line with GÜmÜsay suggestion (GÜmÜsay, 2019), since religion is embedded in the characteristics of paternalistic leadership (Chen *et al.*, 2014; Farh & Cheng, 2000), it should be included as one of the core dimensions of paternalistic leadership. Religion is inconspicuous in paternalistic leadership though it is part of the foundation it stands on - Confucianism. Religion reinforces the need for honesty, respect and obedience through its doctrine and people in a position of power (Parboteeah *et al.*, 2015; Stark, 2001). The leader is expected to care for the followers and be a good example (Mohdali & Pope, 2010). Also, religion dictates members' private and public behaviour through its doctrines (Henley, 2017). As demonstrated above, there is a semblance of these religious processes with the dimensions of

paternalistic leadership. Rituals and rites are prominent in Confucius' beliefs which promote high moral and benevolent behaviour with discipline (authority) to achieve harmony (Tu, 1998). Morality, benevolence, and authority are the three core dimensions of paternalistic leadership (Aycan, 2006; Farh & Cheng, 2000). Also, they are vital principles in culture and religion (Gaitho, 2019; GÜmÜsay, 2019).

The leadership approach of a paternalistic leader relies upon and takes advantage of the existing culture of the people (Aycan, 2006). This leadership approach uses people's culture and religion to lead them because their religion and culture have conditioned their behaviour to listen, obey and follow the leader with little or no resistance. This makes paternalistic leadership more effective in such an environment. A paternalistic leader influences behaviour by caring for subordinates and creating a friendly and family-like environment to achieve established objectives (Aycan, 2006; Farh & Cheng, 2000). Some people make religion the centre of their lives (GÜmÜsay, 2019), and it sums up the experiences of most of the participants in this study. In the experiences shared, some participants displayed absolute reliance and trust in God. They have come to embrace God as the essence of living life. Their behaviour involves applying their religious principles to everything they do. Thus, their leadership approach was shown to be grounded in their religious beliefs, which also represent their culture.

Therefore, this study suggests a connection between religion and leadership and that religion significantly influences leadership behaviour (Gaitho, 2019). It is worth noting that, before religion can have such an influence on anybody, that person must first accept and trust that religion and its beliefs. One cannot believe or follow a religion without faith because faith is the motivation that allows an individual to trust,

accept and imbibe the norms, values, and practices of a religion (Bloom, 2012; Schlessinger, 2007). Trust builds and sustains faith and belief (Bloom, 2012). It is a uniting factor that creates respect and acceptance between followers and leaders. It is understandable now why some of the participants are actively religious and why they uphold and practise their religious beliefs because they trust and have faith in their chosen religion. However, not all participants in this study are religious. Still, they are influenced by religion in one way or the other in their immediate surroundings. Parboteeah *et al.* (2015) claimed that religious influence could be experienced by anybody directly or indirectly through religious values being propagated in society.

5.1.2 My religion my identity

An interesting finding in this study is the use of religion as a form of identification instead of the country of origin. The decision by Hofstede (1983) to exclude religion as a cultural difference from understanding national identity creates a weakness in understanding the national identity of a people, as this study has identified.

This finding is supported by Beyers (2017), as he suggested that religion can be used as a source of identity or used as a cultural identity marker socially or by personal choice. Religion is an important identity marker to most Muslims than ethnicity (Beyers, 2017). This behaviour suggests that religion is a priority and plays a dominant role in the life of the individuals who use it as an identity marker. However, some participants seem oblivious to the role of religion in their lives even though they are actively practising their religion. Religion has become commonplace for them because it is a daily practice and has become a way of life and an identity marker (Beyers, 2017; Van Buren III *et al.*, 2020).

Religion as an identity marker represents strong faith and active participation in a chosen religion. In this study, Gloria strongly believes in her religion and lives her life by her Christian beliefs. She constantly consults with God for almost everything in her life before taking or making any vital decision. She relies tremendously on God for guidance and direction. Her experiences and behaviour suggest that her religion comes first and is an identity marker because it means everything to her. According to GÜmÜsay (2019), individuals cannot associate with a religious organisation if they do not believe in it and practise it (Parboteeah *et al.*, 2015). These participants show devotion and believe in their religion and God. They guide and make sense of their lives with the rules and principles of their religions. In addition, this behaviour implies that the participants are more likely to adhere to and apply their religious beliefs in their business, thereby becoming less receptive to ideas outside of their religion as it relates to their business. According to Gbadamosi (2015), religious people use faith in God as a business survival strategy because they claim to receive feedback from God when they make requests for help in their business, as demonstrated in the previous chapter.

5.1.3 Faith in God

Most of the participants in this study demonstrated strong faith in God. Their success and survival are inextricably linked to God. The concept of God and religion is to give meaning to incomprehensible experiences and future expectations in ways that are not logical and physically observable (Mohdali & Pope, 2010). God is a universal component of religion (Saroglou, 2011) and a fundamental reasoning and the essence of religion (Stark, 2001). God is revered by all who believe in religion and the concept of God (Schlessinger, 2007; Stark, 2001). It is the reason behind religion

and all lives, influencing behaviour and offering reassurance (Van Buren III *et al.*, 2020).

The evidence of faith in God in this study supports the findings of (Gbadamosi, 2015), which suggest that faith in God is used as a survival tool in life and business by African Caribbeans in the UK. He mentioned how African Caribbeans believe that their belief in and commitment to God increased their business, like profits and competitive advantage. It was suggested that the reason for African Caribbean ethnic minority groups turning to God could be that they are searching for answers to the well-known challenges they experienced and still experiencing (Gbadamosi, 2015).

Also, Nwankwo *et al.* (2012) supported the finding in this study as related to God. They asserted that Africans believe in the concept of God, and they (African Christians and Muslims) involve God in everything they do, be it business or otherwise. Just like some of the participants in this study and as detailed in chapter four, God is an everyday activity for them. They use God to make decisions in their business and make sense of their experiences. In views of religion and morality, (Schlessinger, 2007) identified belief in God as a promoter of good moral values and suggested that a high moral behaviour is impossible to learn or attain without the belief in God. Her study showed that the following countries, including Bangladesh, India, and Nigeria, agreed that faith in God influences people and is an essential requirement for good values (Schlessinger, 2007).

However, this behaviour can hurt ethnic minority small businesses in many ways. For instance, strong faith in God can lead to a strict application of religious beliefs and norms. This behaviour can dissuade adherents from listening and accepting support from institutions outside their religion because of their strong faith

in God, which they believe will help them find solutions to all their problems. The participants found it difficult not to see the role of God in everything they do. They give credit to God for everything in their lives and depend on God for direction and protection, as indicated in the analysis chapter. Further, religious practices, such as restrictions, forbidden behaviour, or unacceptable behaviour, can deter members from engaging in specific trades due to their devotion to God because engaging in such trades would mean going against the will of God (Beyers, 2017; Halstead, 2007).

As shown in the previous chapter, the participants' lived experiences simplify and signify trust and faith in their religion. This study suggests that their actions and acts of honesty are based on their religious principles, following what they have been instructed to do as interpreted in their sacred scripture. The participants emphasised the need to be honest in their dealings with people. They claim to sell genuine products and are truthful to their customers about the nature of the products they sell in order not to go against their religious teachings. It is unclear whether this behaviour is strictly influenced by religious beliefs alone. However, what is clear is that this behaviour has spiritual meaning and undertone and is carried out with a purpose. For example, behaviours such as being honest, trustworthy, respectful, and straightforward are believed to be rewarded by God (Halstead, 2007; Marzuki *et al.*, 2012).

Surprisingly, even participants not religious in this study showed signs of being influenced by religion. They uphold some religious principles of the dominant religion in their immediate environment. This evidence collaborates with previous studies asserting that religion strongly influences individuals regardless of their religious beliefs (Parboteeah *et al.*, 2015). Whether a person is religious or not, he or she will be directly or indirectly influenced by the values promoted by the religion in his or her

community or immediate environment. This is possible since religion is integrated into almost every aspect of human life and has become part of the normative system (Parboteeah *et al.*, 2015; Van Buren III *et al.*, 2020). It is practised every day and has systematically become a way of life (Van Buren III *et al.*, 2020), a process of social interaction, control, and support leading to a moral community. Thus, an individual may feel obliged to abide by the norms and values of a community or society in order to remain in good standing or be accepted (Parboteeah *et al.*, 2015).

From an individual level, religion has some form of control over the personal beliefs of participants through trust and faith in their various religions, which goes on to shape their overall behaviour. The data suggest that religion influences personal beliefs and business operations, which supports the findings of (Altinay *et al.*, 2011; Gaitho, 2019). Gaitho (2019) stated that one of the primary purposes of religion is to guide personal and spiritual beliefs. He concluded that religion influences leadership roles and style because the moral behaviour and the visionary aspect of leadership align with religious beliefs and values but caution against extremism. Bloom (2012) agrees that extremism can sometimes result in negative actions, and everyday religious practice can also negatively affect one's life. Altinay *et al.* (2011) did not find any relationship between religion and small business innovativeness, proactiveness and risk-taking but mentioned that religion is one of the key socio-cultural factors that shape values and beliefs. Also, it influences business activities and can negatively influence businesses.

5.1.4 Trusting the process with faith

Religion is beyond just an affiliation. It has a deeper, hermeneutic,

transcendental, and profound meaning to religious people (Halstead, 2007). Some of the participants demonstrated strong faith and a firm commitment to their religion. They followed and applied their religious beliefs as instructed. They showed a high level of morality and benevolence in their dealings with people, in the form of kindness, generosity and honesty, as insisted by their various religions. This uncompromising approach to religion can become problematic when applied in certain aspects of life. Religion may have an obstructive influence on businesses; for example, acquiring a loan is seen as a sin in Islam, and some of the active religious participants in this study will not take a loan because it would mean going against religious beliefs.

According to (Halstead, 2007; Rafiq, 1992), usury or interest on a loan is forbidden in Islam. Interest in loans goes against the Islamic concept of charity and selflessness because God rewards moral and benevolent behaviours. The effect of this behaviour on ethnic minority-led micro-businesses is that if, by any chance, a business owned by a Muslim encounters difficulty or struggles to meet its target due to lack of finance, that business may fail. The reason is that the Muslim owner will not apply for or accept loans that the small business desperately needs to survive from the government or financial institutions based on religious grounds.

The implication of this on ethnic minority-led micro-businesses can be damaging because they will deny themselves and their businesses the financial assistance that is much needed and available to assist their businesses to remain in operation or expand based on religious principles. This behaviour may be tricky to address as the decision to apply or adopt religious beliefs in their business is a conscious decision based on trust and faith in religion. Also, the restrictions imposed by religion on religious people can negatively influence their lives and businesses, like

dietary restrictions and forbidden food and drinks (Marzuki *et al.*, 2012; Rafiq, 1992). The findings of previous studies (Marzuki *et al.*, 2012; Rafiq, 1992) support the revelations in this study about dietary restrictions. Food is more than just a requirement for survival for the participants because it has a symbolic meaning and is entrenched in their religious beliefs (Fischer, 2016).

The participants in this study are from various religions, but the majority are Muslims. So, Muslims have the halal law where they only eat food permitted and consecrated by God (Fischer, 2016; Van Buren III *et al.*, 2020). They forbid the consumption of pork meat or alcoholic drinks. Muslims believe God has revealed what is permissible (halal) and forbidden (haram). Those Muslims who are disciplined enough to follow these provisions made by God are following the moral way of life (Halstead, 2007). Also, Hindus are vegetarians, and they do not eat beef or pork meat because it is considered unclean. Though they are allowed to eat chicken and lamb, most refuse to eat any form or kind of meat (Marzuki *et al.*, 2012). Also, they avoid foods with garlic, onions or any food that will stimulate their senses because it will impede their spiritual experiences (Marzuki *et al.*, 2012). While Sikhs mainly consume meat killed humanely (Fischer, 2016; Marzuki *et al.*, 2012; Rafiq, 1992).

These religious beliefs may explain why the Muslims and a Hindu participant in this study feel obligated to practise their religion in their business because they are following the will of God and selling only food and drinks that are permissible by their religion and God. The interpretations of religious leaders and rules by sacred scriptures determine and guide how to practise religion (Halstead, 2007). Nevertheless, the level of adherence or conformity from followers depends on the degree of faith and devotion the followers have to that religion (Fischer, 2016). This

abstinence or resistance or self-deprivation to certain foods and drinks shows strong devotion by followers who partake in these religious beliefs and practices (Marzuki *et al.*, 2012; Saroglou, 2011).

These restrictions can be conflicting or destructive to businesses as they limit business opportunities and hinder growth, and they are not synonymous only with Muslims. Christians also endure difficulties in addressing the application of religious principles in starting or running their businesses (Marzuki *et al.*, 2012; Porter, 1998). According to Marzuki *et al.* (2012), some Christian sects prohibit alcohol, tobacco, and caffeine, which can hamper business options and influence business survival. Porter (1998) suggested that not all aspects of economic activities or business are considered or confronted in the Christian sacred scripture (Henley, 2017; Porter, 1998). Porter (1998) posed some questions to demonstrate a few conflicting issues of Christian religious beliefs on businesses. For example, is psychological pricing an ethical behaviour? Is paying grease money to expedite a business process wrong? How do business firms survive a competitive environment? Or is using a popular figure in society or a celebrity to promote goods and services wrong? These are some challenges religion poses to businesses, particularly - small businesses, as their target market is volatile and saturated because it requires a small amount of money for a start-up and market entry is easy.

These religious behaviours can be a mitigating factor that can hinder growth and contribute to high business failure in small businesses and ethnic minority-led businesses because religion restricts business opportunities. Also, ethnic minorities use God as the determinant of success or failure, not strategic planning (Nwankwo, 2013). Religion occupies a large part and plays a significant role in the lives of ethnic

minorities (Nwankwo *et al.*, 2012; Van Buren III *et al.*, 2020), as most are religious and live their lives by the rules prescribed by their various religions. These religious rules can discourage entry into some industries and trade and deny owners/managers of ethnic minority-led micro-businesses from taking advantage of other market opportunities available to help their businesses innovate, compete, and survive.

The connection between religion and morality was the mark of cultural advancement (Tilley, 2000). Religion is regarded as a tool for sense-making, coping with uncertainty and a source of moral values for many people. Religion uses morality to reinforce its values and norms (Halsted, 2007; Hofstede, 1983; Saroglou, 2011) and shapes behaviour and attitudes (Bloom, 2012; Stark, 2001). Morality requires us to respect our neighbours and discourage cruel behaviour towards others (Stark, 2001).

5.1.5 Religion as a tool for coping with uncertainty avoidance

The prospect of using religion to address the known and unknown in life is remarkable. Most of the participants in this study are affiliated with different religious bodies, and their level of trust, faith and conviction toward their various religions is extraordinary. As actively religious people, most of the participant's behaviour is tailored to the acceptable behaviour expected of them by their religion. The importance of religion to the participants in this study is in their experiences. Hofstede (1983) claimed that religions provide a feeling of security to people through the messages they preach, which makes uncertainty tolerable. He implied that religion is dominant in strong uncertainty avoidance societies and claims absolute truth (Hofstede, 1983). The findings in this study are consistent with Hofstede (1983), as participants used religion to manage changes and expectations in life, and they have absolute trust in

God, which suggests high uncertainty avoidance.

According to Halstead (2007), fatalism, also believing in fate, prevents Muslim small business owners from taking risks. This Islamic culture encourages a conservative approach to life which can lead to a risk-averse attitude (Halstead, 2007). Religion provides a framework, an understanding and fundamental values that are helpful and valuable during uncertain times (GÜmÜsay, 2019). People use religion as a model of rectitude and a safe umbrella to rely upon during challenging and uncertain times. However, engaging in business activities is a risk, and not taking risks could mean no development or innovation in a business in the area of expansion or diversity. Without business innovation, a small business may remain in a state of stagnation and may dissolve or fail over time.

5.2 Socio-cultural context

5.2.1. Cultural influence on leadership behaviour

In relation to the leadership style of ethnic minority micro-businesses, the findings of morality, benevolence and authority were constructed and are connected to paternalistic leadership. They are also the three core dimensions of paternalistic leadership (Farh & Cheng, 2000). These findings are relevant to understanding the leadership behaviour of the leaders of ethnic minority-led micro-businesses and SMEs. These findings are explored from a cultural perspective using one of the widely used cross-cultural frameworks by scholars in Hofstede cultural dimensions, looking at how culture influences leadership behaviour.

Figure 4. A Model of Paternalistic Leadership

Source: Researcher

This model of paternalistic leadership (figure 4) is an adaptation of Farh & Cheng (2000) and was developed based on the findings in this study, and it proposes that ethnic minority leadership resembles paternalistic leadership. Also, this study suggests that paternalistic leadership has four dimensions: morality, benevolence, authority, and religion, instead of three. These dimensions are the foundation of paternalistic leadership, and there is a constant interplay between the dimensions, as is seen in this study.

5.2.2 Morality as displayed through power distance

The display of morality in this study is centred on respect, trustworthiness and leading by example by the participants. Leadership has a moral dimension, and all leadership is moral leadership because leadership is driven by ideas, values and beliefs that create purpose and followership (Gini, 1997; Northouse, 2021). A moral leader is a driver of moral behaviour and morality is one of the three dimensions of paternalistic leadership (Farh & Cheng, 2000; Gini, 1997). Morality is viewed in this

study as depicted by Farh & Cheng (2000) in chapter two, which includes integrity, which means unselfishness and leading by example. In this study, the participants displayed respect for elders, parents, and subordinates. It is an expected behaviour and core to the cultural norms of the participants, and respect for people falls under the dimension of morality. Morality is the difference between right from wrong and good from bad based on human behaviour and societal values (Ciulla & Ciulla, 2020)

The finding of morality in this study strengthens the claims made by Farh & Cheng (2000) as respect for the hierarchy is an essential social-cultural factor under familism and Confucius values (Farh & Cheng, 2000). Also, in Sub-Saharan African culture, respect for the elderly is an essential cultural practice that shows how integral respect is in shaping and forming people's behaviour (Wanasika *et al.*, 2011). Respect suggests treating people fairly and with care because it is exemplary behaviour that can be emulated, and respect builds trust (Farh & Cheng, 2000). The respect for older people, hierarchy and the practice of gerontocracy creates and confirms power differential. It recognises unequal power distribution and involves unquestioning obedience to instructions and directives, which suggests high power distance and implies paternalistic behaviour (Farh & Cheng, 2000; Wanasika *et al.*, 2011). As demonstrated in the previous chapter, participants exhibited respect for colleagues or subordinates at work to gain their trust and led by example. Others showed respect to elders, and in the form of familism which is a selfless act, family comes first over personal ambitions.

However, morality is different in every society, and it is used to describe socially approved behaviour and the behaviour that is accepted as good or regarded as morally right in a culture or one that is within the prescribed or expected behaviour in

that culture (Benedict, 1934). She claimed that the correct view of moral principles is moral relativism. Also, Mansur *et al.* (2017) found integrity to be a relevant characteristic of paternalistic leaders. It shows the intention behind the actions of a leader when applying care and control. They defined integrity, which replaced morality, as acts according to what is right or fair. In their findings, high integrity suggests a tendency to be selfless. It represents sincerity and trustworthiness (Mansur *et al.*, 2017). Respect is a behaviour perceived to be sincere, right, and fair by the participants in this study based on their experiences.

The lived experiences of the participants, as seen in the analysis chapter in this study, showed they value good moral behaviour - a lack of respect towards people is perceived as terrible behaviour (Shim & Steers, 2012; Wanasika *et al.*, 2011). Respect for all, especially the elderly, not addressing an older person by their first name and being honest are important cultural norms that are required, expected, and regarded as the right or appropriate behaviour for the participants in this study. Malik, Sam, and Halima all demonstrated high level of moral behaviour. Malik cannot call an older person by his or her first name. It is frowned upon by his culture. Sam regularly communicates with his parents mostly to get approval from them before making important decisions in his life. He does not only need their guidance, but it is a cultural practise even though he is an adult. Halima had to sacrifice her personal interest to cater for aged parents when they called for her help. She left everything behind to look after her parents. She said that it is a behaviour that is expected of her by her culture. The actions of these three participants, is a show of respect and an example of the influence of culture on the behaviour of people. Respect is being cultured, and culture influences behaviour. So, their leadership behaviour embodies cultural values which in turn shape their leadership behaviour. It is a sign that someone has had a good

upbringing. A person is a representative of their family, and that person's behaviour is indicative of their family's beliefs. Ethnic minorities hold this cultural practice of respect highly, and in business, it can transform into a good customer experience or service (Wanasika *et al.*, 2011; Wendt *et al.*, 2009). A customer can be a repeat customer due to being treated politely and giving that customer a good experience (Ram *et al.*, 2017). On the other hand, morality in the form of respect can lead to the struggle for power balance between a younger boss and older employees as mentioned above. In most ethnic minority societies, they practise gerontocracy, where older people have what can be described as customary powers (Wanasika *et al.*, 2011). Every younger person is expected to show respect to any older person.

This behaviour is evident in how Sam approaches customers. Sam treats customers politely and shows them respect in interactions with customers. This may explain why customers come from faraway cities such as Birmingham to this shop in London. Further, Malik struggles to balance cultural practice with management. He is a restaurant manager; he has older colleagues from the same ethnicity as him and finds it hard to give them orders or call them by their first name because of his cultural values. Also, Hamed has difficulties telling old customers who haggle a lot why he cannot give them a discount, and sometimes out of respect, he gives them discounts. These behaviours can be a hindrance to growth for these businesses in the long run.

Culture is the primary source of validity of moral rights and rules (Donnelly, 1984), which means that what people assume to be morally right is determined by culture. Morality is culturally relative (Donnelly, 1984; Tilley, 2000), and cultural relativism is particularly about the scope of moral validity but does not support forcing one's moral values onto others (Tilley, 2000). So, this culture of respecting elders and

caring for parents is not a universal practice. It is familiar to people in a particular culture in the world. As suggested by Gini (1997), a moral leader is a person in a position of power who can show other people the difference between right from wrong behaviour and who leads by example. When high moral standards guide a leader's behaviour, followers are likely to establish a close relationship with the leader, and the leader will be seen as a role model (Cheng *et al.*, 2014). High moral behaviour from leaders can produce a high level of trust from followers because it is trustworthy (Cheng *et al.*, 2014; Farh & Cheng, 2000). This behaviour may explain why people accept cultural claims about morality with little or no resistance because they trust and respect the source (Bloom, 2012). Morality in leadership is described as a leader's behaviour that displays high moral standards and integrity through leading by example and unselfish actions (Chen *et al.*, 2011). So, being a moral role model is an essential function of paternalistic leadership, and it is grounded on Confucian ideals that emphasise good morals in government and insist on leadership by virtue (Cheng *et al.*, 2014)

Morality is vital to ethnic minorities as seen in this study and is a universally accepted behaviour (Mansur *et al.*, 2017). The participants exhibited moral behaviour because it is a way of life, an expected behaviour that is assumed to be appropriate or suitable behaviour according to cultural beliefs and society (Hofstede, 2011). Their display of morality suggests a way of life and a paternalistic leadership approach. Moral leadership is described as the behaviour of a leader that shows superior personal virtues that gives legitimacy to the leader and gain respect from subordinates to the leader, and suggests power distance (Farh & Cheng, 2000; Wanasika *et al.*, 2011).

A paternalistic leader is a morally superior individual who leads by example with high moral standards - respect (Chen *et al.*, 2014; Farh & Cheng, 2000). They alluded that the most effective approach to leadership is leadership by virtue and moral example (Farh & Cheng, 2000). A behaviour the participants understand and demonstrate in their business. It is a common theme amongst all participants that may have been shaped by culture. Paternalistic leadership is embedded in the way of life of a people, the beliefs, and rituals of a people, which makes it excel and effective in such an environment (Aycan, 2006; Farh & Cheng, 2000; Pellegrini & Scandura, 2008). It entails treating people fairly and like part of a big family, and where interpersonal relationships are established, paternalistic leaders tend to behave like a father towards employees.

There is a close connection between morality and culture because morality is a function of culture (Tilley, 2000). When people conform to cultural practices by adhering to moral values prescribed by their culture, it helps to sustain that culture (Tilley, 2000). It is described as mental programming (Hofstede, 1983, adapting the behaviour of people in society to the expected behaviour to achieve a common goal. Cultural attitude towards acceptable or moral behaviour has always varied, even in issues that we assume everyone will agree with (Schlessinger, 2007). What is accepted and viewed as morally or ethically right in one culture may not be accepted or seen as morally or ethically right in another culture (Schlessinger, 2007; Tilley, 2000). Looking at morality from a cultural perspective using Hofstede's cultural dimension, a model recognised as the standard for evaluating and understanding cultural aspects of leadership, should assist and identify cultural influences in the leadership behaviour of participants in this study.

There is evidence of high power distance in the experiences of participants in this study, which are incongruent with the power distance in Hofstede's' cultural dimension as described in dimensionalising cultures and in table four (Hofstede, 2011). The participants did not only show respect to elders but their colleagues or subordinates at work. Respect in practice creates and confirms power differential (Farh & Cheng, 2000). It recognises hierarchy and unequal power distribution, which suggest high power distance (Farh & Cheng, 2000). The moral behaviour, such as respect between a boss and subordinates or between a younger person and an older person, as observed in this study, indicates that the participants welcomed and acknowledged hierarchy and is consistent with Hofstede's claims. Unequal power distribution suggests that members of that society value hierarchy and status (Mansur *et al.*, 2017).

Hofstede describes high power distance to include - older people who are both respected and feared. Secondly, parents teach children obedience. He mentioned that Asian and African countries tend to be high on the dimension of power distance, as evident in table four, in chapter three of this study. Power distance is the level of acceptance and expectation of the unequal distribution of power by members of society (Hofstede, 2011), and power inequality conjures submissive behaviour and obedience (Mansur *et al.*, 2017).

According to Farh & Cheng (2000), Confucian values of moral behaviour include respect for the hierarchy of age and responsibility. The consequences of moral behaviour with high power distance on a small business can be seen in the experience of one of the participants in this study. An older employee from the same ethnicity as a younger manager became disruptive at work. The younger manager could not

challenge or question the older employee due to cultural practices like respect for elders. The older employee used culture to undermine the authority of the younger manager based on age difference. The application, practice, or practicality of this kind of behaviour can lead to a toxic working environment devoid of cooperation and, in the long run, cause a strain on the business or total collapse.

Morality informs and guides benevolent behaviour, making it more intricate to separate (Chen *et al.*, 2014). According to Chen *et al.* (2014), moral and benevolent leadership behaviour is trustworthy behaviour that can create a bond and a good relationship between the leader and followers beyond the standard economic contract at work into personal lives. What is permitted or considered as morally right behaviour in one culture maybe considered bad in another culture. Basically, morality is not universally valid (Benedict, 1934).

5.2.3 Benevolence fostering collectivism

The primary concern of a paternalistic leader is the employees' welfare (Chen *et al.*, 2014; Pellegrini & Scandura, 2008), as demonstrated by the participants in different forms. It manifested as genuine concern and care for the well-being of employees, and this behaviour is an act of benevolence (Farh & Cheng, 2000). Benevolence is one of the main dimensions and a core characteristic of paternalism (Farh & Cheng, 2000). It values collectivism (Mansur *et al.*, 2017). It entails that a leader shows care, concern, togetherness, and respect to subordinates. This behaviour of a paternalistic leader is not restricted only to the workplace but to the personal life of employees or subordinates (Cheng *et al.*, 2004).

The dimension of benevolence provides a platform to understand better the leadership behaviour of the leaders of ethnic minority-led micro-businesses. In this

section, the construct of benevolence, as explained by (Farh & Cheng, 2000), is applied to understand the experiences of the participants in this study. The majority of the participants endorsed benevolence. They demonstrated one or multiple aspects of benevolent values in their lives, businesses, and relationships with employees in and outside work, such as treating employees as a family member, being generous and compassionate, and giving one's time and resources to help other people. Also, there is evidence of collectivism in the behaviour of ethnic minority small business owners and managers in London. This shows that the participants place significant importance on benevolent and collective values because they are frequently displayed in their lived experiences shaping how they express themselves and act towards others.

This study suggests that ethnic minorities are benevolent as they display caring, friendly, and supportive behaviour. This finding is supported by Okozi *et al.* (2009) that ethnic minorities adopt a more nurturing, inclusive, and inspiring leadership behaviour. This was the conclusion they reached in research conducted to determine the difference in leadership style between ethnic minority and White supervisors. Okozi and colleagues suggested that ethnic minority leaders have the ability to have a meaningful connection with their subordinates and balance interpersonal skills with humility which sets them apart from other leaders.

Also, in line with the findings in this study and in support of Okozi *et al.* (2009), Mansur *et al.* (2017) confirmed the nurturing and protective behaviour of ethnic minority leaders as they suggested that ethnic minorities endorsed benevolent leadership behaviour in a cross-cultural study on shades of paternalistic leadership. In their study, they had cultural clusters made up of countries from different regions of

the world to study their endorsement of each of the three main dimensions of paternalism. The clusters include Confucian Asia, Middle Eastern, Southeast Asia and Sub-Saharan Africa. These clusters contain countries that make up the majority of the ethnic minority groups in the UK and this study. They all scored high on behaviour aligned with benevolence, such as generosity, the show of concern and friendliness (Mansur *et al.*, 2017).

Consistent with the findings of benevolent behaviour in this study is the findings of (Farh & Cheng, 2000). They described benevolent leadership behaviour to include treating employees as family members, providing job security, assisting during personal crises, and showing holistic concern. Family, teamwork and assisting one another are essential elements in a collectivist society. It provides security and a sense of belonging and makes followership and obedience easy to achieve (Mussolino & Calabrò, 2014). Leaders in collective societies assume the responsibility to care for and make decisions on behalf of their subordinates because they believe it is their duty. Also, they can influence subordinates' personal and work lives as respected figures (Mansur *et al.*, 2017; Mussolino & Calabrò, 2014; Pellegrini & Scandura, 2008;).

Benevolent societies value the dimension of collectivism as the benevolent leader shows kindness, concern, and moderate authority to maintain social control and harmony (Mansur *et al.*, 2017). This view is also supported by Karakas & Sarigollu (2013) as they expect benevolent leadership behaviour to seamlessly suit a collectivist culture due to higher communal sensitivity and community responsiveness. A benevolent leadership behaviour will improve collective performance (Cheng *et al.*, 2014). These findings are consistent with this study as the participants demonstrated

teamwork, subordinates are treated like family members, and the businesses are located in ethnic clusters or communities. The experiences of Gedeon, Halma, Hamed and Gloria in the previous chapter showed benevolence. Gedeon creatively uses benevolence by showing care and concern for his community, which is dear to him. He sells natural products that can improve the lives of people. He works with the community by providing a safe place in his store for free for people who want quiet or want to meditate. Also, he encourages people and small businesses within the community to help them market their products for a small percentage, and by so doing, promoting his products, and experiencing an increase in sales and profit. He displayed genuine care for his customers and the people in his community. Gedeon is not the only one, as Halima has these benevolent principles that guide her everyday life, and she applies them in her business. She genuinely cares for her customers because she believes in treating people right and doing the right. She explains the crowd in the store, and most of her customers are repeat international customers, mostly from Asia. She only sells quality products that are sourced the right way, and her benevolent behaviour is helping the business grow even though the profit is marginal.

Hamed and his colleagues are very close, they have a strong bond and they have formed a small family unit at home. Hamed said every time he goes out to get himself something to eat, he gets something for his colleagues. They openly support each other like Gloria and her employee. Gloria has one employee and treats her like a sister, a family member. They have a unique friendship built on trust and respect that has created a conducive working environment. This behaviour transforms into performance as everyone is happy to come to work, and work with each other and the business reaps the benefits. Hofstede (1983) described collectivism as societies where people belong, are integrated into close-knit in-groups, and continue to enjoy

protection in exchange for unquestioning loyalty. Also, Hofstede claimed that countries such as India, Nigeria, Pakistan, and Bangladesh are all collectivist societies, see table four. Similarly, the GLOBE study collaborates Hofstede's finding that most ethnic minorities originate from collective societies in its socio-cultural practices on the dimension of In-group collectivism.

Moreover, paternalism is common in collectivist societies such as Africa, Asia, Middle East (Farh & Cheng, 2000; Hofstede, 1983; Mansur *et al.*, 2017). Evidence from previous empirical studies supports the suitability and effectiveness of paternalism in collectivist cultures such as China, Indonesia, and Malaysia because it is inherent in their way of life (Aycan, 2006; Farh & Cheng, 2000; Pellegrini & Scandura, 2008). Therefore, paternalism is appropriate or a good fit in a collectivist society as long as the cultural values of that society are in support of it (Mansur *et al.*, 2017).

Further, a benevolent leader displays individualised genuine care and generosity to the well-being of subordinates and, in return, receives respect and loyalty from subordinates (Cheng *et al.*, 2004; Farh & Cheng, 2000; Mansur *et al.*, 2017). Benevolence is regarded as Shi-en, favour granting in China (Cheng *et al.*, 2004). Favour is considered a social investment which carries a handsome return and is expected to be repaid (Cheng *et al.*, 2004). Also, Cheng *et al.* (2004) found benevolence to effectively impact subordinate gratitude and repayment. It encourages high performance and good relationship between the leader and subordinates.

Interestingly, the dynamics of benevolence reflect dualism, two complimentary sides that reveal a symbiotic relationship between the boss and subordinates. The boss provides care and treats subordinates like family. This provides a conducive

working environment for subordinates while subordinates, in return, show respect, loyalty, commitment and performance (Farh & Cheng, 2000). This relationship is described as either benevolent or exploitative paternalism, and the difference is the intention of the paternalistic leader's generosity and employee loyalty (Aycan, 2006). Exploitative benevolence is more transactional, emphasising organisational outcome and subordinates need to show loyalty because of their personal interest. In contrast, benevolent paternalism is genuine care from a leader for his or her subordinates. In return, subordinates show loyalty as a way of expressing gratitude for the sincere generosity and care of the paternalistic leader. Aycan (2006) argued that benevolent paternalism is more effective than exploitative paternalism for forging good relationships and obtaining higher performance and commitment from subordinates.

This tends to be the relationship between subordinates and the leaders of ethnic minority-led micro-businesses in this study. The leaders of ethnic minority-led micro-businesses show care and generosity to their subordinates with an expectation of reciprocity. It fits into the narrative of benevolence (Aycan, 2006; Farh & Cheng, 2000). Just as much as the leaders of ethnic minority-led micro-businesses treat subordinates as family and cater for their wellbeing, they still have a business to operate and strive to make the business a success with the help of their family and employee(s). This supports the idea about the motive behind the care of a paternalistic leader that suggests that there is an expectation to providing care and a conducive working environment from employees (Aycan, 2006; Mansur *et al.*, 2017). So, by caring for employees, the leader expect to inspire and motivate their employees to perform at a higher level.

This benevolent behaviour is not confined to the workplace alone, it extends to the private life of subordinates (Chen *et al.*, 2014). As highlighted above, most of the participants demonstrated a caring and supportive personality and a family environment. They formed close groups and treated each other like family. Personal life and work life are hardly separate as the boss is mostly involved in both. Thus, collectivist culture advances the idea of togetherness, teamwork, a trustworthy environment, harmony, and personalised relationships (Aycan, 2006; Mansur *et al.*, 2017). It is a society where people are born into and belong to strong, cohesive in-groups that provide protection and a sense of belonging in exchange for unquestioning loyalty (Hofstede, 1983; Hofstede *et al.*, 2005).

A benevolent leader approves and accepts collective values such as interdependence, conformity, and responsibilities for others (Mansur *et al.*, 2017). It is true that collective societies have a group consciousness where the group interest is more important than individual goals. It encourages teamwork, and group interaction sustains close relationships and creates a trustworthy environment (Mansur *et al.*, 2017). In a collectivist society, people belong to groups that can be seen as an extension of the family (Mansur *et al.*, 2017). This collective behaviour was visible in the interactions, affiliations, transactions, and socialisation of participants in this study. There were instances where the participants treated their employee(s) like family members. They showed their employees respect and genuine care, two significant features of benevolence (Farh & Cheng, 2000) and their businesses are situated in locations populated by ethnic minorities.

Paternalistic benevolent behaviour does not negatively influence the participants' leadership behaviour, until the consideration and infusion of religion.

Religious beliefs and practices dictate the actions of active religious participants in this study, as elaborated in this chapter and the previous chapter. Benevolence is guided by morality (Chen *et al.*, 2014). Religion heavily influences morality, which suggests that religion influences benevolence (Bloom, 2012; Hofstede, 2011; Parboteeah *et al.*, 2015; Stark, 2001; Van Buren III *et al.*, 2020). Moreover, there is ample evidence in this study that supports this narrative. The participants' acts of benevolence are partly driven by religious beliefs and guidelines in such a way that it has become a way of life.

This reveals a complex interrelationship between benevolence and religion, thus providing a more social perspective of viewing benevolence from a cultural and religious perspective. There are elements of benevolence behaviour in religious beliefs in the reward of good behaviour and the punishment of bad behaviour, as observed in religious scriptures (Halstead, 2007). Schlessinger (2007) claimed that the most benevolent people are those who are involved in one way or the other in religious activities. This suggests that most religious people display benevolence, and benevolent behaviour is guided by morality (Chen *et al.*, 2014). So, as demonstrated, this benevolent behaviour of the participants is not just based on their national culture but influenced by religion too.

Therefore, their expression and interpretation of benevolence are partly based on religious beliefs of kindness and charity. They have endeavoured to satisfy these beliefs by extending them to their businesses. For example, a participant in the hospitality industry serves larger than average portions of food compared to similar food outlets to please customers and conform to religious beliefs despite the fact that it could impact business negatively.

This study suggests that the benevolent behaviour of the leaders of ethnic minority-led micro-businesses in London is a combination of their national culture and religious beliefs as seen in figure three and may be one of the contributing factors to the high rate of failed of micro-businesses in London. This is so because religious practices influence participants to refuse to sell certain products. The participants in the hospitality industry served or gave away more food than usual in the spirit of charity. Some provided long-term credit facilities to customers in the process of expressing kindness and love for neighbours as ordered by their religion. Charity is one of the obligatory religious practices for Muslims (Halstead, 2007). However, this behaviour can ruin a small business, costing them their profit and ability to develop, sustain and survive their volatile and competitive environment (Morrison, 2003). Although this behaviour is done in good faith or intention but bad for business because it is a wasteful and irresponsible way to conduct business. Every business need cash and a good leader to survive.

However, paternalism does not exist without benevolence and authority (Mansur *et al.*, 2017). Paternalism requires care and discipline, which are also benevolence and authority to control and maintain harmony (Farh & Cheng, 2000; Mansur *et al.*, 2017).

5.2.4 Authority as demonstrated through power distance/morality

The dimension of authority has attracted more attention, mostly negative, from Western scholars regarding paternalism (Aycan, 2006; Jackson, 2016). They viewed, mirrored, and compared paternalism with other Western leadership theories (Aycan, 2006), ignoring the dynamics and uniqueness of these leadership approaches. A paternalistic leader maintains authority and expects loyalty and trust from subordinates

(Aycan, 2006). The leader is caring, creates a friendly working environment and is very involved in the private and working lives of subordinates or employees (Aycan, 2006; Farh & Cheng, 2000). Paternalism has been approached from various perspectives and theories by leadership scholars, which has led to the creation of models, frameworks, and dimensions, but authority as a dimension has consistently been present in these models, frameworks, and dimensions (Aycan, 2006; Farh & Cheng, 2000; Mansur *et al.*, 2017). It shows that authority is significant to paternalistic leadership and all leadership concepts.

The meaning of authority used in this study is, as described by (Farh & Cheng, 2000), to include control, unwillingness to delegate responsibility, assertiveness, and self-confidence. Authority is one dimension the participants were crafty about in their responses because there seems to be a negative perception attached to the word authority that the participants did not want to be associated with in this study. They were quick to describe themselves as a team player or part of the team, not the boss. Although, some of their behaviours suggest some form of authority.

The participants in this study do not openly and singularly endorse authority, there is a weak or moderate display of authority as it was mostly combined with benevolence, and the two together form the core of paternalistic leadership behaviour and help define paternalism (Mansur *et al.*, 2017). Mansur and colleagues define the combination of what they called moderate authority and a high level of benevolence as a lighter shade of paternalism. They claimed it is a good fit for societies with high power distance. This best describes the approach of the participants in this study, as they are happy to be benevolent but apply some level of authority to establish control and show they are in charge while maintaining harmony. According to the narrative

shared by Hamed, one of the participants in this study, being assertive was not just a cultural value passed on to him at a young age but also what he learned from life experiences. Farh & Cheng (2000) alluded that a paternalistic leader demands obedience, respect, and loyalty from subordinates. Hamed discovered that being too nice can make a leader look weak, so now he knows when to be friendly and assertive and how to combine authoritarian and benevolence to achieve the best in the workplace. He now knows how to demand respect and obedience.

However, this authoritarian behaviour is proven to be an effective instrument to expedite the accomplishment of organisational goals in resource-strained and challenging environments (Mansur *et al.*, 2017), which seems to be the kind of business environment micro-businesses exist in (Carter *et al.*, 2015; Haq *et al.*, 2023). They are constantly reacting to consumer demands and faced with other challenges like discrimination. Chen *et al.* (2014) agrees with the effectiveness of authoritarian behaviour as they mentioned that an authoritarian leader's success is based on subordinates' obedience. A typical show of authority is being in charge. Peter a participant in this study enjoys being in charge, asserting his authority by giving orders and expecting them to be followed. He joked that his behaviour comes from his line of work and has been vital in meeting customers' expectations, demands and business targets. Also, followers legitimise authority by recognising a leader as an authority and accepting the leader as a leader and a figure of authority (Mansur *et al.*, 2017). Respect for authority or hierarchy is an integral socio-cultural value for ethnic minorities, which makes them submissive and obedient (Mansur *et al.*, 2017; Wanasika *et al.*, 2011).

However, Farh & Cheng (2000) suggest that this is only sometimes the case. They said the broad view of Chinese people being submissive to authority might be correct in a cross-cultural comparative study, but it is not true even though it is an established social value in Chinese culture because there are people in Chinese society who do not view authoritarian behaviour positively. Dickson *et al.* (2003) explained why it is critical to factor individual differences in leadership research before reaching universality in leadership. Further, Farh & Cheng (2000) asserted that power inequality in society, which is also power distance, can determine the level of authority of a leader and suggest appropriate leadership behaviour. For example, in a large power distance society, the right fit or appropriate leadership behaviour will be benevolent leadership behaviour.

Notwithstanding, authority involves the show of power and control by leaders over their followers or subordinates. In return, the followers show loyalty, obedience, and respect to the leader (Farh & Cheng, 2000). It reveals power inequality between the boss and employees. According to Hofstede (1983), the cultural dimension of power distance is associated with the extent to which power or authority is centralised and suggests autocratic leadership behaviour. People try to play down the power inequality in society as much as possible, and there are strong forces that encourage and sustain existing inequalities in society (Hofstede, 1983). Power inequality creates a psychological need for dependency by members without power in society (Hofstede, 1983). It makes the bosses more powerful than they should be because of the dependence of employees or subordinates on their bosses.

Power distance hints at hierarchy and authority (Hofstede, 2011), and religion embraces authority (Stark, 2001), which means there is some form of power distance

in religion. However, there is little to support the idea that religion encourages authoritarian behaviour in this study, although religion has a significant influence on the behaviour of the participants in this study. The participants exhibited and adopted certain leadership behaviours that support and are present in the leadership behaviour under authority (Farh & Cheng, 2000) influenced by religious principles such as providing guidance and expectation of high standards in behaviour and performance (Schlessinger, 2007). It demonstrates a subtle, salient, and positive influence on the authoritarian leadership approach of participants in this study because they led by their religious principles, which promote charity, accountability, togetherness, respect, and honesty (Bloom, 2012; Halstead, 2007; Mohdali & Pope, 2010; Stark, 2001; Van Buren III *et al.*, 2020). Nevertheless, religions have structures with hierarchy and status which come with some form of moral power that suggests superiority and indicates that religion identifies with power distance through moral power, like the hierarchy of priesthood (Hofstede, 2011). Morality is core to religion (Bloom, 2012; Stark, 2001), which means respect for people and authority suggest hierarchy and power distance (Hofstede, 2011; Stark, 2001). Also, this power differential could be interpreted as strict religious rules, regulations and guidelines that are instructions or orders that adherents are supposed to follow obediently with trust and faith without questions (Parboteeah *et al.*, 2015). Even Confucian philosophy promotes central power with legitimate authority for leaders to exercise their duties, which also involve caring for subordinates (Aycaan, 2006; Farh & Cheng, 2000).

One negative aspect of power inequality or authority can be the abuse of power for personal gain, where the leaders of ethnic minority-led micro-businesses can come across as authoritarian. Also, a situation where adherents misinterpret their religious beliefs to justify their actions could lead to extremism (Van Buren III *et al.*, 2020). The

knowledge of having power as a leader and the reliance on the leader for survival by subordinates may encourage the abuse of authority by that leader. It is an area of paternalistic leadership that Western scholars are critical of (Aycan, 2006; Jackson, 2016), but it could be subdued with benevolence (Farh & Cheng, 2000). The benevolent behaviour of a leader discourages the abuse of power for personal gain by the leader showing genuine care and interest in the wellbeing of subordinates (Farh & Cheng, 2000).

In addition, authority from the Confucian perspective portrays a leader as patriarchal (Aycan, 2006; Farh & Cheng, 2000). Power or authority is associated with masculinity (Hofstede, 1983), but a leader can be of any gender. In this study, the gender of the leaders of ethnic minority-led micro-businesses in London is not the focus because any gender can be a leader. So, there is little in this study to support Hofstede's cultural dimension of masculinity and femininity. Hofstede defined masculinity as a society where gender roles are distinct or clearly defined. Men are supposed to display assertiveness, toughness and focus on success. While women are supposed to be tender, caring and focused on life. This study does not support this view, as both the male and female participants showed care and tenderness and were assertive, competitive, and focused on business success. Their gender played little or no role in their leadership behaviour.

Micro-businesses and small businesses need an assertive leader with high confidence and a clear vision to manage the limited resources available to them and make prompt strategic decisions that can elevate the business and give it a competitive advantage over its competitors (Birbirsu & Lakew, 2020). Authority is needed to control, make decisions, and achieve business objectives (Mansur *et al.*,

2017), but measured authority is emphasised by (Farh & Cheng, 2000) as a paternalistic leader do not abuse authority for personal gain and acts as a role model in personal and work life (Farh & Cheng, 2000; Mansur *et al.*, 2017). The nurturing behaviour of ethnic minorities (Okozi *et al.*, 2009) can compensate for their authoritarian behaviour whilst transforming it into benevolence, as seen in this study. This behaviour is observed in the participants as they assert authority with genuine care which corresponds with the description of a paternalistic leader (Farh & Cheng, 2000). Ethnic minority-led businesses and SMEs, in general, are in a fast-paced industry with constant changes in the market. Even with their agility and flexibility, it is a continuous struggle for them to cope and survive a volatile environment. It would be a hit or miss for new businesses, as they either get rewarded or consumed by the market.

Authority is a core dimension of paternalism (Aycan, 2006; Farh & Cheng, 2000; Mansur *et al.*, 2017). Paternalism is a leadership approach that combines authority, benevolence, and morality (Farh & Cheng, 2000; Mansur *et al.*, 2017). The participants in this study have shied away from portraying themselves as displaying authoritarian behaviour. Interestingly, the participants displayed the leadership behaviour of authority in different situations in their daily activities. In this study, most of the participants clearly stated that they make the final decision in their business. Although they claimed to treat their employee(s) right and like family, they suggested that they have a special relationship with their employee(s) based on mutual respect and trust, but when it comes to making important decisions in the business, the boss asserts his or her authority, putting aside friendship. However, as highlighted earlier, only some participants were successful in doing this. Hamed, who has a family-like relationship with his colleagues at work, mentioned he had to be assertive sometimes to get the

job done. Similarly, Gloria, who treats her employee like a sister, suggests that her business is not a joke. Hence, she makes the important decisions in her business, partly with the help of God is the reason for the growth her business is experiencing. Why they distance themselves from authority is not clear. This behaviour may be due to the unfavourable assumption associated with authority by Western scholars (Aycan, 2006; Jackson, 2016).

The paternalistic leadership approach is accepted by the endorsements of the core dimensions of paternalism - morality, benevolence, and authority, including religion by the participants in this study. Also, the findings in this study support the findings of (Aycan, 2006; Farh & Cheng, 2000; Mansur *et al.*, 2017) that the ethnic minority leadership approach is more paternalistic because of their unique cultural setup and dynamism that encourages followership and respect for hierarchy and authority (Aycan, 2006; Farh & Cheng, 2000). It features in their display of respect for people and elders, and leading by example by the participants indicates morality. The show of care, generosity, kindness and treating employees as family suggests benevolence. Authority involves the leaders being assertive, having high expectations and demanding high standards from subordinates because they make the final decision in their business. Also, the participants treated their employees with respect and created a friendly working atmosphere for them to operate. Lastly, religion, on the other hand, involves the application of a supreme being and religious principles and values for sense-making and as a shining light to navigate through life experiences. The theme of religion in this study cuts across the three other themes of morality, benevolence and authority and influences how the participants demonstrate or exhibit them.

Paternalistic leadership relies upon and takes advantage of the existing culture of the people (Aycan, 2006). It uses people's culture and religion to lead them because their religion and culture have conditioned their behaviour to listen, obey and follow the leader with little or no resistance, making paternalistic leadership more effective in such an environment. A paternalistic leader expects subordinates to trust and follow instructions, see the leader as an authority and expect the leader to be involved in their private and working lives (Farh & Cheng, 2000). This is possible when the subordinates are compliant, respect and see the leader as a symbol of authority. Also, the role of a paternalistic leader is to care, nurture, guide and protect.

5.2.5 A perspective of Hofstede and the GLOBE study

This study explored two of the most adopted cultural dimensions of leadership by academics in Hofstede cultural dimension and the GLOBE study to better understand the leadership style or approach of ethnic minority leaders. Out of four Hofstede cultural dimensions, as highlighted in chapter three and table four, the dimension of masculinity and femininity were not explored. The other three, power distance, collectivism and individualism, and uncertainty avoidance were highly accepted and present in the participants' behaviour, as suggested earlier in this chapter. Also, the participants embraced the prescribed six culturally endorsed leadership theories.

However, paternalistic leadership was highly endorsed in this study. With the focus on its three dimensions of morality, benevolence, and authority, of which authority was the least or partially endorsed. Paternalism suits the cultural dynamics of the participants, and the findings in this study support some of the conclusions reached by Hofstede and the GLOBE study. Paternalistic leadership is present in a

collectivist society because of familism and the formation of in-groups. It promotes a hierarchical leadership system through morality and respect for power, status, and age. Followers or subordinates are reliant on the leader, which suggests uncertainty avoidance. Also, looking at the relationship between the GLOBE study and paternalistic leadership. There are aspects of the GLOBE's six culturally endorsed leadership theories in paternalistic leadership (Aycan, 2006; Dorfman *et al.*, 2012; Farh & Cheng, 2000; House *et al.*, 2002). A paternalistic leader inspires subordinates (Charismatic Leadership), establishes a personalised relationship, encourages teamwork, and sees subordinates as a family (Team-Oriented Leadership). The leader is involved in subordinates' personal and work lives and helps them make decisions (Participative leadership), shows support whether it is needed or not, and the leader is generous (Humane-Oriented Leadership). The leader sees it as his duty to protect and care for his subordinates because the leader believes he or she knows what is best for subordinates (Self-Protective), consults subordinates but makes the final decision, and cannot be challenged (Autonomous Leadership).

Further, according to the GLOBE study, the Sub-Saharan Africa group, which includes Nigeria and Sierra Leone and Southern Asia, which consists of Bangladesh, India, Pakistan, Philippines, and Sri Lanka, all scored high in socio-cultural practices on the dimension of In-Group Collectivism, Power Distance and Humane Orientation (House *et al.*, 2002). This means that these countries display care, close family ties, respect, teamwork, and loyalty and demonstrate a high level of acceptance and approval of authority, status privileges and social inequality. They strive to maintain strong family ties, show care, and accept uneven power distribution. Similarly, according to Hofstede's cultural dimension, these countries also highly endorsed or displayed high collectivism and power distance (Hofstede, 1983). The GLOBE findings

collaborate with the findings of (Hofstede, 1983). However, none of the two well-known cultural studies in Hofstede and the GLOBE study explored its influence on paternalistic leadership in non-Western cultures (Jackson, 2016).

5.3 Summary

This chapter discusses and interprets key findings highlighted and presented in the previous chapter. The aim is to examine the lived experiences of the participants and understand their perceptions of their experiences. Also, to explore cultural influence in their daily activities and leadership behaviour while exploring paternalistic leadership.

The findings suggested that the participants are religiously active people, and to them, religion is a socio-cultural activity and practice. Religion and culture are interwoven, and difficult to differentiate because of the similarities in values and norms. So, the participants portray these behaviours simultaneously even though it is displayed in different situations. There is a cultural and religious influence in the participants' behaviour in their display of morality, benevolence, authority, and religious values. Also, this study has demonstrated that there is semblance in the leadership behaviour of the participants with paternalistic leadership. Paternalistic leadership is based on cultural and religious values. In this study, the leadership behaviour of the participants is jointly influenced by their cultural and religious beliefs.

6. Chapter Six: Conclusion

This chapter presents and summarises the major research findings in this study in connection with the research question, aim and objectives, along with research theoretical and practical contributions. It reviews the limitations of this study, reflexivity, and suggest recommendation for further research.

This qualitative phenomenological study aimed to explore the leadership behaviour and cultural influence on the leaders of ethnic minority-led micro-business and their experiences of leading their businesses in London. An interpretive phenomenological analysis was conducted to analyse the lived experiences of 15 participants which yielded valuable insights and enhance the understanding of the cultural influence on the leadership approach of the leaders of ethnic minority-led micro-businesses in London. Four main themes were constructed in this present study, and they were consistent with extant literature. A significant finding of religion altered the existing knowledge on paternalistic leadership theory. This finding contributes to a novel theoretical understanding of paternalistic leadership and offers a different perspective of viewing ethnic minority leadership behaviour.

Religion as a key finding showed how fundamental it is to the well-being of most ethnic minority people, given its integration into their everyday activity. It is a cultural practice, and it is incorporated into every aspect of life both politics and business (Sobolewska *et al.*, 2015). Religion guides and shapes behaviour just like national culture. This study concluded that religion plays an essential role in influencing the behaviour and business activities of the leaders of ethnic minority-led micro-businesses as they showed strong faith in their religion and practise it daily. They rely

on their religion to make sense of their surroundings, and the world around them and navigate through life. This study supports the views of extant literature that suggest that ethnic minorities are religious people, and that religion influences their leadership behaviour (Crockett & Voas, 2006; Gaitho, 2019; Henley, 2017; Nwankwo *et al.*, 2012). For instance, Black Africans have always carried, expressed, and practised religion in every area of their life, while in the Middle East, religion is a way of life. Africans and Asians are very religious people who see religion as a significant part of their life. Therefore, this implies that ethnic minorities are religious people. Also, religion significantly influences the leadership behaviour of religious people. They use their leadership position to express their religious beliefs because it aligns with their leadership aspirations. This study found out that most leaders of ethnic minority-led micro-businesses in London led their business from a religious perspective.

The experiences of religion extend beyond rational reasoning as it helps to fulfil a purpose beyond logic. It creates subjective experiences, meaning and understanding of life and provides a sense of security by reassuring members that all will be well as demonstrated in the previous chapter. However, religion can negatively influence small businesses and may contribute to the high number of failed small businesses as some religious organisation prohibits certain activities, foods and drinks which limits or discourage business opportunities available to their members (Altinay *et al.*, 2011). These prescriptions of acceptable and unacceptable behaviour of members may lead to business failure as members are left with limited but overcrowded business options or opportunities with strong competition to compete with and may discourage entry into specific industries because of extremism, restrictions and forbidden practices imposed on members (Altinay *et al.*, 2011; Bloom,

2012; Fischer, 2016; Gaitho, 2019; Halstead, 2007).

Nevertheless, it is not all doom and gloom regarding religion, as it has its positives that encourage good behaviour and moral order (Altinay *et al.*, 2011; Parboteeah *et al.*, 2015; Schlessinger, 2007; Stark, 2001). It increases productivity, accountability, and a good work ethic (Mohdali & Pope, 2010; Van Buren III *et al.*, 2020) and produces trustworthy, disciplined, and God-fearing leaders (Gaitho, 2019), which are suitable and appropriate for leadership and businesses. Religion should be taken into consideration when attempting to address the challenges of the leaders of ethnic minority micro-businesses as it is a dominant feature in their daily activities as seen in this present study, and it influences their decision making and general behaviour.

Also, the findings in this study suggest that the leaders of ethnic minorities micro-businesses in London displayed and are more receptive to paternalistic leadership style. Paternalistic leadership is a cultural leadership with three main dimensions of morality, benevolence, and authority that guides the actions and behaviour of the leader. It is mostly associated with the indigenous Chinese culture. However, this study enhances the understanding of paternalistic leadership theory with the inclusion of religion. Paternalistic leadership is based on Confucian values, and Confucianism is a cultural system and a spiritual path or a religion, which means paternalistic leadership is based on cultural and religious beliefs. Therefore, based on the knowledge of the presence of religious principle in paternalistic leadership theory and the strong presence of religion in the lived experiences of the participants in this study, the dimensions of paternalistic leadership were expanded to four, from three to include religion, (morality, benevolence, authority, and religion).

Paternalistic leadership is not only a Chinese leadership concept, but also a non-Western leadership that is popular and practised in Africa, and in most of Asia, and South America (Aycan, 2006; Chin, 2013; Farh & Cheng, 2000; Jackson, 2016). Even with such prominence, from a theoretical standpoint, paternalistic leadership is still being ignored with little recognition from Western scholars. This study acknowledges paternalistic leadership theory as a non-Western leadership approach because paternalistic leadership behaviour was frequently displayed and exhibited by the participants in their experiences. According to Chin (2013) it seems there is a bias against paternalistic leadership theory. It is criticised for its authoritarian dimension, labelling it as extreme, even though this dimension of authority is present in all leadership. However, paternalistic leadership theory embodies aspects of most leadership styles which makes it more encompassing or a more rounded leadership suitable for most situations. It is a leadership that combines fatherly benevolence, strict discipline with moral and religious values to achieve its aims and goals in an organisation. Ethnic minorities are open to paternalistic leadership because they are grounded on paternalistic leadership dimensions, even some studies described ethnic minorities as welcoming, respectful, nurturing, inclusive, inspiring, and religious people (Nwankwo *et al.*, 2012; Okozi *et al.*, 2009).

This study suggest that the behaviour of the participants is influenced by their national culture. Culture influence behaviour, and it is used to maintain harmony and stability in society (Hofstede, 2010; Schein, 2010). However, religion plays a similar role as culture in society. In this study, the cultural influence on the leaders of ethnic minority-led micro-businesses in London is made up of a combination of national culture and religious beliefs. These two concepts, culture and religion cannot easily be

separated, and the participants used them interchangeably since culture and religion share similar values and norms (Beyers, 2017). Ethnic minorities are cultural and religious people and religion has a strong cultural presence that makes it more difficult to determine in practice, which one is being displayed at any given time. Therefore, this suggests that cultural and religious beliefs inform and influence their leadership behaviour.

Paternalism is rooted in the spiritual and indigenous culture of a people and asserts care and control to achieve goals and objectives which exemplify the lives of most ethnic minorities (Aycan, 2006; Farh & Cheng, 2000). As such, it is prudent to conclude that the owners and managers of ethnic minority-led micro-businesses managed from an ethnic-cultural perspective which signifies cultural influence. Culture and religion are foundational tools for sustaining society (Hofstede, 2010; Schein, 2010). Also, this study corroborates the findings of Hofstede, and the GLOBE study that ethnic minority people have high collectivism, power distance and uncertainty avoidance, which plays a big role in interpersonal relations and the behaviour or relationship within ethnic groups. Ethnic minorities have respect for hierarchy, they live in communities, form tight-knit groups or a family, and they cater for each other. They like structure and stability as they struggle with uncertainty, so they tend to turn to religion to help manage uncertainty.

Micro-businesses are integral and contribute immensely to the socio-economic advancement of the UK (Hyde, 2022). They create job opportunities, goods and services and revenue for the government. Most ethnic minority businesses are small businesses (Hyde, 2022). Despite their immense economic contribution, they account for most failed businesses in London and the UK. Ethnic minorities need to continue

to diversify and explore new markets away from their ethnic niche market that meet and cater for only the needs of fellow ethnic minorities.

6.1 Theoretical Contribution

This study adds to the numbers of qualitative phenomenological research in leadership as there are limited qualitative phenomenological research in organisational or leadership studies (Ehrich, 2005; Sanders, 1982). There are demands for more qualitative and phenomenological research in social sciences and management studies which includes leadership to advance the development of these areas of research (Ehrich, 2005; Sanders, 1982). Also, there is a relatively small body of literature focused on understanding paternalistic leadership theory and the leadership style of ethnic minorities (Chin, 2013; Jackson, 2016; Okozi *et al.*, 2009; Pellegrini & Scandura, 2008). This present study furthers the understanding of the conceptualisation of paternalistic leadership, as existing literature associate paternalistic leadership mainly to the East with three dimensions of morality, benevolence, and authority. Also, as a non-Western cultural leadership style, paternalistic leadership theory can add to the understanding of the leadership style of ethnic minorities as they are non-Western and embrace and express themselves through their cultural beliefs.

This study looked at the cultural influence on the leadership style of ethnic minority-led micro-businesses in London and found out that ethnic minorities are mostly religious people with a paternalistic leadership style. Interestingly, paternalistic leadership theory embodies elements or aspects of religion which is part of the foundation of paternalism (Aycaan, 2006; Farh & Cheng, 2000). This construct has given paternalistic leadership a new dimension and has created a new approach to

understanding paternalistic leadership. This present study suggests that the dimensions of paternalistic leadership should be four to include religion that is, morality, benevolence, authority, and religion (see Figure 4).

This study contradicts the idea that paternalistic leadership theory is grounded only in the indigenous culture of a people (Aycan, 2006; Farh & Cheng, 2000), as there is evidence that it has religious characteristics. It should not be surprising as paternalism is rooted in Confucian ideals that embrace and integrate religious and cultural beliefs and values (Aycan, 2006; Farh & Cheng, 2000; Tu, 1998). It suggests that religion should be considered one of the dimensions of paternalistic leadership theory. It is unclear why paternalism is assumed to apply only to the East by some Western scholars (Aycan, 2006). Aycan (2006) stated that paternalistic leadership theory has been considered as an instrument for societal development both in the East and West. Paternalistic leadership is not transformational, transactional, situational, servant, or spiritual leadership but a combination of all these leadership approaches as shown in this study in an earlier chapter because it embodies or encompasses elements of these leadership approaches (Cheng *et al.*, 2014; Fry *et al.*, 2017; Pellegrini & Scandura, 2006). A paternalistic leader can demonstrate all or one of its dimensions at any time based on the situation.

Paternalistic leadership has endured and suffered denigration from the West with attention or emphasis on its authoritarian dimension (Aycan, 2006; Jackson, 2016). It has been ignored by Western scholars in cross-cultural studies on leadership even though paternalistic leadership is one of the recognised non-Western cultural leaderships (Dickson *et al.*, 2003; Pellegrini & Scandura, 2008). According to Mansur *et al.* (2017), paternalism without control (authority) and care (benevolence) is not

paternalism. What defines paternalism is the coexistence of control and care (Mansur *et al.*, 2017).

6.2 Practical Implication

The contribution of this study to policy development could impact ethnic minority micro-businesses and small businesses in general. Especially considering the current debate on how disproportionately disadvantaged ethnic minorities are in most sectors of the economy and issues on economic empowerment, diversification, social inclusion, and community regeneration (Kašperová *et al.*, 2022). Therefore, exploring the leadership behaviour and influencing factors such as culture and religion from the participant's point of view will help policy makers. This study showcases and illuminates the lived experiences of the leaders of ethnic minority-led micro-businesses in London, revealing the influence of cultural and religious beliefs on leadership behaviour and the consequences on their businesses.

Based on the present study, a number of recommendations can be made to address the unique dynamics of ethnic minority micro and small businesses within the socio-cultural environment they exist and operate. These recommendations do not offer an instant or definitive solution to the distinct challenges faced by ethnic minority micro-businesses in London. Instead, they represent a long-term strategy that will improve the experiences of the leaders of ethnic minority micro-businesses in London, and it demands strategic planning, dedication, and patience. Implementing these measures will not only enhance the relationship between the government and ethnic minority communities but also contribute to accurate data collection regarding ethnic minority micro and small businesses in London and across the UK. Furthermore, these initiatives will enable the government to leverage its existing relationships with

stakeholders such as religious and financial organisations, aligning their efforts and shared interest to achieve a common goal.

The government, policymakers and financial institutions need to stop offering an umbrella solution to issues or challenges faced by ethnic minority-led micro-businesses. Ethnic minorities are unique in themselves because there are different ethnicities in the term ethnic minority. They experience unique challenges that require a singular and specific approach, not a general one as previous study have shown that ethnic minorities are less likely to engage with external business support (Fadahunsi *et al.*, 2000; Kašperová *et al.*, 2022). According to Kašperová *et al.* (2022), ethnic minorities perceive rejection before they apply for financial support from banks. To address this perception, they suggested that financial institutions review their pre and post application processes to understand how the present process affects ethnic minority customers. The knowledge gained should support finance application processes and improve their relationship with ethnic minority groups.

The government can implement an enlightenment and educational campaign aimed at informing the leaders of ethnic minority micro-business about existing government initiatives and their associated benefits. This initiative would effectively encourage greater participation in government schemes among ethnic minority groups. Also, it should be introduced in areas with a substantial ethnic minority population, particularly within their neighbourhoods and local markets, to maximise the program's impact as most ethnic minority businesses are located in their neighbourhood. Further, an important aspect of this program involves the deployment of well-trained government officials who themselves should belong to ethnic minority groups. These officials would specialise in government schemes and policies

designed to support ethnic minority micro-businesses. Also, having ethnic minority representatives would enhance participation and foster improved relations between ethnic minority communities and the government. This approach would create a sense of trust and comfort among ethnic minority groups, as they can approach someone from their own community whom they trust. The lack of trust between ethnic minorities and the government was experienced during this study. Most individuals within ethnic minority communities approached were reluctant to participate in this study due to the suspicion that I might be affiliated with the UK government.

These ethnic minority government officials should be stationed within the local markets and ethnic minority neighbourhoods. Where they would actively engage with ethnic minority micro and small business leaders by informing and educating them about relevant government schemes and policies available to support ethnic minority businesses. Additionally, they would convey their readiness to assist and address any concerns or questions that the leaders of ethnic minority small businesses may have. This hands-on, community-centred approach is going to enhance awareness, participation, and the overall effectiveness of government initiatives aimed at supporting ethnic minority small businesses and create more job opportunities. Therefore, indirectly addressing the discrimination in the labour market.

Government officials and policymakers should collaborate with religious institutions to connect with ethnic minority micro-business owners and managers, as many of them draw heavily from their religious beliefs for guidance in their business and hold their clergy in high regard as seen in this study. Religious organisations can serve as a valuable channel to promote government initiatives, including educational and awareness programs, aimed at empowering, and informing ethnic minority

business leaders about the available and relevant business support schemes and their benefits to ethnic minority micro and small businesses. By partnering with religious organisations, the government can leverage them as effective instruments to champion its initiatives. These religious groups can play a pivotal role in disseminating information and encouraging ethnic minorities to participate in government schemes designed to support both nascent and established ethnic minority businesses. Also, religious organisations can act as influential platforms for outreach, education, and motivation, ultimately fostering greater engagement and collaboration between ethnic minority communities and government efforts to bolster their business prospects.

This study has highlighted religion as a significant socio-cultural element that is very influential in the lives of the leaders of ethnic minority-led micro-businesses in the UK earlier in this chapter and in previous chapters. Religion influences how people live, lead, interact, and conduct business. So, it is not surprising to discover that religion dictates how the leaders of ethnic minority-led micro-businesses live their lives and operate their businesses, how they source financial support, and the kind of business or industry they operate (Beyers, 2017; Halstead, 2007). The problem with ethnic minority-led micro-businesses is not just about the inability of the leaders to lead or source funds to start, sustain and develop their business but the contentious issue of religion. Religion significantly influences most ethnic minorities, so the government should factor in or consider religious beliefs in policymaking.

Furthermore, the government should actively promote and endorse the establishment of religious commercial banks within ethnic minority communities, ensuring easy accessibility for financial assistance and support in various aspects. This initiative will create a space where these communities feel comfortable engaging,

built on a foundation of trust in the system, especially considering their current unfavourable experience with the government. The issue of unequal treatment, especially concerning access to finance, has been extensively highlighted and emphasised by scholars and commentators (Carter *et al.*, 2015; Love & Roper, 2015). Consequently, it is imperative for the government to increase its investments in addressing this disparity, fostering ethnic minorities' involvement with financial institutions. To address this situation, the government should collaborate closely with commercial banks and credit and loan agencies, facilitating the provision of flexible and affordable loans tailored specifically for small businesses, not limited to ethnic minorities-led micro-businesses. Additionally, establishing a regulatory body to guide, monitor, and enforce any agreements reached in this regard is crucial for its implementation and success in the long term (Kammer *et al.*, 2015; Kašperová *et al.*, 2022).

Moreover, financial institutions should demonstrate their commitment by investing in research to assess the volume and outcomes of applications. Transparency is key; making the collected data accessible would signal a commitment to inclusivity and diversity. Furthermore, this research should extend beyond mere application statistics and encompass other bank-customer interactions, including complaints and lending appeals. By delving into these broader banking experiences, a comprehensive understanding can be gained, shedding light on whether the perceptions held by ethnic minorities regarding banks are rooted in a more extensive context (Kašperová *et al.*, 2022).

In conclusion, it is essential for the government to gather high-quality data on small businesses within ethnic minority communities to make well-informed decisions

and formulate evidence-based policies. Accurate data is paramount for effective planning, as inadequate or outdated information can lead to misguided or unfavourable policy outcomes. Surprisingly, the government's data on ethnic minorities has remained unchanged since 2015 (Hutton, 2022). However, the enlightenment and educational program suggested can help generate more data on ethnic minorities as they will be required to provide some basic information about themselves and businesses as they partake in the program. This proactive step ensures that researchers, government, and policymakers have close to precise figures regarding the number of ethnic minority businesses in the UK. Additionally, the government should engage ethnic minorities in the policy-making process. By participating in these discussions, they can enhance the relevance of the support provided and establish relationships based on trust. Collaborative efforts between ethnic minority communities and policymakers are crucial for developing policies that truly meet the needs of these unique groups and their businesses and foster a supportive environment. (Kašperová *et al.*, 2022).

6.3 Research Limitations

No research is without its limitations, including conducting a qualitative phenomenological study, which involves exploring human experience in their lifeworld. The limitations experienced in this research include time constraints, issues with access, a lack of previous research studies and a global pandemic.

The global pandemic - COVID-19 impacted this research to the point where the research design in this study was adapted from ethnography to the phenomenology research approach. It further disrupted access to participants and transportation (my movement) with government restrictions on movement, social distancing and the

number of people and households allowed to meet or gather outside. The government rules were given good thought in this study, as proper care was taken to protect me and the participants by utilising personal protective equipment (PPE) and keeping my distance when making contact and during the interviews.

Additionally, conducting interviews on the spot, during sales, with distractions, may have impacted the richness of the data. Also, it may have helped produce very rich data because participants did not have time to prepare self-serving answers to the research questions. So, they responded from their hearts and shared raw experiences on the spot. Also, being recorded on a recording device discouraged most participants from participating in this study, and the knowledge of the recording influenced how freely they spoke, which may have impacted the richness of the data collected for this study.

One of the limitations of this study is the research location. This study focuses on ethnic minority-led small businesses in London and this field of study will benefit more from more exhaustive research across the UK as it will have a broader reach and will produce richer data that can provide a more comprehensive description of the experiences of leaders of ethnic minority-led micro-businesses in the UK. However, the representation of ethnic minority groups in London in this study (which is not an accurate representation of ethnic minority micro-businesses in London and the fact that the focus of this study was only on London) further revealed the limitations of this study. Therefore, the findings in this study only reflect the experiences of the leaders of ethnic minority-led micro-businesses in the retail industry, in London and so may vary from other small business leaders in other industries or locations that the data has not been able to capture. However, the aim of this study is not to generalise but

to gain a substantive understanding of the lived experiences of a phenomenon or people. This study did not cover the UK, just some areas in London. Also, it can assist policy-makers in making informed policies and provide data for the government to plan with and ease the execution of the plans.

Finally, is the limitation of non-Western leadership style. The popular leadership approaches promoted today in academic literatures are mostly Western concept of leadership that represent their culture, and some of these leadership approaches are portrayed as an effective and universal leadership approaches (Alves *et al.*, 2006; Ardichvili, 2001; Chin, 2013). There are a few literatures that explore or investigated non-Western leadership styles and its effectiveness in non-Western organisations and cultures. This made it more difficult for this study to examine the leadership approach of the leaders of ethnic minority-led micro-businesses in London.

Paternalistic leadership is established in the traditional Chinese system and Confucius's values underpin it. It is a recognised non-Western leadership style that is still very relevant at present, but it may not be a true reflection of the cultural system of other nations (Chin, 2013; Jackson, 2016). Notwithstanding, there may be similarities between the Chinese cultural beliefs and that of societies across the world that may suggest (the practice of) paternalistic leadership (Aycan, 2006; Chen *et al.*, 2014; Farh & Cheng, 2000; Jackson, 2016; Pellegrini & Scandura, 2008; Wanasika *et al.*, 2011). More studies on paternalistic leadership outside Asia are required to know its relevance, application, and effectiveness in other societies.

6.4 Reflexivity

As an ethnic minority with prior knowledge about the research topic, which guided the research interview questions for this study, it may suggest some form of bias. Also, with time spent immersing myself in this study, I acknowledge it will be difficult to distance myself from this study because of the need to explore, understand, interpret, and capture the lived experiences of the participants. According to Finlay (2013), in the phenomenological study, the researcher finds it difficult to separate from the phenomenon being studied because to achieve a good understanding of a phenomenon, the researcher needs to engage with, immerse in and be receptive to new knowledge about the phenomenon. However, doing this study has improved my knowledge about conducting research. It has aroused my interest in micro-businesses and leadership as I knew nothing of paternalistic leadership until this study, and my understanding of the challenges of ethnic minority micro-businesses was myopic.

Although, I found it challenging at times during the research process, especially the analysis chapter, which created doubt and made me question my ability to complete this research. However, I am grateful for the experience and the in-depth knowledge I gained about ethnic minorities and their challenges. Also, the global pandemic directly affected the research approach of this study. It was changed from ethnography to phenomenology in a short period of time, and I am very grateful to my supervisor, who suggested I have a backup plan in case the pandemic got worse, and it did.

Also, I underestimated access to the leaders of ethnic minority-led micro-businesses in London. As an ethnic minority person, myself, I envisaged easy access into ethnic minority communities. However, I got a reality check as most ethnic minority

micro-business leaders I approached were highly suspicious of my true intentions. They were reluctant to partake in this research because they were not convinced, I was carrying out a research study to fulfil my school commitment, even though I showed them all the necessary documents to prove I was a doctoral student. Their suspicion made it more difficult than expected to recruit participants for this study. I feel like the knowledge gained from carrying out this study has improved my interest and given me an overview of the experiences of ethnic minority micro-businesses in London. Also, it has increased my appreciation of research studies generally.

6.5 Recommendations for Further Research

The findings in this study have raised more questions about the leadership approach of the leaders of ethnic minority-led micro-businesses. Also, the limitations of this study provide a chance for further research. The leadership approach of ethnic minorities away from small businesses in the retail industry in London should be explored to have a good perspective on the leadership behaviour of ethnic minorities in the UK. All stakeholders will benefit from broader research on the leadership style of ethnic minorities in the UK as it will provide a richer insight into their behavioural pattern which both the government and policy makers can utilise to construct inform policies. Also, ethnic minority small businesses have suffered discrimination in different forms that have impeded their growth and slowed them down in reaching their full potential. Therefore, based on this fact, future studies should embark on an assessment of what government policies have been put in place to revive ethnic minority-owned or managed businesses in London, post Covid-19 and how successful these businesses have been as a result of the newly developed policies in their favour.

Relatedly, future research works can be centred on finding out the impact of religious financial institutions on ethnic businesses in London. Such a study can provide a blueprint on how to incorporate religious banks into the banking system of the UK and enlighten people on the challenges and complexity of practising religion as well as conducting business. Also, it will provide an avenue and ease the worries of religious leaders of micro-business from going against their religious beliefs while doing business. This is because access to finance is one area that has been well documented, identified and emphasised by scholars or commentators that needs addressing by the government. Also, many leaders of ethnic minority-led micro-businesses in London are religious.

Lastly, since religion is a significant socio-cultural element that is very influential in the lives of the leaders of ethnic minority-led micro-businesses, future studies should explore the influence of religion on the performance and leadership approach of ethnic minority-led micro-businesses. Also, future research regarding the presence of religion on paternalism is needed as it will extend knowledge in leadership and cross-cultural leadership studies. The reason is that religion influences how individuals from diverse ethnicities live, lead, and interact with people and conduct business. Through such a study, business owners and managers would be well informed about the influence of their leadership approach on their businesses and be in a good position to lead their enterprises into the future more easily.

7. References

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8. Appendices

Appendix A. Sample of consent form

Participant No.

CONSENT FORM

How does the leadership style of owner/managers of ethnic minority SMEs impact their business?

Etemah O. Jeff

The University of the West of Scotland

School of Business and Creative Industry

You are invited to take part in this research study for the purpose of collecting data on the leadership style of owner/managers of ethnic minority-led SMEs with less than 10 staff, in the retail industry and in London.

Before you decide to take part, you must **read the accompanying Participant Information Sheet.**

Please do not hesitate to ask questions if anything is unclear or if you would like more information about any aspect of this research. It is important that you feel able to take the necessary time to decide whether or not you wish to take part.

If you are happy to participate, please confirm your consent by circling YES against each of the below statements and then signing and dating the form as a participant.

1	I confirm that I have read and understood the <u>Participant Information Sheet</u> for the above study and have had the opportunity to ask questions	YES	NO
2	I understand my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw my data, without giving a reason, by contacting the lead researcher and the Research Support Office <u>at any time</u> until the date specified in the Participant Information Sheet	YES	NO
3	I have noted down my participant number (top left of this Consent Form) which may be required by the lead researcher if I wish to withdraw from the study	YES	NO
4	I understand that all the information I provide will be held securely and treated confidentially	YES	NO
5	I am happy for the information I provide to be used (anonymously) in academic papers and other formal research outputs	YES	NO
6	I am happy for the interview to be <u>audio recorded</u>	YES	NO

7	I agree to take part in the above study	YES	NO
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Thank you for your participation in this study. Your help is very much appreciated.

Participant's Name	Date	Signature
Researcher	Date	Signature

Appendix B. A sample of participant information sheet

PARTICIPANT INFORMATION SHEET

What is the purpose of the study?

The purpose of this study is to gain an understanding of the effect of the leadership style of owner/managers of ethnic minority-led businesses.

Why have I been chosen to take part?

You are invited to participate in this study because you are an owner/manager of ethnic minority-led business in the retail sector in London with less than 10 employees.

What are the possible benefits of taking part in this study?

There may be no direct benefit from taking part in this research. However, you may benefit from the experiences and information you give as they will provide a better understanding of the leadership styles of ethnic minority-led SMEs and inform policy makers of your needs. It is expected that this will help make leadership a focus to owner/managers of ethnic minority-led businesses and inform future policies.

Are there any risks associated with taking part?

There are no significant risks associated with your participation in this research. This research has been approved through The University of the West of Scotland formal research ethics procedures. It is almost impossible to identify all potential risks in a research procedure till the researcher enters the field. Although the present global pandemic COVID-19, is a potential health risk and all national guidelines and instructions will be judiciously followed. If interviews cannot be achieved online, then measures such as face covering, social distancing and hand sanitiser will be strictly observed for your safety in the course of this research.

Do I have to take part in this study?

Your participation in this study is strictly voluntary. But if you decide not to participate in this study, you can exercise your right to withdraw your consent at any time without duress or penalty.

What will happen to me if I decide to take part?

If you decide to take part in this research, you will be asked questions about the effect of your leadership style on your business. The interview will take place either online or at your preferred location and time. Preferably, we would like to audio record your responses and will require your consent for this and the location should be in a fairly quiet place. The interview should last for sixty minutes (60mins).

Data Protection and Confidentiality

All data gathered about you during this study will be kept strictly confidential and processed in accordance with the general Data Protection Regulation 2016 (GDPR) and the Data Protection Act 2018. Your data will be anonymised and referred to by a unique participant number rather than name. If you consent to being audio recorded, all recording will be destroyed once they have been transcribed. Your data will be viewed by the researcher/research supervisors and school board.

What will happen with the result of the study?

The result of this study will be summarised in published articles, reports, and presentations. Major findings will be made anonymous in any formal output unless we have your prior written permission to attribute them to you by name.

Making a Complaint

If you are unhappy with any aspect of this research, please first contact the lead researcher, Dr Karen Maher. If you still have concerns and wish to make a formal complaint, please write to:

Name: Dr Karen Maher

Position: Lead Supervisor

The University of the West of Scotland

London Campus

235 Southwark Bridge Road

London.

SE1 6NP

Email: [REDACTED] Personal details withheld.

In your complaint letter, please provide the name of the researcher and detail the nature of the complaint.

Appendix C. A sample of research questions

Interview Questions

Background

1. Can you tell me about yourself and your reason for starting this firm?

Pick up questions:

- 1a. How long has it been active?
2. Can you describe your experience as a business owner?
 - 2a. How would you describe your business today?
3. Can you tell me about your typical day at work?

Employee Relationships

4. How many employees do you have working for you?

Pick up questions:

- 4a. How long have they been working for you?
- 4b. How would you describe how your employees view you?
- 4c. From your point of view, how committed are your employees to your firm?
5. Can you please tell me about the relationship between you and your employees?

6. How involved are you in the life of your employees?

Business Success

7. What is your definition of business success? How will you know if your business has achieved that?

8. Can you tell me of anything you have done to improve your business?

9. How would you describe government support to your business?

9a. Have you taken out any government support? And why?

10. Can you tell me if you have approached family and friends for support in your business? Why?

11. Can you tell me why you chose the location for your business?

Ethnicity/Culture and Religion

12. Would you say you have a religion or faith?

Pick up:

12a. Can you tell me a little bit about how this shapes your beliefs in life?

12b. How would you describe the influence of your belief in your business?

13. How would you describe your ethnicity?

13a. Please give an example of how your ethnicity impacts your firm and life?

13b. Can you describe your relationship with people from the same ethnic group?

14. Can you tell me how dominant your national culture is in your life? why?

Leadership

15. Can you tell me how you manage a challenging situation in your business?

Pick up question:

15a. Have you ever had to fire an employee? What happened that led to that point? What happened afterwards?

16. Can you describe your appraisal process?

16a. How would you describe your reward system?

17. Can you describe your power of authority in your firm as the boss?

17a. Can you tell me how you manage your business?

17b. How would describe your ability to assign duties?

18. Can you give me an example of when you have had to make a strategic decision/operational decision?

18a. Can you describe your employees' involvement in decision making?

18b. How would you describe your approach to achieving set goals for your business?

18c. Would you describe yourself as a team player? Why? Can you give an example when you acted in team spirit?

19. Can you tell me a little about your business policies?

20. Are you aware of gender equality? How have you applied it in your business?

Appendix D. A sample of conducted interview

Interviewer

So, hello, nice to meet you. I'm Jeff. Can you confirm that you've read through the participant document?

Res.

Yes, I have read through it and I consent to thank you very much.

Interviewer

Can you tell me about yourself?

Res.

Okay. So, I'm from Bangladesh. I came here when I was seven, started into college, and then started working in retail and management for a major UK supermarket and then moved over here to support my brother with the local business.

Interviewer

Is this a family business?

Res.

My brother's got a partnership with a couple of his friends and yeah, just to try and support basically in terms of admin, and whatnot.

Interviewer

How long has this place been active?

Res.

My brother took over about seven months ago. Yeah.

Interviewer

So, before him?

Res.

This place has been active for about nine years. 10 years? About 10 years. Yeah. So previous owners, obviously. Yeah, it was turned to a grocery shop about 10 years ago, roughly.

Interviewer

Yeah. So, you're basically like the manager?

Res.

Yeah, I suppose you could say that. As seen as my colleague over there decides to take the Meek out of me, calls me the manager when I'm really not just support, I guess. Yeah. Yeah.

Interviewer

Can you describe your experience as the manager here so far? For the period you've been here, how has your experience been?

Res.

Been from a retail background where I used to work at Sainsbury's is very different. Asian community likes to haggle a lot in our prices.

You know, like, you get generally, the service around here you know like the customers, they're more friendly.

Local community, you know, like they come in to support the local businesses. So, they'll come in to do like their daily shopping and regular shopping, they'll come in, have a chat and whatnot.

Yeah, it's tough environment to be in. Seen as you got a lot of competition. So you've got right across the road, you've got someone over there, then, you know, you go up there, you know like we've got quite a few, quite a few retailers. So, it's not exactly. Yeah. It's true. Yeah. Okay.

Interviewer

How would you describe business today? How has it been today?

Res. 2:52

Depending on weather, depending on weather, and depending on the time, you know, like, today, it's been okay. You know, you get moments of busy buzz otherwise, you know, like, you get a lot of downtime as well. Yeah. It depends on the community, so, you know, like, nine o'clock in the morning, so, like I said, it's based on the local community. You get busy spots in the morning, so when the moms drop off their kids, and then the same thing in the afternoon about 3:15 you'll get the same thing where you know, like, the moms will come and do their shopping and whatnot.

Interviewer

Basically, is that like your typical day?

Res.

Yeah, pretty much a typical day, Saturdays, and Sundays the trade starts on the later part.

Yeah, probably after lunchtime, and yeah.

Interviewer

Alright, so the next question is about employees. Yeah.

How many employees do you have here?

Res.

5 five Yeah.

Interviewer

So how long have they been working?

Res.

We've got a colleague that started about two weeks ago. Jubarl has been part of this building. He is as old as this building, right? No, not really. No, Jubarl has got the most experience out of all of us, about eight years I think? eight years? Five, six years. So, my apologies. Five or six years, I've been a month and a bit. And my brother took over for about seven months. Yeah.

Interviewer

Thank you. So how would you describe how your employees or colleagues see you as the manager?

Res.

Waste of space no. Because of the management style, you know, like, it's more trade intense for me, you know, like, I had to look after our whole store. We're talking about nearly a million pounds store. A supermarket was one of their trading managers, which basically meant the shop floor was my responsibility. So, Oh. Yeah. Yes. So yeah, the trade intensity is so different. My management style was a bit more, you know, like, how would i best describe it? People used to see me, you know, like, in one corner, the next minute, they see me in another corner, you know, like, having to trade the whole shop floor, its big space.

So, yeah, definitely something you know, like, it's changed. It's changed. I'm not the same person I was. And I'm still learning how to, I guess, negotiate, navigate with the local community? I find it a little bit more different.

My Bengali isn't very good. Yeah. So, you know, there's times where I don't understand something where the customer wants something. So, I'd be calling him about 100 times a day, you know, like, oh, gee, I don't understand this sort of thing.

Yeah. I think if you had to ask my colleagues, what they think of me, you know, they'd say I'm learning how the, you know like how local small retail store works, basically. Yeah.

Appendix E. Coding Sample

Interview	Theme 1	Theme 2	Theme 3	Main Theme
<p>Interviewer</p> <p>Would you say you have a religion or faith?</p> <p>Res. Gloria</p> <p>I am a Christian. I have faith, i have a very strong faith. I wouldn't have done as much as i've done if it wasn't for my faith in God and putting my faith into action.</p>	<p>Actively religious with strong faith in God. Religious affiliation and believed her success are due to God and her belief in God.</p>	<p>Religious affiliation, strong faith in God</p>	<p>Religious influence</p>	<p>Religion</p>
<p>Interviewer</p> <p>Okay. We'll just move on from that. So, can you tell me what's the relationship between you and your employees?</p>				

<p>Res. Hamed</p> <p>Okay, it's very good. We have a friendly conversation, we can banter a lot and you know, like, was just take the Meek out of each other, a colleague over there would be like, Oh, you're the boss and I'm like, I'm not the boss. There is support, yeah, so you know, like, the relationship is really good.</p>	<p>There is a show of care, friendship, and playfulness. They work together as a team. They treat each other as a big family that looks out for each other.</p>	<p>Presence of camaraderie, care, friendship, and teamwork. It provides for a conducive working environment.</p>	<p>Genuine care and family atmosphere at place of work.</p>	<p>Benevolence</p>
<p>Interviewer</p> <p>So, can you tell me anything you've done to improve your business?</p> <p>Res. Michael.</p> <p>You have to be straightforward with people, you have take control your customer talk to them nice, don't be arrogant with them, don't be stupid with them, make them feel like they</p>	<p>Respect for people and customers. Treating people and customers right and being</p>	<p>His honest behaviour is a highly held virtue that is important to him and his</p>	<p>Moral behaviour key for business</p>	<p>Morality</p>

<p>are human being because it's not only you doing this business, thousands of people are doing this business.</p>	<p>honest to them to gain trust and patronage.</p>	<p>business.</p>		
<p>Interviewer</p> <p>As a manager, how would you describe it? Your power of authority?</p> <p>Res. Malik</p> <p>So I feel myself ok any problem there I have to face it, I have to make sure that staff are really doing and they're following according to the procedure and staff they giving the respect to me as I'm the manager and any problem they coming and approaching me and they asking and before they making any decision they come to me and</p>	<p>He is incharge and wants to know and approve every decision before there are made. He has the final decision as the boss. He has a hands-on approach and</p>	<p>He is the boss, demand respect and wants to be in the known all the time.</p>	<p>Show of authority</p>	<p>Authority</p>

<p>getting idea or asking me first like can we do those kind of decision, can we take this kind of decision at the end yeah. So, it's everything's finalising by me.</p>	<p>demand respect from his subordinates. Ensures everyone follows the business rules and regulations.</p>			
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